

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

ALLINTERACT

Report 2:

“Initiatives which are making societal actors aware of the scientific research that led to the solutions they appreciate”

March 2022

Project Number: 872396

Project Acronym: ALLINTERACT

Project title: Widening and diversifying citizen engagement in science

Executive Summary

1. Introduction

ALLINTERACT, Widening and diversifying citizen engagement in science is a Horizon 2020 project that aims on the one hand, to create new knowledge about how to transform potential citizen participation in science into actual engagement in scientific research with social impact and on the other hand to discover new ways to engage societal actors in research, including young citizens (16-29 years old) and vulnerable groups that have traditionally been marginalized from science (e.g., low socioeconomic background, ethnic and religious minorities, women, LGBTQI). In order to achieve this twofold overall objective, six specific objectives were established. This report aims to respond to objective O2) to explore the **initiatives** that are already making **societal actors aware of the connection between the solutions they appreciate and the scientific research** that led to them. This is done in the framework of two Sustainable Development Goals –Quality Education and Gender Equality – and with a mixed method approach, by using a literature review, analytics of social media, communicative focus groups and a survey.

2. Methodology

The data collection in WP2 consisted of several tasks and the implementation of different techniques:

1. A systematic review of scientific and grey literature. Scientific papers indexed in Web of Science (mainly in those journals indexed in Journal Citation Reports) and Scopus were explored, as well as relevant reports from EU-funded research projects and official EU documents with relevant contributions to the topics under review. The search was made under specific keywords on gender and education in Q1 and Q2 journals. As a result of this process, 4 articles with focus on Gender and 10 articles with focus on Education were reviewed.
2. Social Media Analytics of citizens' interactions on the targeted areas (quality education and gender equality) was based on the Social Impact in Social Media methodology (Pulido et al., 2018)¹, which allows access to the social impact of science. This research conducted a quantitative and qualitative analysis under both a bottom-up and top-down strategy, that lead to the extraction of 3,565 messages, from which 506 messages (262 in gender and 244 in education) were discarded from the analysis. The final sample included a total of 3,059 messages.
3. 12 FG (6 on gender/6 on education) were conducted as part of WP1, on which topic b) "Citizen awareness of the impact of scientific research" was discussed. FG followed the guidelines established in the Focus Group protocol of the project, as well as the individual and collective protection measures based in the country due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Focus groups in gender included the selection of different profiles of participants: Women (including vulnerable women) from a women's group; Members of an LGBTQI group; Women (including young women) from a women's group. Focus groups in education include the selection of different profiles of participants: Parents; Teachers; Students. FG were divided into an Experimental Group and a Control Group, since the focus groups not only serve to collect

¹ Pulido, C. M., Redondo-Sama, G., Sordé-Martí, T., & Flecha, R. (2018). Social impact in social media: A new method to evaluate the social impact of research. *PloS one*, 13(8).

information on the project's objective, but as pre- and post- test to the actions to replicate in WP5.

4. A survey on the European population aimed at analysing which awareness-raising initiatives and actions are enhancing citizen participation in science, including that of vulnerable groups and young citizens, as well as the recruitment of new talent for science.

The aforementioned tasks have contributed to the achievement of all objectives of the project.

3. Results

The following part of this Executive Summary include the main results obtained after the implementation of the four techniques (Literature Review, Social Media Analytics, Focus Group, and Survey) conducted within ALLINTERACT's project to respond to O2: 1) gender at the core of scientific research, 2) science targeting different social groups, 3) Social Media to engage with different social actors, 4) Science with power to transform people's lives and 5) Fake news and hoaxes.

Gender at the core of scientific research

Literature showcases that when gender is not included in research activities – whether in groups composition or field of intervention, results will be overlooking a factor that can change results or the way a project is conducted. In gender, identified initiatives were public, predominantly national, top-down and mostly focused on education. Three specific audiences were identified after reviewing the initiatives: Public universities (37%), researchers (38%), and academics (25%).

Science targeting different social groups

Existing scientific literature highlights that the biggest number of initiatives correspond to the “Top-Down” category (6), whereas the other three were classified as “Bottom-Up”. Similarly, SMA showcases that most of the initiatives did not target specifically any group. However, some of the interventions were addressed to specific social actors, such as teaching staff, children and youth or policymakers. In FG, participants declared that participation in the discussion of everyday topics with scientific evidence increases self-confidence in people who are not used to get involved in these matters or do not have the right tools or platforms to get access to. Thus, we conclude that disseminating the social impact of science is important. In the same line, survey results showcase those respondents who interacted with science through both analysed interactions (living a situation that changed their mind about science and following a scientist on social media) were more likely to receive information about scientific results on gender and education. Therefore, it is important to create initiatives that can become a space in where different audiences can interact, so new ideas and knowledge can come up as a result.

Social Media to engage with different social actors

The importance of social media in science has been identified in all data collection techniques. On the one hand, quantitative results from SMA showcase that in all the cases except one (Facebook, education), more than half of the messages included the access to some type of scientific evidence (including supposed and certified evidence). Similarly, survey participants expressed that in both, gender and education, the most common communication tool used to receive information about scientific research were social networks (14.1% and 12.7%). On the other hand, qualitative data supports this finding. For instance, women participants in FG declared to rely more on social media

compared to people from older ages and SMCO results showcase that scientific argumentation has fostered participation and virtual dialogue among users on concepts of education and/or gender.

Science with power to transform people's lives

A wide majority of citizens interactions on social media included transformative examples of initiatives that were increasing citizens' awareness of the social impact of research. In the same vein, FG results showcase that science is recognized as very important for people's lives, especially in fields such as medicine. Scientific research is also perceived as a key element to re-configure some social beliefs, like what it really means the Women's International Day, for example. People can actually understand what this day means and, as a consequence, change their mind. Although the term "science" was not always well received by younger generations, which could have an impact in the way they engage with it, scientific research is perceived as a key element to reconfigure some social beliefs, according to FG participants. Finally, FG respondents emphasized the awareness of the importance of scientific research is directly connected with the degree of people's trust in the field.

Science and scientific evidence play a key role in a world facing new challenges: fake news and hoaxes

Among the main initiatives to raise citizens' awareness of social impact of scientific research, those that aim to provide tools to distinguish scientific evidence from hoaxes are given special consideration. Therefore, LGBTIQ+ participants in the FG expressed that it is key to disseminate research and scientific information and results at a large scale, which in turn will help to stop fake news. Quantitative data points to the same direction and more than half of the respondents of the survey knew at least one initiative to distinguish scientific evidence from hoax in education and gender. However, the proportion of respondents of the survey who knew initiatives to distinguish evidence from hoax and who received information about scientific results decreased with age. The most known initiative were scientific magazines. Survey results also stressed that both analysed interactions (living a situation that changed their mind about science and following a scientist on social media), promoted citizens' knowledge of initiatives to distinguish scientific evidence from hoax in gender and education.

4. Conclusions

The following report was prepared with the aim of explaining the objectives, techniques, methodologies and results that respond to Objective 2: explore the initiatives that are already making societal actors aware of the connection between the solutions they appreciate and the scientific research that led to them. Regarding the project objectives, it provides a better understanding about the general and specific objectives of ALLINTERACT project. Finally, it offers an overview about the preliminary results and conclusions, which respond to O2. Data gathered and analysed for O2, brought new insights on citizens' awareness of the impact of scientific research, including the identification of elements fostering (transformative dimension) and hindering (exclusionary dimension) their access to those benefits. Also, it provided fundamental information about specific groups and communities and their relationship with science and their perceptions about this field of knowledge, as well as their opinions about scientific research and the importance of counting on validated content in an era in full with fake news and hoaxes. In addition, it stressed the importance of social media as channels and platforms that science must continue using in order to disseminate results and engage with different targets. All the analyses were then integrated in the core Report 2 under the title "Initiatives which are making societal actors aware of the scientific research that led to the solutions they appreciate", giving answer to O2.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. INTRODUCTION	7
2. LITERATURE REVIEW	7
2.1 Overview	7
2.2 Raising citizen awareness of social impact of research in Gender	7
2.2.1 Overview	7
2.2.2. Methodology	8
2.2.3 Results	10
2.3.3.1. Articles review according to the sub-categories	14
2.2.4 Conclusions: Raising awareness initiatives of social impact in Gender	18
2.2.5 Reference	19
2.3 Raising citizen awareness of social impact of research in Education	20
2.3.1 Overview	20
2.3.2 Methodology	20
2.3.3 Results	23
2.3.3.1. Articles review according to the sub-categories	27
2.3.4 Conclusions: Raising citizen awareness of social impact in education	33
2.3.5 References	34
3. SOCIAL MEDIA ANALYTICS	35
3.1 Overview	35
3.2 Methodology	35
3.2.1 Methodology for the Social Media Analysis	36
3.2.1.1 Selection of the social networks for the Social Media Analytics	36
3.2.1.2. Data collection for the Social Media Analytics	37
3.2.1.3. Social Media Analytics Sample	38
3.2.1.4.SMA Analysis	39
3.2.2. Social Media Communicative Observation	40
3.2.2.1. Selection of the Facebook and Reddit Groups	40
3.2.2.2. Selection of Social Impact Platforms Forums	43
3.2.2.3. Data Collection	43
3.2.2.4. Social Media Communicate Observation - Analysis	47
3.3. Results	48
3.3.1. Social Media Analytics on Gender	48
3.3.1.1.Top-Down	48
3.3.1.2.Bottom-Up	63

3.3.2. Social Media Analytics on Education	66
3.3.2.1. <i>Top-Down</i>	67
3.3.2.2. <i>Bottom-Up</i>	82
3.4. Results of the Social Media Communicative Observation	88
3.5. Conclusions	98
4. FOCUS GROUPS	100
4.1 Overview	100
4.2. Methodology: Focus Group	100
4.2.1. Gender	101
4.2.2. Education	107
4.2.2. Data collection	111
4.2.3. Analysis	111
4.3. Results of the Focus Groups: TOPIC b) How citizens benefit from scientific research	112
4.3.1. Results on Gender	112
4.3.2. Results on Education	129
4.4.1. Conclusions on Gender	146
4.4.2. Conclusions on Education	147
5. SURVEY	148
5.1 Overview	148
5.2.1. Sociodemographic questions	148
5.2.2. Analysis of the questions related to education	156
<i>Question 1</i>	157
<i>Question 2</i>	177
5.2.3. Analysis of the questions related to gender	194
<i>Question 1</i>	195
<i>Question 2</i>	213
5.3. Analysis of the impact of social interactions on the recognition (or not-recognition) of scientific evidence or education hoaxes	231
6. CONCLUSIONS	252

1. Introduction

The overall task of WP2 of the ALLINTERACT project is to explore the initiatives that are already making societal actors aware of the connection between the solutions they appreciate and the scientific research that led to them in regard to the SDGs of Quality Education and Gender Equality.

In order to respond to this objective, a series of tasks have been conducted, namely a Literature Review, Social Media Analytics, Focus Groups and a Survey. Different Consortium partners have been involved in the aforementioned tasks and analyses that integrate this report coordinated by the Institute of Political and Social Sciences (ISCSP) and the Interdisciplinary Centre for Gender Studies (CIEG), University of Lisbon (UL).

2. Literature review

2.1 Overview

In response to O2, the literature review on the exploration of the initiatives that are already making societal actors aware of the connection between the solutions they appreciate and the scientific research that led to them was conducted. The methodology followed in retrieving literature reviews in both fields, the results of the literature review, and the main conclusions are presented below, respectively. Findings of this literature review inform the design and development of the social media communicative intervention, which is presented in Chapter 3 of this report, the focus groups, which is presented in chapter 4, the survey which is presented in chapter 5, as well as of the interventions and policy recommendations which will be presented in other deliverables of the project.

2.2 Raising citizen awareness of social impact of research in Gender

2.2.1 Overview

This section provides information regarding the literature review of the exploration of the initiatives that are already making societal actors aware of the connection between the solutions they appreciate and the scientific research that led to them, corresponding to ALLINTERACT's O2. With this aim, a systematic literature review has been conducted in Scopus and the Web of Science scientific databases. In addition, grey literature has been searched to complete the task. Section 2.2 of this report includes the methodology followed in this literature review, with a focus on gender and Education, the results obtained and the main conclusions. The results were analysed and grouped into three categories: the social, political and scientific impact of research on gender and Education from which citizens have benefitted. The results inform the design and development of the focus group in gender which is explained in chapter 4, as well as the survey (chapter 5), the interventions and the policy commendations which will be presented in other work packages of the project according to the aim they contribute to. Researchers from ISCSP-ULisboa and UB have participated in the elaboration of this section.

2.2.2. Methodology

The aim of this literature review is to explore existing social science research regarding the exploration of the initiatives that are already making societal actors aware of the connection between the solutions they appreciate and the scientific research that led to them. To do that, scientific literature in the research area of Social Sciences published between 2010-2021 in journals indexed by Scopus and the Web of Science scientific databases was identified. Article is the document type set when searching for literature in Scopus and the Web of Science. Searches in both databases were conducted in English. In addition, impact factors were also been considered when conducting literature searches. Specifically, Q1 and Q2 journals for the searches made on Web of Science, and Q1 journals for the searches made on Scopus. To complete the task, grey literature has also been searched.

The following combinations of keywords were used to do the articles' research in Scopus and Web of Science:

Gender

- Social awareness of gender research
- Social awareness of scientific research and gender
- Social awareness of scientific research and social inequalities
- Science impact in reflective societies
- Gender research impact in reflective societies
- Gender research and impact in reflective societies
- Knowledge transfer societal impact
- Gender and Knowledge transfer societal impact
- Knowledge transfer gender impact
- Knowledge transfer and gender impact
- Gender research and knowledge transfer
- Knowledge transfer age impact
- Knowledge transfer and age impact
- Knowledge transfer and social inequalities

Regarding Web of Science database, searches were made following a specific procedure:

- Firstly, a general search of the keywords on all the indexes belonging to the Web of Science Core Collection.
- Secondly, a specific search of the keywords on Social Sciences Citation Index (SSCI).
- Thirdly, a specific search applying the data range exclusion criteria.

- Fourthly, a specific search applying the “article” and “journal” criteria.
- Fifthly, a specific search selecting only a list of the main Social Sciences areas.
- A final selection applying “Q1” and “Q2” exclusion criteria.

In the case of Scopus, searches were made as follows:

- Firstly, keyword searches were made applying the first filter: “Article, Abstract, Keywords”.
- Secondly, a specific search applying the data range exclusion criteria.
- Thirdly, a specific search applying the “Social Sciences” criteria.
- Fourthly, a specific search applying the “article” and “journal” criteria.
- A final selection applying “Q1” exclusion criteria.

Figure 2.1. Methodology process for the literature review on gender

A total of 343,496 articles resulted after the searching on Web of Science database and Scopus, of which 243,255 were out of scope, 73,115 were discarded due to lack of article impact, 26,728 due to be out of range, and 294 were off topic.

A final sample of 4 articles matched the selection criteria for topic b, and thus were reviewed and selected for the analysis. Selected articles were classified into 7 categories:

- 1) Aim of the awareness-raising initiative
- 2) Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/public)
- 3) Level of intervention (i.e. local/national/international; bottom-up/top-down)

- 4) Field of intervention
- 5) Audience (targeted and real)
- 6) Role of the targeted audience
- 7) Level of scientific evidence

For each of these categories, the transformative dimension (i.e. what facilitates the targeted impact) and the exclusionary dimension (i.e. obstacles hindering the achievement of the targeted impact) have been identified. Data has been classified according to the established categories (1-7) and dimensions as outlined in the Work Plan M1-M7 (see the following table).

Table 2.1. Analysis grid

O2) explore the initiatives that are already making societal actors aware of the connection between the solutions they appreciate and the scientific research that led to them;								
		<i>Aim of the awareness-raising initiative</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/ public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local/national/ international; bottom-up/top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Audience (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Role of the targeted audience</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension							
	Exclusionary Dimension							

2.2.3 Results

4 articles were identified regarding the raising awareness of social impact in gender. From this total it was possible to establish some quantitative results and an analysis under specific sub-categories. After analysing the identified articles and categorising them, the main categories of analysis lead to the following results displayed in figures 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, 2.6, 2.7, and 2.8.

Promoting organization

Figure 2.2. Promoting organization

The four articles include initiatives that can be categorized as “Public”, which represents a big opportunity in terms of reach not only during the process of the implementation of the initiatives, but in particular because of the **social impact** that they can have.

Level of intervention

Figure 2.3. Level of intervention

In terms of the level of intervention, a total of four of the initiatives were categorized as National, one as institutional and one as international.

Level of intervention

Figure 2.4. Level of intervention

Also related with the level of intervention, it was found that all of the initiatives can be categorized as Top-Down.

Field of intervention

Figure 2.5. Field of intervention

In terms of the field of intervention, it was found that three of the initiatives belong to Education, one to scientific research and one to Nanotechnology.

Audience

Figure 2.6. Audience

Three specific audiences were identified after reviewing the initiatives: Public universities (37%), researchers (38%), and academics (25%).

Role of the targeted audience

Figure 2.7. Role of the targeted audience

Regarding of the role of the targeted audience in the reviewed activities, it was identified that these included implementation (50%), to make contributions (33%), and to evaluate (17%).

Level of access to scientific evidence

Figure 2.8. Level of access to scientific evidence

In all of the initiatives it was possible to identify a high level of scientific evidence.

A review of the selected articles is displayed in the following pages, according to the sub-categories established for this purpose:

2.3.3.1. Articles review according to the sub-categories

The articles categorised within this section include four sub-categories that were established after the analysis of every initiative selected for the purposes of this report. In this sense, the subcategories are the following: a. Better research for better outcomes, b. Benefits beyond Academia, c. Gender as a key dimension for knowledge, and d. Open collaboration in research impacts in results.

a. Better research for better outcomes

The article written by Olmos-Peñuela et al. (2004) seeks to achieve a better understanding of the processes underlying knowledge transfer (KT) in social sciences and humanities (SSH). The research team worked with 97 CSIC (Spanish Council for Scientific), SSH (Social Sciences and humanities) research groups, under a methodology which included literature review on university-industry relationships, knowledge transfer, relational knowledge transfer, consultancy, contract research, joint research, training, personnel mobility. Researchers also established the following hypothesis: 1) Research groups conducting research that places a strong focus on the societal impact of research are more likely to engage in KT activities, 2) The more multidisciplinary the research group, the more likely it is that the group engages in KT activities, 3) Larger research groups are more likely to engage in KT activities, 4) Research groups whose leaders have higher academic status are more likely to engage in

KT activities, 5) Research groups whose leaders are star scientists, are more likely to engage in KT activities.

In terms of key findings, researchers reported that KT activities are based on relational rather than commercial activities. Also, they found that 25% of the research groups reported a strong focus on the potential societal impact of their research when establishing their project objectives. In terms of societal impact, they established that is a significant variable in all the regressions. More specifically, the likelihood to engage in consultancy activities, contract research, training and personnel mobility increases for research groups that have a strong focus on the societal relevance and impact of their research. In specific, they identified that the most frequent relational activities in which SSH research groups engage are consultancy and contract research.

The team also found that the characteristics of research groups (e.g. size and multidisciplinary) and individuals (e.g. academic status and star scientist) are associated with involvement in KT activities and that a deliberate focus on the societal impacts and relevance of the research conducted is strongly related to active engagement of research groups in all the modes of KT considered in this study.

From these findings, the research team suggested that KT practices within the SSH should be studied using a wider set of activities than the types of commercialization included in the technology transfer models used in technology and engineering fields. Regarding the Spanish context, they concluded that personnel mobility to non-academic environments is associated with leaving academia, loss of autonomy and regulatory restrictions that make it difficult for the researcher to return to a position in academia.

On the other hand, they established that more multidisciplinary groups show higher engagement in contract research activities. Also, that research impact (i.e. group leader being a star scientist) is important for promoting research group engagement in KT activities – especially consultancy and contract research (the most frequent KT activities in the SSH). Finally, and from a managerial perspective, findings suggested that measures promoting a focus on the societal impact of research could enhance research groups' engagement in KT activities.

b. Benefits beyond Academia

In the article written by Perez Vico & Jacobson (2021) the goal is to contribute to the literature on the impact of academic R&D, further challenging the dominant belief. Empirically, this paper seeks to identify the impact of academic R&D, explain what conditions this impact and indicate how policy could be improved in this technological field. In order to obtain the results, the research team worked with 35 key members of the Technological Innovation System (TIS) in Sweden, under a methodology that included a literature review about academic R&D, policy, nanotechnology, technological innovation system (TIS), semi structured interviews with 35 key members of the TIS were conducted in the period 2006–10, and the development of a matrix of analysis where we note if causal links appear between activities and functions in the data and provide illustrative examples of these links. The matrix included Activities (conducting research, scientific publishing, educating, providing direct guidance, commercializing, providing research infrastructures) and Functions (Influence of the

direction of research, legitimation, market formation, entrepreneurial experimentation, resource mobilization, knowledge development and diffusion, development of positive externalities).

Some of the key findings point to the fact that academic R&D activities impact greatly on entrepreneurial experimentation, contributing to a strong function. Yet, lack of resources for verification of experiments and industrial partners hamper the impact. Also, that Academia has a large impact centered on mobilizing human resources and building research infrastructure, however, the access to innovation-related financial capital is, in their words, problematic. In our analysis, these two elements can be classified as an exclusionary dimension.

In contrast, researchers identified that Academia has contributed to the generation of three relatively strong functions: entrepreneurial experimentation, knowledge development and diffusion and resource mobilization, and that the influence on the direction of search, legitimation and development of positive externalities remain weak in spite of extensive activities directed at them.

Although its benefits, the limited industry interest reduces the impact on system dynamics from academic contributions to entrepreneurial experimentation (and market formation) by constraining the number of industrial partners to academic spin-offs and access to complementary resources (resource mobilization) held by established industry. In this sense, the weakness of influence on the direction of search and legitimation also limits the effects of academic activities directed towards resource mobilization and knowledge development and diffusion.

In terms of conclusions, researchers said that TIS framework not only helps them to identify the impact of academic R&D but also explains which contextual factors condition their effects on system dynamics and suggests how these may be enhanced. Also, they emphasized the importance of indirect effects in analyzing the impact of academic R&D. Yet, these effects may have a long gestation period which means that we risk underestimating them. Finally, they concluded that Policy-makers seeking to improve the impact of academic R&D should help to resolve these issues.

c. Gender as a key dimension for new knowledge

By applying the EFFORTI evaluation framework to three empirical case study interventions that aim to integrate the gender dimension in tertiary education and research content, Palmén et. al (2020) worked based on literature review on gender, education, gender in education, gender in research and teaching, gender knowledge, mainstreaming sex and gender, Research Funding Organisations (RFOs), R&I, Research Performance Organisations (RPOs), and also in the analysis of three empirical case studies work located in Austria and Spain. They decided to follow the logic of theoretical sampling (Corbin & Strauss, 2015) as case studies aimed to integrate the gender dimension into teaching and R&I focusing on different points of the innovation cycle, from tertiary education, i.e. through the curriculum and teaching to research and technology transfer.

In terms of findings, researchers identified that in two of the case studies (FEMtech Research Projects and the Catalan University) unrealistic expectations of the interventions were held, given the amount of available budget. Also, a lack of sanctions negatively contributed to the implementation of, and the

outcomes and impacts of two of the case studies. In addition, in all of the case studies they were able to see how the gender concept was defined and operationalized, and how it affected the outcomes and impact of the interventions. In this sense, one of the main factors hindering implementation was a lack of recognition and status of gender studies.

On the other hand, in all three cases one of the keys enabling factors is the institutional commitment at the level of the rectorate and top management positions towards gender equality policies. In the specific case of cases studies from tertiary education, we they identified how successful strategies for implementation combined a central coordination unit which had gender competence and expertise with gender mainstreaming throughout study programmes. The case of the Catalan University demonstrated that gender competence is key for rolling out the integration of the gender dimension throughout the curriculum. Also, in terms of research, both case studies in tertiary education identified the lack of academic recognition of gender studies as an implementing obstacle. And finally, the outcomes and impacts related to these three interventions included an increased awareness and interest in gender, increased gender competence and increased commitment to gender teaching and research, more and better research, and an improved accreditation process.

After analyzing the outcomes of their research, they concluded that beyond the simple counting of keywords, training experts across the scientific disciplines is necessary to provide a more in-depth understanding how and when the gender dimension has been integrated into research and higher education. In terms of transformative dimension, in all three cases, to design / implement initiatives towards including a gender dimension in tertiary education and business enterprise sectors was identified as part or the role of the targeted audience.

On the other hand, when it comes to implementation, they concluded that gender competence is key. In this sense, building competences of researchers in the gender dimension is however a long-term process that requires in some cases challenging accepted 'norms' in certain scientific disciplines and therefore may take a great deal of time. In contrast, they found that usually the gender dimension in research becomes the weakest part of gender equality plans, which under our analysis can be framed as an exclusionary dimension.

Finally, although outcomes and impacts may be gradual, a slightly increased awareness may eventually lead to a better and 'more inclusive' way of doing and promoting science.

d. Open collaboration in research impacts in results

On a very detailed article, Beck et. all (2020) worked with the aim of linking dispersed knowledge on Open Innovation, Open Science, and related concepts such as Responsible Research and Innovation by proposing a unifying Open Innovation in Science (OIS) Research Framework. Researchers selected 47 scholars from diverse disciplines to work with.

They worked under a literature review on innovation, research, open innovation and a methodology included a multi-step collaborative approach involving the group of scholars from the social sciences,

humanities, and natural sciences to work to: 1) jointly conceptualize the OIS (Open Innovation in Science) Research Framework; 2) map relevant literature streams defining the different elements, logics, and interdependencies to be synthesized.

In terms of findings, researchers identified that outcomes of open and collaborative practices at the later stages of the research process can closely resemble those of research that does not apply OIS practices. Also, that as outcomes of OIS practices ensue along the entire research and dissemination process, they can create scientific and societal impacts along the way. In addition, they found that gaining a better understanding of mechanisms that facilitate openness and collaboration in science can optimize the application of OIS practices, unlocking these system-level efficiencies and clearing a path for more impactful research. And finally, they were able to identify that economic impacts can result from both inbound and outbound processes of knowledge transfer in the context of OIS.

These findings led the researchers to conclude that a more complete understanding of the available knowledge is needed to manage processes of openness and collaboration in science. Also, they argued that these methods have the potential to drive future research activities through their integration, and that their framework suggests specific connections and interdependencies. For the team it was key to employ an open and collaborative approach, because this allowed them to bridge disciplinary differences in terms of underlying norms, theories, assumptions, methods, and languages. In this sense, the integration of different perspectives provided them a more comprehensive picture that identifies robust results but also contradictions, tensions, and inconsistencies across scientific fields. However, the lack of specific connections and interdependencies may have an impact on the application of this framework was identified as part of the exclusionary dimension of this initiative.

And finally, they concluded that structuring the knowledge about open and collaborative research practices that they synthesized in terms of multi-level antecedents and contingencies, as well as outcomes and impacts, provides a common foundation for jointly developing a future research agenda.

2.2.4 Conclusions: Raising awareness initiatives of social impact in Gender

After the analysis of the selected articles, several conclusions can be socialized. Firstly, when it comes to research groups, it is important to highlight that training and the possibility of participating in different research groups not only help team members to get to know different backgrounds and approaches when it comes to scientific research, but also this factor can have a major benefit on the societal relevance and the impact of any research project. An important concept can be linked to personnel mobility: multidisciplinarity (Olmos-Peñuela, Castro-Martínez & d'Este, 2014). This is another factor that can be useful for better and more complete research but also to help people to be in touch with other ways to do research. And this has an impact in Knowledge Transfer, which is important to promote a deeper engagement of research groups (ibid). This can easily be linked to the case of Open Innovation in Science (OIS) (Beck et al, 2020), since outcomes made from this approach do not only help to get better results, but also creates a whole new process of researching which in the end can create stronger scientific and societal impacts from the beginning to end.

In this sense, the characteristics of research groups, like multi or interdisciplinarity, its size and gender composition, for example, and also individuals, are strongly linked with the involvement in KT activities

(ibid). As a consequence, and considering the level of engagement, openness and collaboration in this regard, this may have a direct impact on the results of any research project.

Scientific research is present in several fields in society and it is very important that what is investigated from a scientific point of view, can be well received for decision markers. In this sense, and taking as an example the article focused on Nanotechnology in Sweden (Perez Vico & Jacobsson, 2012), it is clear that academic activities focused on research and development have a great impact in those who are willing to experiment or to explore entrepreneurship. Nevertheless, this article also points that lack of resources for verification of experiments and industrial partners hamper this impact. In other words: How do we create a healthy ecosystem to provide the right tools to those who want to take their work to other fields in society? It is clear that Academia has demonstrated its capacity to mobilize human resources or to build research infrastructure in this regard, but it is also obvious that innovation-related financial capital still remains as an exclusionary dimension.

The limited industry interest negatively impacts in the process initiated by Academia. This gap must be addressed, since it is clear that scientific research has a profound impact in the way societies develop and evolve. Not enough resources and space for researchers and their work to be developed in the market, for example, hinders the benefits society can get from scientific research and this kind of initiatives.

All of the above is crossed by a key component that must be included in the analysis: gender. In the article written by Palmén et.al (2020), the gender concept was defined and operationalized and this affected the outcomes and impact of the interventions. When gender is not included in research activities – whether in groups composition or field of intervention, results will be overlooking a factor that can change results or the way a project is conducted. Authors of this article highlighted that one of the main factors hindering implementation, in specific, was a lack of recognition and status of gender studies. Researchers referred to the three cases that they studied and concluded that in all of them one of the most important factors is what they called institutional commitment, in particular in high positions of power, like rectorate and top management. This, in return, has a direct impact in gender equality policies.

In this sense, the case of the Catalan University illustrates that one key element is competence when it comes to observe and analyze a central aspect, like the curriculum (ibid). In contrast, when there is no recognition of gender studies or gender recognition, this emerges as an implementing obstacle. From a more positive point of view, the inclusion of gender as a factor will definitely have an impact in teaching, research and also accreditation processes for academic institutions.

In general, it was identified a high level of access to scientific evidence in all of the initiatives, which is important in the process of identifying the initiatives that are already making societal actors aware of the connection between the solutions they appreciate and the scientific research that led to them.

2.2.5 Reference

Beck, S., Bergenholtz, C., Bogers, M., Brasseur, T. M., Conradsen, M. L., Di Marco, D., ... & Xu, S. M. (2020). The Open Innovation in Science research field: a collaborative conceptualisation approach. *Industry and Innovation*, 1-50, <https://doi.org/10.1080/13662716.2020.1792274>

Olmos-Peñuela, J., Castro-Martínez, E., & d'Este, P. (2014). Knowledge transfer activities in social sciences and humanities: Explaining the interactions of research groups with non-academic agents. *Research Policy*, 43(4), 696-706, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2013.12.004>

Palmén, R., Arroyo, L., Müller, J., Reidl, S., Caprile, M., & Unger, M. (2020). Integrating the gender dimension in teaching, research content & knowledge and technology transfer: Validating the EFFORTI evaluation framework through three case studies in Europe. *Evaluation and program planning*, 79, 101751, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.evalprogplan.2019.101751>

Perez Vico, E., & Jacobsson, S. (2012). Identifying, explaining and improving the effects of academic R&D: The case of nanotechnology in Sweden. *Science and Public Policy*, 39(4), 513-529, <https://doi.org/10.1093/scipol/scs037>

2.3 Raising awareness of social impact in education

2.3.1 Overview

This section of Report2 gathers the state of the art regarding raising awareness of social impact, contributing to the achievement of ALINTERACT's O2. The results inform the design and development of the focus groups on education, which are explained in chapter 4, as well as the survey on education, which is presented in chapter 5, the interventions and the policy commendations which will be conducted in other work packages of the project. To that end, a systematic literature review has been conducted through an extensive identification of scientific contributions published during 2010-2020 in journals indexed in the scientific database of Scopus. To complete the task, grey literature was also searched. The following sections gather the methodology followed in this review, the results obtained and the main conclusions. In this line, the report identifies the social, political and scientific impact of research on education from which citizens have benefitted. Researchers from RUG and UB have participated in the elaboration of this section.

2.3.2 Methodology

This literature review aims to explore existing social science research regarding raising awareness of social impact in education. For this reason, a literature review was conducted to identify worldwide scientific contributions on the topic. Studies indexed in the scientific database of Scopus were searched and retrieved for the analysis. Sources have been selected seeking an interdisciplinary approach, both regarding the journals' and the articles of selection. For this literature review, the following combinations of keywords were used:

- Social awareness of scientific research AND education
- Social awareness of scientific research and youth AND education
- Social awareness of scientific research AND education

- Social awareness of scientific research and social inequalities AND education
- Science impact in reflective societies AND education
- Knowledge transfer societal impact AND education
- Knowledge transfer education impact OR Knowledge transfer and education impact
- Knowledge transfer and social inequalities AND education

In addition, a combination of the following searchable keywords was used to conduct the literature review:

education	actions	groups	Science	Scope
programs	awareness-raising	vulnerable groups	Science	education
interventions	citizen science	youth	Scientific	educational
	social impact	young citizens	Research	culture
	social transformation	special needs		cultural
	social cohesion	cultural minorities		High School Education
	Equality	ethnic minorities		Primary Education
	Egalitarian	children		Preschool Education
	Inclusion	teenager		Early childhood education
	Engagement	adolescent		Ordinary School
	awareness	migrant		School
	implementation	student		College
	literacy	community		University
	Successful Educational Actions			Adult School

The inclusion criteria of the literature we used is: 1) Subject area is Social Sciences, 2) the writing language is English, 3) the document type is article, 4) the keyword is education when available, 5) the publish year of these literature were during 2010-2021, 6) the source type is journal and 7) the journal is indexed in Journal Citation Reports (Q1 or Q2) or Scopus (Q1)

Figure 2.6. Methodology for the literature review on education

The literature search yielded 104 potential articles, of which 82 were discarded because they were out of scope, 12 due to unavailability on Scopus and there were 2 articles repeated. A final sample of 10 articles was included in the analysis.

For the analysis, the data retrieved from the 10 articles was organised in the following categories:

- 1) Aim of the awareness-raising initiative
- 2) Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/public)
- 3) Level of intervention (i.e. local/national/international; bottom-up/top-down)
- 4) Field of intervention
- 5) Audience (targeted and real)
- 6) Role of the targeted audience
- 7) Level of scientific evidence

For each of these categories, the transformative dimension (i.e. what facilitates the targeted impact) and the exclusionary dimension (i.e. obstacles hindering the achievement of the targeted impact) have been identified. Data has been classified according to the established categories (1-7) and dimensions as outlined in the Work Plan M1-M7 (see the following table).

Table 2.3. Analysis grid

O2) explore the initiatives that are already making societal actors aware of the connection between the solutions they appreciate and the scientific research that led to them;

		<i>Aim of the awareness-raising initiative</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local/national/international; bottom-up/top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Audience (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Role of the targeted audience</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>
Article	Transformative Dimension							
	Exclusionary Dimension							

2.3.3 Results

10 articles were retrieved regarding the raising awareness of social impact in education. From this total it was possible to establish some quantitative results and a latter analysis under specific sub-categories. After analysing the identified articles and categorising them, the main categories of analysis lead to the following results displayed in figures 2.9, 2.10, 2.11, 2.12, 2.13, 2.14, and 2.15.

Promoting organization

Figure 2.9. Proportion of promoting organization of initiatives in this category (Education)

A very interesting fact in these results is that the biggest number of the initiatives (seven in total) were categorized as “Self-organization”, followed by two initiatives that were classified as “Public”.

Level of intervention

Figure 2.10. Level of intervention of the initiatives in this category (Education)

In terms of the level of intervention, a total of seven initiatives were classified as “Local”, followed by two initiatives which were categorized as “National”.

Level of intervention

Figure 2.11. Level of intervention of the initiatives in this category (Education)

Regarding the approach of the initiatives, the biggest number of them correspond to the “Top-Down” category (six in total), whereas the other three were classified as “Bottom-Up”.

Field of intervention

Figure 2.12. Fields of intervention of the initiatives in this category (Education)

Different fields of intervention were categorized after the review of each initiative. The biggest number (two) correspond to Education, followed by Out-of-school education (one), Science communication/Climate change (one), Sustainability (one), Education/ training in Sciences (one), Educational technology / gender (one), and medical education (one).

Audience

Figure 2.13. Audiences reached by each initiative in this category (Education)

In terms of the audience, there is a correlation when analysed the fields of intervention. In this case, the biggest number correspond to students (three), followed by educators (one), 12 years-old children (one), climate experts (one), broad audience in education (actors from university administration, students, students' self-administration organizations, research and teaching, as well as representatives from the private sector and public administration) (one), students and staff (one), 30 HIV providers (one), and 227 female participants (one).

Role of the targeted audience

Figure 2.14. Role of the targeted audience in each initiative in this category (Education)

This category shows that in terms of the role of the targeted audience, the majority correspond to participants in research (four), followed by readers (three), and students (two).

Level of access to scientific evidence

Figure 2.15. Level of scientific evidence registered in each initiative in this category (Education)

Finally, regarding the level of access to scientific evidence, there is a solid number of initiatives which show a high level (six), compared to the ones classified as low (three).

A review of the selected articles is displayed in the following pages, according to the sub-categories established for this purpose:

2.3.3.1. Articles review according to the sub-categories

The articles categorised within this section include five sub-categories that were established after the analysis of every initiative selected for the purposes of this report. In this sense, the subcategories are the following: a. New researches and approaches for a more sustainable world, b. Impacts of social backgrounds in the learning process, c. Making an impact on health research, d. New ways of teaching impacts in positive outcomes, e. Education as a tool for a world free of gender violence, and f. Sustainability, a key element in Education.

a. New researches and approaches for a more sustainable world

Climate change has become a major topic in recent years, not only from a political point of view, but also from a key field as education. A group of initiatives aimed to tackle this issue were found during the process of the literature review.

With the aim of examining how ten- to twelve-year-old children experienced and made sense of their growing climate change awareness through an after-school program that used participatory methods to facilitate children's informed climate change action, Trot (2020) developed a study in the Mountain

Western of USA in which 55 children ages 10–12 (52.7% girls) who were in fourth to seventh grade and attended 18 different primary (61.8%) and middle schools (38.2%) in the region voluntarily participated. Participants were 56.4% white, 25.4% Hispanic/Latinx, 14.6% biracial or multiple ethnicities, and 3.6% Asian/Pacific Islander, and most children (61.8%) were from low-income households. Based on a mixed-methods techniques, the researcher used a combination of surveys and focus groups to address research questions.

In general terms, despite wide variation at the program's outset, children's average climate change awareness post-program expanded beyond their own pre-program knowledge, beyond the average U.S. teen or adult, and in some cases beyond the boundaries of program content. According to the scholar, children understood local to global impacts of climate change and its solutions through human action, while expressing a sense of hope for the future and an eagerness to be active participants in the global transformation towards sustainability that is now required. In particular, children's growing climate change awareness – rather than inducing distraction or avoidance behaviours – became a platform for their expanded agency and informed action to minimize harms.

In this case, given the transformative potential rightly attributed to education in averting climate change threats, there is a need to develop educational methods that are constructive – simultaneously building awareness, enabling agency, and enacting change. From a wider perspective, findings of this study shed light on methods for cultivating children's constructive climate change engagement. In particular, through the combination of hands-on educational activities, photovoice process, and youth-led action projects, children simultaneously acquired critical knowledge, made personal and place-based connections to the issue, and enacted sustainable solutions they envisioned for themselves. In the immediate term, the significance of climate change education lies in its potential to generate an informed and engaged public that is prepared to advocate and act to avert the most destabilizing effects of climate change. Children can be competent knowledge-bearers and critical actors in this transformation.

On a similar note, but aimed to a different target audience, Cook and Overpeck (2019) made a review written for climate experts dissatisfied with current approaches for contributing to societal responses to climate change via their interactions with publics. By reviewing the origins and contemporary manifestations of the deficit model, showing that it is the underlying basis for how experts imagine and conduct their interactions with publics. Rather than simply raising awareness among experts concerning their role(s) in perpetuating the deficit model, the authors use experts and their assumptions to organize our synthesis. This led the researchers to demonstrate that experts' prevailing means of contributing to socioscientific controversies are crippled, not by public indifference or ignorance, but by experts' allegiance to the assumption that information transfer can prompt behaviour change. The transfer of climate experts' knowledge by itself has little chance of changing publics' behaviours. It may be that such approaches work with people already disposed to the information or who defer to experts, but it is unlikely to affect publics who are doubtful, those whose livelihoods are precarious, or those who do not want to consider the terrifying implications of climate change.

b. Impacts of social backgrounds in the learning process

The first article of this sub-category, written by Carrasco-Sáez et al. (2019), describes the sociological importance and the process of social adaptation of users to a Personal Learning Environment (PLE). It includes the validation process of an instrument for the study of the PLE of 8th grade students belonging to 15 schools in the Biobío Region of Chile. A non-random sample composed for 472 Chilean 8th grade volunteer students from both primary state-run and private schools was used. The average age of the students who participated in the study was 13 years.

In terms of the validation method for this instrument, four stages were identified: i) Expert judgment: considering the opinions of six educators and experts in information and communication technologies (ICT); ii) a pilot test: that included a non-probabilistic sample of 472 subjects; iii) a principal component analysis (PCA); and iv) a confirmatory factor analysis (CFA). The Questionnaire on Work Habits and Learning for Professional Futures and the Context Questionnaire SIMCE TIC were used as a reference. The research was carried out through a non-experimental, descriptive, and transactional study during the second semester of the academic year in 2017.

Regarding the key findings of this initiative, authors found that when performing a psychometric analysis, a Cronbach alpha coefficient of 0.89 was obtained, which confirmed that the adaptation of the instrument is good. The results of the dimensional analysis help us define a structure for the new instrument considering three components that explain 55% of the total variance. The results of the confirmatory factor analysis showed adjustment indexes that support the theoretical model proposed for the PLE study.

From a completely different perspective, but related to the sub-category, Claridge et al. (2018) conducted a study aimed to gather qualitative data from with students and staff at one London, UK healthcare-based university to explore their perceptions of factors contributing to the attainment gap found between White and BAME students. The methodology used was qualitative, allowing an exploratory, in-depth and non-hypothesis-driven approach to eliciting a rich description of experiences and events relating to individual students and staff.

Regarding the findings of the study, the student data were best explained by two main themes: social factors and stereotyping, whilst staff data were also best explained by two main themes: social factors and student and staff behavior. Social factors suggested ethnically defined social networks and the informal transfer of knowledge impacted academic performance, isolating minority groups from useful academic information. BAME students may also be at a further disadvantage, being unable to attend social and academic functions for cultural or family reasons. Black students also mentioned changing their behavior to combat negative stereotypes in a variety of contexts.

c. Making an impact in medical research

The first article fitting in this category belongs to Gallagher et al. (2017), in which they described the interprofessional perspectives of HIV providers who participated in this regional program to understand success and areas for strengthening pedagogical modality, content, and impact on clinical

practice, with the participation of 30 HIV providers from New England, UK. A mixed methodology implemented between 2013 and 2014 to analyze quantitative programmatic data allowed to determine that since 2010, NEAETC (New England AIDS Education and Training Center) evolved modalities to a greater focus on active learning (case discussion, clinical consultation), decreasing didactic training by half (18–9%). This shift was designed to move from knowledge transfer to translation, and qualitative findings supported the value of active learning approaches. Providers valued interactive trainings and presentation of cases supporting knowledge translation. On-site training encouraged peer networking and sharing of lessons learned. Diversity in learning priorities across providers and sites validated NEAETC's approach of tailoring topics to local needs and encouraging regional networking.

In terms of conclusions, researchers established that tailored approaches resulted in improved provider-reported capacity, peer learning, and support. Future evaluations should explore the impact of this multipronged approach on supporting a community of practice and empowerment of provider.

The second article was written by Issa et al. (2011) was aimed to evaluate the call on researchers to study the effectiveness of multimedia design principles, made by the Association of American Medical Colleges' Institute for Improving Medical Education's, under the report entitled 'Effective Use of Educational Technology'. This initiative was targeted to Year 3 medical students at a private, midwestern medical school progressing through their surgery clerkship during the academic year 2009–2010 in the US.

Based on a methodology that included a pre-test / post-test control group design, the traditional learning group received a lecture on shock using traditionally designed slides and the modified-design group received the same lecture using slides modified in accord with Mayer's principles of multimedia design. In terms of findings, both student cohorts had similar levels of pre-lecture knowledge and showed significant improvements in retention ($p < 0.0001$), transfer ($p < 0.05$) and total scores ($p < 0.0001$) between the pre- and posttests. Repeated-measures ANOVA analysis showed statistically significant greater improvements in retention ($F = 10.2$, $p = 0.0016$) and total scores ($F = 7.13$, $p = 0.0081$) for those students instructed using principles of multimedia design compared with those instructed using the traditional design.

d. New ways of teaching impact on positive outcomes

With the aim of determining whether the Bayesian updating activities are able to produce significant epistemological gains in an otherwise traditional course, the study conducted by Warren (2020) worked with a control group (C, 55) and an experimental group (E.E, 34, 32) of students from one calculus-based introductory physics course on mechanics.

A quasi-experimental design at a medium-sized regional campus of a land-grant institution. The principal difference between the two conditions was the use of Bayesian updating activities in the experimental sections. Data were collected via administration of the EBAPS during the first week of classes and again during the final week. This instrument is a 30-item forced-choice assessment of students' personal epistemologies.

In terms of findings, a Comparison of the pretest scores for the two experimental sections (E1 and E2) show no credible differences at the 95% level, indicating an acceptable level of homogeneity between the two groups on the pretest. For the moment, despite some differences found in the study, researchers choose to operate under the assumption that the populations of the three sections are initially uniform enough to produce reasonably valid conclusions of treatment efficacy based on comparisons of the post-test results. Taken together, the differences in gains between the E and C conditions indicate the E condition made meaningful, credible, and broad epistemic gains relative to the C condition.

e. Education as a tool for a world free of gender violence

With the aim to examine the prevalence and nature of different forms of intimate partner violence, and to gain a better understanding of the complex interactions and relationship between various forms of IPV and the impact on mental health and behavioural problems, Guggisberg (2017) conducted a study in which 227 adult females aged between 19 and 65 years from the metropolitan area of Perth (Australia) participated.

A non-experimental quantitative research design was employed. Participants were recruited to complete a specifically constructed 96-item questionnaire that used standardized questions and subscales while visiting one of nine support services (eight district offices of a government support service and a women's health service). Information was sought on exposure to different forms of IPV experienced in the past 6 months and its impacts. Logistic regression was used to investigate the influence of different combinations of victimization on mental health and substance using behaviour.

The researchers established different combinations of IPV victimization: a. Type 1 = women who experienced sexual violence at the same time as physical violence and controlling behavior; b. Type 2 = women who did not experience sexual violence but were exposed to physical violence and controlling behavior, and c. Type 3 = women who did not experience any sexual or physical violence but controlling behavior; and Type 4 as the reference group = women not exposed to any form of IPV. Combining the Violence Assessment Index (VAI) and the Controlling Behavior Index allowed to measure different combinations of IPV and assisted in dispelling the misconception of discrete acts of violence as a consequence of conflict.

In terms of findings, of the 277 participants, 67 (29.5%) did not experience any form of IPV, and of the 160 women who reported recent victimization by a current or former intimate partner, only 36 (16.3%) experienced single forms of violence of which 34 (15%) reported exposure to controlling behavior. These findings suggest the almost all women who reported IPV were subjected to multiple forms of IPV. In specific, IPV victimization where sexual violence is a component (Type 1) had the most severe impact on women's mental health and health risk behaviors. 73% of women were subjected to sexual violence in addition to physical violence and controlling behavior. These women were on average 22.86 more likely than the control group to experience anxiety and depression. Women in this category also reported potential alcohol dependence and current cigarette smoking. Respondents exposed to Type 1 IPV also reported threats to their children (abduction, homicide), and violence during pregnancy.

Findings of the study have implications for future practice and policy including school-based prevention programs. Study results also highlight the need for more research in this area. This paper argued that key challenges include building knowledge and skills leading to confidence and capacity, as well as encouraging social connectedness to share experiences and resources. It was suggested that using technology, as means of acquiring and sharing knowledge, allows educators to access information flexibly and to develop skills by integrating social networking technology. Hence, it was argued that an online community of teaching practitioners, as an informal online group, could be created. Teachers could share experiences of delivering the prevention program, comment on successful lesson plans and exchange resources. Collaborative learning is a key component through interaction with others.

f. Sustainability, a key element in Education

With the aim of presenting an initial conceptual description of sustainability transfer for universities in Germany, Nölting et. all (2020) developed a series of activities in Germany to enable relevant activities at universities to be identified, made visible, and analyzed in detail. The empirical study for the development of a sustainability transfer concept was broken down into three steps: 1. exploration through expert discussions and workshops with actors working in the areas of transfer and sustainability; 2. an empirical survey of experts on transfer, and 3. an empirical study on the implementation of sustainability transfer in teaching to identify a concrete teaching format.

In total, reports of 17 student projects from the winter semesters 2016/17 and 2017/18 were evaluated, and six of the reports built the data as detailed case studies. Twelve documents from the case studies were thus evaluated using qualitative content analysis. Researchers considered, as criteria: forms of interaction, methods for structuring interaction, role of students, factors influencing the cooperation process, types of results, and links to sustainability. In addition, six exploratory interviews were conducted with the practice partners in the six case studies in order to assess the learning and impact potential of the projects on the part of the practice partners.

In terms of findings, the definition of sustainability transfer provided, and the six descriptive characteristics enable such transfer activities to be systematically identified and described. Also, researchers found that visibility can increase appreciation for this form of transfer. The descriptive characteristics also enable empirical analysis and comparison between different forms of sustainability transfer, which in turn allows a more precise positioning in the focal area of universities and increases the academic compatibility.

On a similar note, and based on a review aimed at understanding and specifying how education for sustainable development in early childhood education may be implemented, Bascopé et all. (2019), undertook a systematic review of peer-reviewed articles on ESD for ECE (n = 30). After an expert committee revision of the articles reviewed, three cornerstones (scientific action-integrated, community-based and value-oriented scopes) and three sets of suitable pedagogical approaches (art-based, outdoor-based and project-problem-based) were identified. The review was enhanced by an unsystematic review of articles (n = 26) that specifically referred to the cornerstones and approaches. Finally, a double-blind expert coding and categorization of the articles (n = 56) was performed in order to validate the results.

As a result, authors suggested a procedural framework, rather than a theoretical one, based on international experience as evidenced by the scientific literature, which is intended to provide information on activities and innovations that programs of education for sustainable development should encompass. In particular, looking through the literature on ESD, researchers highlighted certain common critical points needed to orient the pedagogical approaches, which must be understood as not intrinsically being part of the approaches, since those are not exclusive to ESD. However, the use of them in an ESD context is made possible through the acknowledgement of those critical nodes. The authors expanded on the three cornerstones for ESD activities: (1) they should be action-integrative, meaning they should encourage practical activities that integrate scientific and non-scientific knowledge; (2) they should be community-based, and encourage relevant activities with transformative goals; and (3) they should be value-oriented, with a large enough scope to develop ethics and aesthetics attitudes regarding humans and non-humans.

2.3.4 Conclusions: Raising citizen awareness of social impact in education

Based on the analysis of the selected articles, the main conclusion that can be obtained is the fact that education is the key in the process of getting not only in touch with scientific research, but also with the way its results have an impact in every day's lives. And this can be applied to diverse knowledge fields.

From a social impact perspective, one of the most important conclusions is linked with a concept that has been worked from different perspectives: sustainability. Through initiatives targeted to specific audiences, such as climate experts, it is clear that sustainability is key when thinking about the future when it comes to environment care. Education, in this sense, can certainly avert climate change threats, but there is still a need to develop educational methods that are constructive in three specific ways: building awareness, enabling agency, and enacting change.

It is important to create initiatives that can become a space in where different audiences – from climate experts to school students, can reflect, talk and even put their hands on, so new ideas and knowledge can come up as a result. In this sense, collaboration emerges as a key component for these audiences to work together for better results.

On the other hand, but also related with sustainability as a concept, but specifically in Education, presents a series of challenges. One of the most important is linked to the concept of transfer, which must also be worked to allow a more precise positioning in the focal area of universities and increases the academic compatibility, as stated in one of the articles reviewed in this section. Sustainability is also important in personal learnings environments, since it will allow people to get fully involved in educational processes. Therefore, it becomes clear that education for sustainability must be part of the curricula, in particular citizenship education, since it will help students to understand the magnitude and complexity of the changes needed in today's world.

From a research impact perspective, and regarding education in traditional institutions, such as schools or universities, it is important to highlight the social background component, which conditions the way in which the learning processes take place. As reviewed in one of the articles, forms of discrimination, whether conscious or unconscious, may negatively impact the abilities of students either in examinations or coursework choices. In this sense, it is important to include the student's background as a whole – including aspects as ethnicity, for example, when developing any educational process.

Education is key when addressing issues as gender violence, transmissible diseases, such as HIV, or even on a formal education process of medicine students. As stated in three of the articles considered for this report, it is important to work with groups through initiatives that can leverage information about these topics. In this sense, innovation either through specific or ground-breaking methodologies or via the application of technology or multimedia resources may have a positive impact in research outcomes.

All the initiatives described and analysed in previous pages present a high level of access to scientific evidence. All of them work as positive examples of how they are already making societal actors aware of the connection between the solutions they appreciate and the scientific research that led to them.

2.3.5 References

- Bascopé, M., Perasso, P., & Reiss, K. (2019). Systematic Review of Education for Sustainable Development at an Early Stage: Cornerstones and Pedagogical Approaches for Teacher Professional Development. *Sustainability*, 11(3), 719. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11030719>
- Carrasco-Sáez, J. L., Butter, M. C., Badilla-Quintana, M. G., Pérez, L. J., & Farfán, J. M. (2019). Sociological Importance and Validation of a Questionnaire for the Sustainability of Personal Learning Environments (PLE) in 8th Grade Students of the Biobío Region in Chile. *Sustainability*, 11(5), 1301. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11051301>
- Cook, B. R., & Overpeck, J. T. (2019). Relationship-building between climate scientists and publics as an alternative to information transfer. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews. Climate Change*, 10(2), 1-17. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wcc.570>
- Gallagher, D. M., Hirschhorn, L. R., Lorenz, L. S., & Piya, P. (2017). Developing a community of practice for HIV care: Supporting knowledge translation in a regional training initiative. *Journal of Continuing Education in the Health Professions*, 37(1), 27-36. [doi:10.1097/CEH.0000000000000141](https://doi.org/10.1097/CEH.0000000000000141)
- Guggisberg, M. (2017). Violence against women in the family home: Acknowledging the role of education and the opportunities to utilise technology in prevention efforts. *Technology, Knowledge and Learning*, 22(2), 227-235. [doi:10.1007/s10758-017-9303-6](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10758-017-9303-6)
- Issa, N., Schuller, M., Santacaterina, S., Shapiro, M., Wang, E., Mayer, R. E., & Darosa, D. A. (2011). Applying multimedia design principles enhances learning in medical education. *Medical Education*, 45(8), 818-826. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2923.2011.03988.x>
- Nölting, B., Molitor, H., Reimann, J., Skroblin, J.-H., & Dembski, N. (2020). Transfer for Sustainable

- Development at Higher Education Institutions—Untapped Potential for Education for Sustainable Development and for Societal Transformation. *Sustainability*, 12(7), 2925. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12072925>
- Trott, C. D. (2020). Children's constructive climate change engagement: Empowering awareness, agency, and action. *Environmental Education Research*, 26(4), 532–554. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504622.2019.1675594>
- Warren, A. R. (2020). Impact of Bayesian updating activities on student epistemologies. *Physical Review Physics Education Research*, 16(1). <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevPhysEducRes.16.010101>

3. Social Media Analytics

3.1 Overview

As detailed in the DoA (p.10) in March 2021 (M6) the Social Media Analytics tasks of the project started. According to the GA (p.138) this analysis aimed to:

“provide information about how citizens interact in social media, focusing on the areas of gender and education (O1, O2, O3 & O4). For this analysis, social networks such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram and Reddit will be considered. The focus will be on how citizen participation in science can be enhanced through online awareness-raising initiatives which link social advancements to the scientific research which led to them.”

For this purpose, ALLINTERACT consortium has followed the Social Impact in Social Media methodology (Pulido et al., 2018)², which consists of the identification of quantitative and qualitative evidence of the potential or real impact of research shared on social media.

This chapter of Report 2 contains the Social Media Analytics for topic b) Citizen awareness of the impact of scientific research.

3.2 Methodology

ALLINTERACT Social Media Analytics is based on the Social Impact in Social Media methodology (Pulido et al., 2018)³, which allows access to the social impact of science. This research has conducted a quantitative and qualitative analysis. The social networks selected, the methodological procedure, and the analysis of the messages obtained through the SMA protocol are detailed below.

² Pulido, C. M., Redondo-Sama, G., Sordé-Martí, T., & Flecha, R. (2018). Social impact in social media: A new method to evaluate the social impact of research. *PloS one*, 13(8).

³ Ibid.

3.2.1 Methodology for the Social Media Analysis

3.2.1.1 Selection of the social networks for the Social Media Analytics

SMA sought to reach citizens' voices, paying special attention to vulnerable groups and young citizens⁴. For this reason, different social networks were included in this analysis. Considering that each social network has specific characteristics, Table 3.1 compiles the main characteristics of each social network that were taken into account before the SMA.

Table 3.1. Characteristics of the selected social networks

Network	Options	Characteristics	
Facebook	Pages	Most Facebook pages are not individual initiatives, but they belong to organizations, associations, media or campaigns. Citizens like or follow these pages, so they can see on their home page the contents shared by these pages. When pages share their content, citizens interact with this content through likes, sharing or comments, so this is one way to access citizens' voices	
	Groups	Public	Public groups include the voices of citizens, as all those users who are members of the group can post in the group and interact with the shared content. Users who are not part of the group can find the group (as long as the group is visible) and can see the content and interactions shared within the group, but they can only interact with the content through likes (they cannot publish a new post or comment in existing posts).
		Private	ALLINTERACT will not access private groups.
	Individual profiles	<p>One option to search what individual citizens post in their timelines is to browse by hashtags (e.g. #gender). The results will show only those posts containing the hashtag, which are public, including pages and those citizens with a public Facebook profile.</p> <p>NOTE: It is important to ensure that the results obtained through this search are representative of society, because the use of hashtag is not broadly normalized yet and most users do not post using hashtags. In fact, the use of hashtags is more common in pages or institutional profiles than in individual profiles.</p> <p>NOTE: Most citizens do not have their profiles in a public option, so it is difficult to get the whole picture in a search using hashtags.</p> <p>The second option is to use the keyword instead of the hashtag (without the #) in the browser and refining by "publications". However, the results in this search show only publications containing the keyword posted by your friends or public pages. Therefore, this is not a real alternative, as it is impossible to see the whole picture in these results.</p>	

⁴ Pulido Rodriguez, C. M., Ovseiko, P., Font Palomar, M., Kumpulainen, K., & Ramis, M. (2021). Capturing Emerging Realities in Citizen Engagement in Science in Social Media: A Social Media Analytics Protocol for the Allinteract Study. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 20, 16094069211050163.

Twitter	Individual profiles	The search can be carried out through hashtags and the results will show all public posts posted by individuals using the hashtag. Interactions with other citizens can be analysed through RT, comments or likes.
Instagram	Individual profiles	The search can be carried out through hashtags and the results will show all public posts posted by individuals using the hashtag. Interactions with other citizens can be analysed mainly through likes. This social network is the most visual of all and users share pictures with hashtags and sometimes, a brief description. Therefore, it contains fewer written interactions among users.
Reddit	Subreddit	When you conduct a search on Reddit, you can obtain results by posts and communities/users. As Reddit does not use #, the results of the post show all posts that use the keyword in every public Reddit. When the search is refined by communities, you obtained all communities that mention that word (sorted by relevance, new... and filtered by a period of time). In the communities, users share posts and comment posts about different topics. Some communities have categories to filter the posts (e.g.: by topic, type of post, location...)
	Individual users	Individual users can join Reddit communities and post or comment on existing posts

Source: ALLINTERACT SMA protocol

3.2.1.2. Data collection for the Social Media Analytics

The procedure carried out for the SMA is based on the ALLINTERACT Social Media Analytics Protocol (Flecha & Pulido, 2021)⁵ and summarised in Figure 3.1.

⁵ Flecha, R., & Pulido, C. (2021). Allinteract - Social Media Analytics Protocol is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution - NonCommercial - ShareAlike 4.0 International License is available in https://archive.org/details/@crea_research

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Figure 3.1. Procedure for ALLINTERACT Social Media Analytics

According to this protocol, the SMA has followed a twofold strategy:

- **Top-Down:** this approach consists in the definition of keywords related to gender/education and the topics of the project to contrast if these topics are expressed by citizens in their opinions, comments and post expressed in social media.
- **Bottom-Up:** this approach consists in the identification of topics that emerge from those keywords and hashtags most used by citizens in twitter. Then the emerging topics are contrasted with the topics defined by the project and analyse if they cover all aspects proposed by the project and/or there are some additional issues that were not covered initially by the project.

3.2.1.3. Social Media Analytics Sample

From the 3,565 messages extracted⁶, 506 messages (262 in gender and 244 in education) were discarded from the analysis, as detailed in Table 2.

Table 2. Sample

Topic	Social Media	TOTAL	Included	Excluded
Gender	Twitter	927	748	179
	Reddit	97	34	63
	Instagram	28	21	7
	Facebook	11	9	2
	Twitter (Bottom-Up)	51	40	11
Education	Twitter	668	617	51
	Reddit	293	208	85

⁶ The complete data set can be found in Zenodo Repository. Soler-Gallart., M (2021). D1.1.ALLINTERACT_RawData (Version v1.0.0) [Data set]. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4729725>

	Instagram	86	64	22
	Facebook	152	141	11
	Twitter (Bottom-Up)	1252	1177	75
	TOTAL	3565	3059	506

The main reasons for this discard were:

- Broken links or not having access to the content, which made impossible the categorization
- Not being related to areas of study that are gender and education
- Not falling in the scope of topic a, or not showing how citizen benefit from science

Therefore, the final sample included a **total of 3,059 messages**.

3.2.1.4. Social Media Analytics - Analysis

The analysis of the selected messages for topic a) “Citizen awareness of the impact of scientific research” was also based on the SMA protocol, as can be detailed in the following Table 3.2:

Table 3.2. Analysis grid for Topic b) Citizen awareness of the impact of scientific research.

O2) explore the initiatives that are already making societal actors aware of the connection between the solutions they appreciate and the scientific research that led to them;							
	<i>Aim of the awareness-raising initiative</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private/public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local/national/international)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Audience (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Role of the targeted audience</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>
TD							
ED							

* Transformative/exclusionary dimension

The categories and dimensions of the analysis were defined as detailed in Table 3.3:

Table 3.3. Definitions of dimensions and categories for topic b.

Dimensions	Transformative dimension: includes those messages that evidence what facilitates the implementation of initiatives that raise citizens’ awareness of the impact of scientific research
-------------------	--

	Exclusionary dimension: includes those messages that show barriers hindering the implementation of initiatives that raise citizens' awareness of the impact of scientific research
--	--

3.2.2. Social Media Communicative Observation

The SMCO has aimed at further exploring which awareness-raising initiatives are succeeding at enhancing citizen participation in science, in regard to the SDGs of quality education and gender equality, with gender also being considered transversely throughout all SDGs.

The distribution of the task was the following:

- a) Posts identified in mentioning successful awareness-raising initiatives were further explored, to identify which of them refer to actions that **succeed as well in engaging citizens in active science participation**. Researchers reviewed them one by one and classified them following the above-mentioned categories (Citizen awareness of the impact of scientific research, Awareness-raising initiatives succeeding at engaging citizens in scientific participation, including the Open Access movement, awareness-raising actions that foster the recruitment of new talent in the sciences, and policies that promote awareness-raising actions and citizen engagement in science). The success rate of the identified initiatives was also calculated.
- b) How the content of the posts of users participating in the discussion changed once evidence of the social impact of research was introduced were analysed. To that end, from the extracted data in this WP, all posts directly or indirectly interacting or referencing the introduced evidence were selected. Researchers have analysed post threads to identify changes in the debate.
- c) The correlation between awareness of the social impact of research and engagement in science were also analysed.

3.2.2.1. Selection of the Facebook and Reddit Groups

This research has selected the social media groups/pages considering the most used words when talking about gender and education identified in WP1. Based on these words, groups were searched for on the social networks Facebook and Reddit. Specifically, 61 groups were searched, 29 for gender and 32 for education (see Table 3.4.).

Table 3.4. Table summarising the groups that were pre-selected and subsequently contacted for gender and education:

Social Media	Pre-selected Groups Gender	Pre-selected Groups Education
Facebook	CAMPAIGN AWARENESS AGAINST GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE & GENDER INEQUALITY!, UNI-Mentors in Violence Prevention, The	Parents for children's education / Parents union from all around the world, School teacher and administrator educational resources, Child Care'

	Feminism Platform, Gender equality in the Red Cross and Red Crescent Movement, ETUC Gender Equality, Global Youth Movement Against Gender Based Violence, LGBT Advocacy, EMPOWER EQUALIT. CHILD RIGHT AND GENDER EQUALITY SUPPORT, Gender-based Violence Campaign Group., Gender Based Violence SOLUTIONS, Gender Equity and Reconciliation International, Equality 4 Women, LGBTQ+ Protest Group	Development, Education & Parenting, Our Voice: Communities for Quality Education Group, International Special Needs Teachers/ Learning Support Teachers, Amazing Educational Resources, Special Education Community, Quality Early Childhood Education and Care, PARENTS, TEACHERS AND STUDENTS FORUM, All Teachers' Unity Platform, Teachers and Students, Teachers Throwing Out Grades, The Quality Education Project, Special Education Community, FAME - Families Against Mis-Education.
Reddit	r/feminism, r/feminisms, r/FeMRADebates, r/PurplePillDebate, r/bisexual, r/SRSFeminism, r/AskFeminists, r/Equality, r/TwoXChromosomes, r/AskWomen, r/relationships, r/SexualHarassment, r/GenderIssues, r/MeToo, r/LGBTTeens, r/women	r/education, r/ScienceTeachers, r/ApplyingToCollege, r/teaching, r/science, r/Teachers, r/college, r/parenting, r/ParentTeacherGroups, r/ECEC, r/FutureTeachers, r/ScienceEducation, r/highschool, r/specialed, r/Teacher, r/Children.

We contacted the administrators of these groups to participate in the research, of which four replied, two of them decided to participate. However, it was not carried out because they did not provide the ethical consent created to participate in the research.

In parallel, the research team decided to create and search for other social media groups/pages. In the area of gender, five groups on Facebook and five on Reddit were created and selected again, while in the area of education, 5 Reddit groups were created and 5 Facebook groups/pages were contacted where scientific evidence in education was already being discussed.

Table 3.5. shows the names of the gender groups and in which language they are spoken in the group.

Table 3.5. Facebook and Reddit groups created on gender:

Facebook			Reddit		
Selected Groups	Language	Origen	Selected Groups	Language	Origen
Contra el acoso que reciben quienes apoyan a las víctimas / VG Aisladora	Spanish	Created	r/Contra_SOSH	Spanish	Created

Against the harassment of victim supporters / IGV	English	Created	r/Against_SOSH	English	Created
Our right to fall in love	English	Created	r/OurRigthToFallInLove	English	Created
Grup de Dones Sherezade: Dialogant el Feminisme	Catalan	Selected	r/genderviolence	English	Created
Social Impact Science Platform	English	Created	r/science_gender_sappho	English	Created

The table below lists the names of the education groups and in which language the group speaks.

Table 3.6 Facebook and Reddit groups or pages created about education:

Facebook			Reddit		
Selected Groups	Language	Origen	Selected Groups	Language	Origen
Comunidades de Aprendizaje. Schools as Learning Communities	Spanish	Selected	r/GruposInteractivos	Spanish	Created
Tertulias Literarias y Musicales Dialógicas	Spanish	Selected	r/InteractiveGroups	Spanish	Created
Actuaciones Educativas de Éxito. Comunidades de Aprendizaje	Spanish	Selected	r/TertuliasDialogicas	Spanish	Created
Comunidade de Aprendizagem / Comunidad de Aprendizaje	Spanish	Selected	r/DialogicGatherings	English	Created
Inclusividad NEE en CdA. Inclusion SEN in Schools as Learning Communities	Spanish	Selected	r/EducacionInclusiva	Spanish	Created

In these groups, posts were written in relation to the results of the ALLINTERACT research, in which users could interact with the content. The groups were also used to provide information and consent for those who wished to participate. The selected groups were informed, and consent was obtained from the administrators and the users whose comments were analysed.

3.2.2.2. Selection of Social Impact Platforms Forums

ALLINTERACT research has been involved since the beginning, in October 2020, in the creation of two Social Impact Platforms, one in gender and the other in education. So, the ALLINTERACT team at the University of Barcelona has decided to incorporate these in the current SMCO analysis.

These platforms are led by the Research Group in Sociological Theory and Impact of Research (TSIR). The two platforms are non-populist participatory platforms, available to everyone, both to consult and to contribute. They are contributing to deepen, on the one hand, in the development of sociological theory at the international level and, on the other hand, to the analysis and improvement of the social impact of research.

These platforms are built with a bottom-up approach that brings together not only researchers and practitioners, but all citizens, both to consult and to contribute. These participatory instruments are committed to promoting an egalitarian dialogue based on validity claims and the sharing of scientific evidence with all citizens. Thus, these platforms are Open Access platforms available to everyone. Any citizen who wants to participate will be able to sign in and contribute. Participation will be totally voluntary.

These platforms are:

- SAPPHO scientific evidence platform is focused on Gender SDG.
(<https://socialimpactsience.org/gender/>)
- ADHYAYANA scientific evidence platform is focused on SDG Quality Education, from a multicultural perspective. It will deepen, on the one hand, the development of sociological theory at the international level and, on the other hand, it will contribute to the analysis and improvement of the social impact of research.
(<https://socialimpactsience.org/education/>)

The research team contacted the platforms' administration team to inform them of the selection and obtained consent. We also contacted the people selected for the study and obtained consent (Online consent form <https://forms.office.com/Pages/ResponsePage.aspx?id=qzwxosOxOk-7ESFXRH3btA8lqcPRmYtGj4JVP3l6T1ZUQ1VIVkFIMUVGN1hCN1hHQ1pBQjITMjE4Ry4u>)

3.2.2.3. Data Collection

The information collected has been carried out from May 2021 to December 2021 (6 months) for the social networks Facebook and Reddit. While the information from the Social Impact Science forums has been collected from October 2020 to December 2021 (15 months).

A total of 21,322 members made up the 20 groups selected/created (10 in gender and 10 in education) and the two Social Impact Science Platforms. **A total of 1,383 posts related to the research objective** have been made, which have had **3,397 interactions (reactions and sharings)** and **576 comments** have been made.

3.2.2.3.1. Data collection on gender

In the field of gender, a **total of 885 posts have been made in relation to the research on Facebook, Reddit, and Social Impact Science on Sapfo**. Of the **3,171 members who are part of the groups/pages or forums have interacted (reactions and sharings) 1,882 times and made 158 comments**.

Details are given below:

Facebook Gender

In relation to the 5 Facebook groups/pages, **486 posts** related to the results of the research project have been published and a total of **600 members have joined**, of which **1,875 have interacted and made 38 comments**.

Table 3.7. Detailed table of the gender-related Facebook groups/pages studied.

Facebook				
Group/Page	No. members of / followers	No. of Research Post	No. of Interactions	No. of Comments
Contra el acoso que reciben quienes apoyan a las víctimas / VG Aisladora	110	106	400	3
Against the harassment of victim supporters / IGV	77	110	175	10
Our right to fall in love	25	45	71	2
Grup de Dones Sherezade: Dialogant el Feminisme	65	10	20	0
Social Impact Science Platform (Gender)	323	215	1,209	23

Reddit Gender

In the case of Reddit, 5 sub-communities were created, of which a **total of 313 posts** were made about the project and a total of **45 members took part, of which 7 interactions and 4 comments were made**.

In January 2021, when we looked at this data again, we realised that Reddit administrators had deleted around 276 comments in January 2022. So, there are currently 37 public comments left in 2021

Table 3.8. Detailed table of Reddit groups on gender.

Reddit				
Group	No. of members	No. of Research Post	No. of Interactions	No. of Comments
r/Contra_SOSH	13	98 (6)	3	2
r/Against_SOSH	12	98 (7)	2	2
r/OurRigthToFallInLove	8	65 (6)	0	0
r/genderviolence	3	22(14)	1	0
r/science_gender_sappho	9	30 (4)	1	0

Social impact Platform Gender

The **2,526 members** of the platform have made **86 related posts** of which other members have made **116 comments** in which they discuss the scientific evidence on gender. People have contributed reflections, scientific articles, experiences, or statistical data.

Table 3.11. Detailed table of members, comments, and feedback on Sapfo Platform.

Sapfo Platform		
No. of members	No. of Post	No. of Comments
2,526	86	116

3.2.2.3.2. Data collection on education

In the field of education, **a total of 498 posts** have been made in relation to the research on Facebook, Reddit, and Social Impact Science on Adhyayana. Of the **18,151 members** who are part of the groups/pages or forums have interacted (reactions and sharings) **1,515 times** and made **418 comments**.

Facebook Education

In the 5 selected Facebook groups/pages on education, about **90 posts** related to the results of the research project have been published. There are **17,527 members** in these groups, of which **1,506 interactions and 8 comments** have been made.

Table 3.10. Detailed table of the education Facebook groups/pages surveyed.

Facebook				
Group/Page	No. of members/followers	No. of Research Post	No. of Interactions	No. of Comments
Comunidades de Aprendizaje. Schools as Learning Communities	4,947	28	338	1
Tertulias Literarias y Musicales Dialógicas	1,107	7	30	0
Actuaciones Educativas de Éxito. Comunidades de Aprendizaje	2,617	35	972	7
Comunidade de Aprendizagem / Comunidad de Aprendizaje	8,631	8	135	0
Inclusividad NEE en CdA. Inclusion SEN in Schools as Learning Communities	225	12	31	0

Reddit Education

In the case of Reddit, 5 sub-communities were created, of which **a total of 203 posts** were made about the project and a total of 49 members took part, of which **9 interactions and 3 comments** were made.

Table 3.12. Detailed table of Reddit groups on education.

Reddit				
Group/Page	No. of members	No. of Research Post	No. of Interactions	No. of Comments
r/GruposInteractivos	13	72	3	0
r/InteractiveGroups	9	70	2	2
r/TertuliasDialogicas	12	55	1	1
r/DialogicGatherings	9	45	3	0

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

r/EducacionInclusiva	6	33	0	0
----------------------	---	----	---	---

*These Reddit groups are no longer accessible.

In January 2022, when we looked at this data again, we realised that the Reddit administrators have removed the five sub-communities.

Social Impact Science Adhyayana

The **575 members** of the platform have made **133 related posts** of which other members have made **407 comments** in which they discuss the scientific evidence on gender. People have contributed reflections, scientific articles, experiences, or statistical data.

Table 3.12. Detailed table of members, comments, and feedback on Adhyayana Platform.

Adhyayana Platform		
No. of members	No. of Post	No. of Comments
575	133	407

3.2.2.3.3. Final Research Sample

For the final analysis, the first 5 posts on education and 5 on gender that are related to scientific evidence were selected. Finally, **76 comments were analysed (20 on gender and 56 on education)**.

3.2.2.4. Social Media Communicate Observation - Analysis

The analysis of the Social Media Communicative Observation consisted in exploring the effects of introducing scientific evidence in the interactions.

The selected groups have been studied in detail using the software MAXQDA2020, to explore which of the selected actions have succeeded at enhancing participation in science.

The comment threads were listed according to the order of appearance (E1, E2, E3,...), while listing the participants (1, 2, 3...) who made contributions that were related to the object of study. Finally, **57 comments were analysed (21 on gender and 36 on education)**.

The messages have been categorised by the following selected actions and we have identified for each category the transformative and the exclusionary dimensions. The categories we have analysed are: 1) Aim of the enhancing-participation action; 2) Promoting organisation (i.e., aim; private/public); 3) Level of intervention (i.e., local/national/international; bottom-up/top-down); 4) Field of intervention;

5) Participants (targeted and real); 6) Type of participation (i.e., role of participants); 7) Level of access to scientific evidence; and 8) Social impact.

For each of these categories, the transformative dimension (i.e., what facilitates the implementation of the targeted actions) and the exclusionary dimension (i.e., obstacles hindering the implementation of the targeted actions) were identified.

The SMCO analysis has consisted mainly of a review one by one of the posts, classifying them and identifying and selecting the actions that succeed in active science participation. The consent form has been obtained from the participating members of the analysed posts.

Then we have identified the changes in the debate after the scientific evidence was introduced in the discussion.

Once data has been categorised, we have calculated the correlation between the two variables “citizen awareness of the social impact of research” and “citizen engagement in science”.

3.3 Results

3.3.1. Social Media Analytics on Gender

Following the ALLINTERACT SMA protocol, the SMA in gender has implemented a twofold strategy, including a top-down and a bottom-up approach.

3.3.1.1. Top-Down

As abovementioned, the top-down strategy was conducted in Twitter, Facebook, Instagram, and Reddit. Due to the different characteristics of each social networks, they were analysed separately.

3.3.1.1.1. Twitter (top-down)

The SMA in Twitter included the analysis of the hashtags #Equality, #Gender, #GenderEquality, #WomenRights and #HeForShe, with a total of 927 tweets. More than 8 out of 10 of the tweets (85.29%) obtained at least one retweet, being 11.16 de average number of retweets obtained.

All the identified messages were included in the transformative dimensions and included examples of how citizens were aware of the social impact of research in the field of gender.

3.3.1.1.1.1. Aim of the initiatives on Twitter (top-down)

The initiatives identified in Twitter mainly aimed to raise citizens' awareness about gender-related issues, to share evidence-based strategies to overcome gender inequalities and to increase the visibility of the impact of scientific research:

- **Awareness-raising:** The most common aim of the identified messages was to raise awareness about how the research was contributing to the identification of current problems of societies

and the overcoming of gender inequalities. These messages explicitly referred to scientific contributions to denounce social problems and to raise citizens' awareness about the importance, prevalence, and consequences of gender inequalities.

- **Share evidence-based strategies:** The aim of these messages and initiatives was to share examples of practices, policies, resources, or strategies that have been designed and developed as a result of scientific research and that can be implemented to improve gender equality. Some examples in this regard propose practices and strategies to promote bystander intervention at workplace, an institutional repository for evidence-based gender practices or a compendium of actions to design transport connectivity using a gender perspective.
- **Increase the visibility of the impact of research:** The third most common aim of the identified messages was to increase the visibility of the impact of research, including sharing scientific advances in the field of gender equality, showing the potential social impact of research, and providing examples of successful cases in which scientific research has improved citizens' lives. In this category, there were examples of campaigns to promote the visibility of women scientists in different fields of knowledge, of women's contributions to science, of how NGOs are implementing evidence-based methodologies to promote gender equality and of how companies are including gender parity in their boards. It is especially relevant the case of some messages in which one pharmaceutical company explained how gender equality and the contribution of diverse women scientists made possible COVID-19 vaccines.

3.3.1.1.1.2. Promoting organization

The identified initiatives were promoted by a wide diversity of social actors, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Promoting organizations (Twitter – Gender)

As this Figure 2 reflects, the most common promoting organization were the academia (30.75%), including scientists, universities, scientific journals and scientific platforms and citizens (29.19%), which referred to bottom-up initiatives that emerged from society, including individual citizens and associations. The presence of initiatives promoted by NGOs (11.65%), companies (9.94%) and

international organizations (9.63%) was also relevant. Finally, the least common promoting organizations in these messages were public administration and governments (1.24%).

3.3.1.1.1.3. Level of intervention

On the one hand, regarding the level of intervention, more than three-quarter parts (77.65%) of the identified initiatives were international initiatives, as shown in Figure 3. National initiatives were also relevant while local initiatives were the least common:

Figure 3. Level of intervention (Twitter – Gender)

On the other hand, the field of intervention of the identified initiatives was diverse and included topics such as gender violence, the gender gap, women leadership, the consequences of COVID-19 in women, among others. Figure 4 presents the main field of intervention covered by the identified initiatives:

Figure 5. Use of scientific evidence (Twitter – Gender)

Users’ response to tweets was different depending on the access to scientific evidence. This way, as presented in Table 14, users were more likely to interact through retweets with messages that contained some type of scientific evidence (including both, supposed and certified evidence):

Table 14. The average number of interactions by access to scientific evidence.

	Average number of RT of messages with no scientific evidence	Average number of RT of messages with some type of scientific evidence
#Equality	4.98	3.82
#HeForShe	2	8.50
#Gender	5.23	17.86
#GenderEquality	2.13	6.98

Table 14 shows how, in three of the hashtags, the tweets that were more likely to be retweeted were those that contained some type of scientific evidence, including scientific articles from journals indexed in Journal Citation Reports or Scopus as well as statistics from reports or official data.

3.3.1.1.2. Facebook

The top-down strategy in Facebook consisted of the identification of messages in the pages Never Alone, NOH8 Campaign, World Wide Women, Women Rights News and Equality Now. According to their descriptions, the aim of the two first pages is to raise awareness about sexual abuse in the first

case and LGBT discrimination in the second. The other three are pages where news related to gender issues and women's rights are shared. A total of 9 messages, including posts and comments were included in the final analysis.

The analysis of the dimensions concluded that the 9 identified messages corresponded to the transformative dimension, which mean that contained examples of citizens' awareness of the social impact of research in the field of gender.

3.3.1.1.2.1. Aim of the initiatives on Facebook

Most of the identified messages were examples of how citizens are aware of the social impact of scientific research in the field of gender and use scientific contributions to share evidence-based discussions on Facebook pages. However, there were two posts that included examples of the visibility of scientific research and the promotion of evidence-based strategies to overcome gender violence:

- **Evidence-based discussion:** Most of the messages in this category included examples of how citizens who were aware of the social impact of scientific research were able to use scientific contributions in discussions about gender issues and based their arguments on scientific claims.
- **Overcoming gender violence:** One post was identified in this category and included an example of citizens promoting bystander intervention in situations of gender violence as well as the help signal for victims.

Visibility of scientific research: One post was related to this topic and included the sharing of scientific advances related to women's health, specifically in the field of endometriosis.

3.3.1.1.2.2. Promoting organization

On Facebook the promoting organizations included two social actors: citizens and the press, as presented in Figure 6:

Figure 6. Promoting organization (Facebook – Gender)

More than three-quarter parts of the messages (77.78%) emerged from individual citizens, while 22.22 % of the messages were promoted by the press. The initiatives promoted by citizens included citizens mobilizations, citizens' platforms, and individuals. Unlike other social platforms, Facebook is a network in which individual citizens play an important role to discuss with other citizens.

3.3.1.1.2.3. Level of intervention

Regarding the level of intervention, all the identified messages included examples of initiatives or debates at the international level, with international campaigns or discussions of international news. As for the field of intervention, the main topics covered were related to the conceptualization and the differences between gender and sex and also to transphobia and violence against women, as shown in Figure 7.

Gender VS Sex

Women
Violence
Gender
Health Transphobia

Figure 7. Topics addressed by the identified initiatives (Facebook)

3.3.1.1.2.4. Audience and access to scientific evidence

All the messages contained examples of initiatives addressed to the whole society, that reached that part of society who is actively involved in Facebook pages. In all the cases, the expected role of the target audience was to discuss and debate gender-related topics. For this purpose, access to scientific evidence was present in 77.78% of the cases, as described in Figure 8:

Figure 8. Use of scientific evidence (Facebook- Gender)

Most of the messages (66.67%) contained examples of supposed scientific evidence, which referred to statistical data and results from research that comes from a report or from sources that cannot be

certified to be indexed in scientific databases such as Journal Citation Reports or Scopus. The rest of the messages were examples of access to certified scientific evidence (11.11%) or of no use of scientific evidence (22.22%).

3.3.1.1.3. *Instagram*

The SMA in Instagram included 21 posts from the hashtags #womenempowerment, #domesticviolence, #womenrights, #feminism and #genderequality. Due to the characteristics of the social network, the analysis in this case considered as a unit of analysis the whole post, including the text and the image.

The analysis of the dimensions concluded that all the identified messages corresponded to the transformative dimension, which represents that all messages contained examples of citizens' awareness of the social impact of research in the field of gender.

3.3.1.1.3.1. Aim of the initiatives on Instagram

The posts identified in Instagram mainly aimed to denounce situations of gender violence or gender inequalities worldwide, to raise citizens' awareness about gender-related issues and to increase the visibility of the impact of scientific research in gender:

- **Social denounce:** Some posts aimed to denounce the situation of violence and inequality that suffered many women around the world. All these posts included how citizens were aware of the importance of scientific research in the identification of such inequalities.
- **Awareness-raising:** The posts within this category aimed to raise awareness about how research can contribute to the overcoming of gender violence, through the identification of the prevalence of situations of violence and the promotion of evidence-based strategies to be implemented in different contexts, including companies, educational contexts, and science.
- **Visibility of scientific research in gender:** Some posts included examples of how scientific research contributes to the implementation of evidence-based strategies that can promote gender equality. The main examples in this vein, include gender-equitable boards in companies and the reduction of gender violence through sport.

3.3.1.1.3.2. Promoting organization

The identified initiatives were promoted by several social actors, ranging from associations (36.36%) to press (4.55%) and academia (4.55%), as presented in Figure 9:

Figure 9. Promoting organization (Instagram – Gender)

As observed in the picture, most initiatives were bottom-up and included promoting organizations, such as associations (36.36%), NGOs (22.73%) and citizens (13.64%), which represent almost three quarters parts of all the social actors. On the contrary, those initiatives promoted by the academia and international organizations, such as the United Nations or the OECD represented 4.55% and 9.09%.

3.3.1.1.3.3. Level and field of intervention

Most of the identified messages corresponded to initiatives implemented at the national level (72.22%), followed by at international (22.22%) and local level (5.56%), as presented in Figure 10:

Figure 10. Level of intervention (Instagram – Gender)

The analysis of the field of intervention of the initiatives pointed out that the main topic was related to denouncing gender violence, gender inequalities and sexual harassment, although topics such as gender bias, COVID-19 and gender policies were also relevant (Figure 11):

Figure 11. Topics addressed by the identified initiatives (Instagram)

3.3.1.1.3.4. Audience and access to scientific evidence

Almost all Instagram posts were addressed to society as a whole or did not include information about any specific target groups. However, one post included an example of a sports program to reduce gender violence and was addressed specifically to girls and young women. Another post in this line included some recommendations to reduce the gender gap and targeted companies and firms.

More than half of the messages (61.90%) included access to some type of scientific evidence. This scientific evidence was in most cases statistical data about the prevalence of gender violence or gender inequalities but in other cases included access to full reports. Figure 12 presents the distribution of messages that contained some type of scientific evidence:

Figure 12. Use of scientific evidence (Instagram – Gender)

3.3.1.1.4. Reddit

The SMA on Reddit included the analysis of posts and comments included in 5 communities: r/PurplePill, r/bisexual, r/FEMRADebates, r/Feminism and r/Feminisms. A total of 34 messages including posts and comments were analysed within this topic. It is important to mention that on Reddit communities there are two types of messages: posts and comments. Both types of messages were included in the analysis.

Most of the identified messages contained examples of citizens' awareness of the social impact of scientific research in gender and were included in the transformative dimension (94.12%). Figure 13 shows the proportion of messages included in the transformative and exclusionary dimensions.

Figure 13. Distribution of dimensions (Reddit – Gender)

The 5.88% of the messages that were included in the exclusionary dimension included barriers to citizens' awareness of the impact of scientific research, such as messages that undervalue scientific contributions. Reddit users can vote or downvote other users' comments and posts. In this line, those messages in the exclusionary dimension obtained an average rating of 2 votes, while transformative messages obtained an average of 69 votes.

3.3.1.1.4.1. Aim of the initiatives on Reddit

Two main objectives were identified in the analysed messages on Reddit. On the one hand, initiatives in which citizens shared evidence-based discussions about gender issued and on the other hand, awareness-raising messages about gender violence:

- **Evidence-based discussion:** This group included examples of how citizens who were aware of the social impact of scientific research promoted discussions on Reddit communities based on scientific contributions in gender issues and based their arguments on scientific claims.
- **Raise awareness:** The messages in this group included examples of citizens sharing how the research was contributing to the identification and the overcoming of gender violence worldwide. These messages explicitly referred to scientific contributions to denounce gender or domestic violence.

3.3.1.1.4.2. Promoting organization

As abovementioned, Reddit is a social network organized in communities, where users' interactions can be found in two types of messages: posts and comments. The cornerstone of this social network is that both types of messages are shared by individual users who can propose a specific topics for the

debate, ask for advice or share news with other members of the community. For this reason, unlike other social networks, on Reddit all the identified messages emerged from individual citizens and not from companies, academia, or public administration, which implies that is completely bottom-up.

3.3.1.1.4.3. Level and field of intervention

First, regarding the level of intervention, almost all the messages included initiatives implemented at the international level (96.43%) and only 3.57% of the messages referred to national initiatives (Figure 14):

Figure 14. Level of intervention (Reddit – Gender)

Second, regarding the field of intervention, “gender” and “violence” were the most recurrent field in the analysed communities (Figure 15). However, other messages included discussions around relevant topics, such as attraction in relationships, sexual abuse, gender bias and homophobia, among others.

Figure 15. Topics addressed by the identified initiatives (Reddit)

3.3.1.1.4.4. Audience and access to scientific evidence

In all cases the target audience were other Reddit users who are involved in the same community and the expected role of the target audience was to contribute to the debate and join the discussion. These discussions included in more than half of the cases, some type of access to scientific evidence, including statistical data, reports, or scientific articles. Figure 16 shows the access to scientific evidence.

Figure 16. Access to scientific evidence (Reddit – Gender)

As presented in Figure 16, 34.41% of the messages included supposed scientific sources and 19.35% included results from certified scientific evidence from Journal Citation Reports or Scopus. It is also relevant to mention that 2.15% of the messages included citizens reclaiming other users to provide scientific evidence to prove their comments and to base their statements.

Unlike on other social networks, Reddit users can vote or downvote the comments written by other users. The analysis of the average punctuations of the comments depending on the access to scientific evidence is summarised in Table 15:

Table 15. Average comments' punctuation by the access to scientific evidence.

Level of access to scientific evidence	Average punctuation
No scientific evidence	4.33
Supposed scientific evidence	73.20
Certified scientific evidence	10.98
Reclaimed scientific evidence	76.00

The results in Table 15 point that those comments that were based on people's opinions and contained no access to scientific evidence obtain the lowest punctuations, while those that reclaimed scientific evidence to other users were rated the highest. Comments that provide access to some type of scientific evidence obtained higher punctuations than those that did not provide the access to scientific sources. This finding suggests that users value those contributions to the debate that are based on scientific sources and not on people's opinions.

3.3.1.2. Bottom-Up

The bottom-up strategy in SMA was implemented on Twitter and included hashtags that were retrieved from the daily trending topics in all European countries.

3.3.1.2.1 Twitter (bottom-up)

This section contains the SMA on Twitter and includes the hashtags #IStandWithLinda, #EqualPayDay, #WiMINConference21, #ReclaimTheStreets and #EnoughisEnough and a total number of 40 tweets. 85% of the messages were retweeted at least once, obtaining an average of 2.42 retweets.

The analysis of the dimensions concluded that all the messages identified on Twitter (bottom-up) corresponded to the transformative dimension, which means that contained examples of citizens' awareness of the social impact of research in the field of gender.

3.3.1.2.1.1. Aim of the initiatives on Twitter (bottom-up)

Most of the tweets aimed to raise awareness about gender-related issues, but there were also examples of proposals of evidence-based methodologies:

- **Awareness-raising:** The posts within this category aimed to raise awareness about how research can contribute to overcoming the gender pay gap in companies and the gender gap in medicine. Additionally, there were also examples of how citizens took advantage of news of cases of gender violence to denounce situations of gender violence and sexual harassment worldwide.
- **Proposal of evidence-based methodologies:** The messages in this group included posts in which German policymakers proposed new and evidence-based methodologies to identify, measure and analyse the gender pay gap in companies and firms.

3.3.1.2.1.2. Promoting organization

The initiatives identified in the bottom-up strategy were promoted by diverse social agents, as presented in Figure 17:

Figure 17. Promoting organization (Twitter – Bottom-up)

More than half of the initiatives (55%) were promoted by academia and were all related to the scientific conference Women in Medicine of Ireland. Citizens and associations represented 15% of each one and included contributions from individual citizens and also associations such as associations of women in business. Finally, the press and policymakers were also present.

3.3.1.2.1.3. Level and field of intervention

As abovementioned, an important proportion of messages were related to the conference Women in Medicine in Ireland, which was implemented at the national level. In the same line, the period of the extraction coincides with the Equal Pay Day in Germany. Therefore, most of the messages (95%) corresponded to initiatives implemented at the national level, although there were also international initiatives, as shown in Figure 18:

Figure 18. Level of intervention. (Twitter – Bottom-up)

As for the field of intervention, the initiatives addressed topics such as women in medicine (including women's health, the gender gap in scientific careers, visibility of scientific contributions promoted by women and the recognition of the importance of gender diversity in research teams). Other topics that were present included the gender pay gap or sexual violence, as shown in Figure 19.

Figure 19. Topics addressed by the identified initiatives (Twitter – Bottom-up)

3.3.1.2.1.4. Audience and access to scientific evidence

The target audience included on the one hand scientists who participated in the Women in Medicine conference and on the other hand, citizens and society from Germany involved in the Equal Pay Day. In both cases the expected role of the target audience was to discuss and debate around the topics covered by the initiatives and for this reason, they had access to some type of scientific evidence. In this vein, more than 80% of the messages included access of the target audience to scientific evidence (including supposed and certified scientific evidence). The following Figure 20 represents this finding:

Figure 20. Access to scientific evidence (Twitter – Bottom-up)

As in the top-down analysis, in this case, users also interact differently with the content depending on the access to scientific evidence. In the bottom-up approach, users were also more likely to retweet messages that contained some type of scientific evidence, including certified scientific evidence (scientific articles published in journals indexed in Journal Citation Reports or Scopus) and supposed scientific evidence (statistics, official data, and reports, among others). The following Table 16 summarises the average number of retweets in the two hashtags that contained messages with and without scientific evidence:

Table 16. Average number of interactions by access to scientific evidence.

Hashtags	Average of RT in messages with no scientific evidence	Average of RT in messages with some type of scientific evidence
#WiMINConference21	0.67	2.74
#EqualPayDay	2.28	2.44

Although the difference is more noticeable in the first hashtag, the number of retweets obtained by messages with access to some type of scientific evidence was higher in both hashtags.

3.3.2. Social Media Analytics on Education

The SMA in education, as well as in gender, has followed a twofold strategy, including a top-down and a bottom-up approach.

3.3.2.1. Top-Down

The top-down strategy was conducted on four social networks: Twitter, Facebook, Instagram, and Reddit. Due to the different characteristics of each social network, the messages were analysed separately.

3.3.2.1.1 Twitter (top-down)

The SMA in Twitter using a top-down strategy consisted of the analysis of the hashtags #PublicEducation, #School, #Students, #Learning and #Education. A total of 617 tweets were included in the final analysis. Almost all of the tweets got at least one Retweet (98.06%), with an average of 9.45 retweets.

All the identified messages contained examples of citizens' awareness of the social impact of scientific research in gender and were included in the transformative dimension.

3.3.2.1.1.1. Aim of the initiative on Twitter (top-down)

The analysis of the aims of the initiatives brought 5 main objectives:

- **Raise awareness:** The messages in this group included examples of messages sharing how the research was contributing to the improvement of quality education for students from all over the world. Some initiatives that particularly stood out above the others; aimed to raise awareness about the importance of afterschool programs in educational achievement, and about the impact of school meals and milk programs in schools with children from low socioeconomic status. In the same line, some initiatives that aimed to denounce situations of inequalities within educational contexts, such as racism in schools or gender violence in universities were also noticeable. These initiatives included diverse podcasts, such as campaigns, podcasts, conferences, or workshops, among others.
- **Promote evidence-based policies:** These messages were focused in the improvement of education through the promotion of policies based on scientific evidence. This way, the messages aimed to promote evidence-based policies to stop school segregation, to promote science education and to implement feeding programs in schools with high levels of poverty.
- **Share evidence-based resources:** These initiatives aimed to share evidence-based resources, practices or activities with schools, teachers, or parents. The proposed resources addressed diverse topics, such as statistic literacy, gender, remote learning, reading for students with dyslexia, recycling, and computer science, among others.

- **Promotion of science:** Some of the initiatives aimed to promote science education in society, by increasing the levels of scientific literacy and fostering citizen science. Three types of initiatives were identified in this group: 1) some initiatives included coding challenges that citizens could join and learn some of the coding algorithms, 2) conferences and debates for all citizens about topics related to children's education and mental health, and 3) share the latest scientific advances to citizens to increase the visibility and the awareness of the impact of scientific research.
- **Successful cases:** The examples in this group included messages that shared successful cases of how research contributed to improving the quality of education. The key point of this group is that citizens not only shared the results or the benefits in education but linked these benefits to previous scientific research. This way, the successful cases included examples of connectivity projects that made possible remote learning in rural zones, experiences of STEM projects that included hands-on activities and the improvement of quality education through teachers' training.

3.3.2.1.1.2. Promoting organization

Almost half of the initiatives (41.33%) were promoted by citizens or citizens' campaigns, in contrast with the 0.18% that were led by the public administration. Figure 21 presents the diversity of social agents that promoted the identified initiatives:

Figure 21. Promoting organization (Twitter – Education)

As shown in Figure 21, those initiatives that emerged from society in a bottom-up approach (including those that were promoted by citizens, associations, and NGOs) represented almost two thirds of all the initiatives (62.52%). On the contrary, top-down initiatives promoted by academia or public administration represented less than 20%. Among the main associations, there are youth, teachers,

The more frequent topics were on the one hand “Afterschool”, due to the citizens’ campaigns that aimed to raise awareness about the importance of afterschool programs and to implement these programs in schools, and in the other hand “School”, mainly because of the messages that included the impact of scientific research in schools during COVID-19 pandemic. Other common topics were “Artificial Intelligence”, “Learning”, “Education”, “Brain”, “Civil Rights”, “Science”, among others.

3.3.2.1.1.4. Audience and access to scientific evidence

Most of the identified initiatives were addressed to all citizens and did not specify a target group. However, those initiatives that aimed to promote evidence-based policies specifically targeted policymakers, and those that shared evidence-based resources and activities were focused on teachers, schools, parents, and educational professionals. In the same line, initiatives that contained examples of educational projects to promote science education targeted children and youth. When the target audience was specified, their role was active and included joining challenges, participating in activities, discussing with professionals and citizens, and implementing evidence-based strategies.

The access of the target audience to scientific evidence included initiatives with no access to scientific evidence, with access to supposed scientific evidence (statistics, official data, or reports) and certified scientific evidence (articles published in journals indexed in Scopus or Journal Citation Reports). Figure 24 represents the access of the target audience to scientific evidence:

Figure 24. Access to scientific evidence (Twitter -Education)

More than 7 out of 10 initiatives included access to some type of scientific evidence (45.81% to supposed scientific evidence and 25.15% to certified scientific evidence). Citizens’ reactions and responses to the identified messages were different depending on the access to scientific evidence, as shown in Table 17:

Table 17. Average number of interactions by access to scientific evidence.

<i>Hashtags</i>	Average RT of messages with no access to scientific evidence	Average RT of messages with access to supposed scientific evidence	Average RT of messages with access to certified scientific evidence
Students	2.91	4.20	4.88
School	3.59	4.29	3.93
Education	11.23	20.15	6.27
Learning	2.52	12.20	3.12

Table 17 summarises how, the average number of retweets gained by messages with access to some type of scientific evidence (including supposed and certified evidence) was higher than the average of retweets with no access to scientific evidence. Public Education was not included in the analysis because did not contain messages in all the categories.

3.3.2.1.2. Facebook

The top-down strategy on Facebook consisted of the analysis of the pages Teacher2Teacher, WeAreTeachers, Edutopia, MindShift, and Education Week. The first two are spaces of dialogue among teachers and educational professionals; whereas the other three are pages where educational news are shared. A total of 146 messages, including posts and comments were included in the final analysis.

All the messages were included in the transformative dimension because contained examples of awareness of the impact of scientific research.

3.3.2.1.2.1. Aim of the initiatives on Facebook

The analysed Facebook pages were agora spaces for teachers to discuss and to ask for advice and provide support. Therefore, the main aims of the identified messages were related to discussions about evidence-based resources and to the exchange of evidence-based strategies:

- **Discussions about evidence-based resources:** Especially one of the pages (WeAreTeachers) included examples of how teachers are aware of the impact of research on education promoted and joined discussions about evidence-based resources in the didactics of mathematics. The main topic of these discussions was finger counting and other related resources.
- **Share evidence-based strategies:** This aim was present in all the analysed pages and included teachers and citizens sharing evidence-based strategies and practices to be implemented at the school level or in classrooms. These strategies were related to the guarantee of children's health and safety in schools during the pandemic, reading methodologies, racism in schools and summer learning loss, among others.

3.3.2.1.2.2. Promoting organization

More than 9 out of 10 initiatives (91.49%) were promoted by citizens, as shown in Figure 25, although initiatives coordinated by the press, schools and scientists were also present:

Figure 25. Promoting organization (Facebook – Education)

As mentioned before, two of the analysed pages constituted agora spaces for teachers to share resources, discuss or ask for advice. For this reason, in Facebook, unlike other social networks, most of the messages emerged from individual citizens, who use these spaces to interact with their peers.

3.3.2.1.2.3. Level and field of intervention

The analysed Facebook pages are international spaces for discussion among teachers from all over the world. Therefore, almost all the initiatives and messages targeted the international level, as seen in Figure 26:

Figure 26. Level of intervention (Facebook – Education)

Only in two cases, the messages were related to local or national initiatives. The former referred to the actions implemented in one school to guarantee safety during the pandemic, whereas the latter was related to the influence of the national curriculum.

Regarding the field of intervention, most of the messages were related to a discussion among teachers regarding finger counting and other issues related to the didactics of mathematics. For, this reason, as shown in Figure 27, it is the most frequent topic:

Figure 27. Topics addressed by the identified initiatives (Facebook)

In addition to the didactics of mathematics, other relevant fields of the intervention included summer learning, mental disorders, evidence-based policies, educational expectations, or educational psychology, among others.

3.3.2.1.2.4. Audience and access to scientific evidence

According to the description of two of the analysed pages, which included most of the identified messages, the content of these pages mainly targeted teachers and school professionals. Therefore, the main target audience of the initiatives on Facebook included teachers and school professionals, although some of the messages included a wider audience of citizens. The expected role of the target audience was to discuss the topics proposed in the different posts of the pages; thus, teachers interact with each other writing comments and answering to the proposed topics. The presence of scientific evidence in these debates was not very widespread, and teachers used to base their arguments on their working experience. Nevertheless, almost 20% of the messages contained access to some type of scientific evidence, including supposed scientific evidence (statistics, data from reports or scientific articles from non-indexed journals) or certified scientific evidence (articles from scientific journals indexed in Journal Citation Reports or Scopus), as shown in Figure 28:

Figure 28. Access to scientific evidence (Facebook – Education)

3.3.2.1.3. Instagram

The SMA on Instagram included the analysis of the hashtags #QualityEducation, #StopBullying, #ScienceEducation, #Learning and #Education. A total of 66 posts were included in the final analysis. Due to the characteristics of the social network, the analysis of Instagram includes not only the content of the post, but also the image.

Most of the posts were included in the transformative dimension, as they contained examples of citizens' awareness of the impact of scientific research in education, but 4.55% of the messages included barriers to the awareness of the impact of scientific research and therefore, were classified as exclusionary. Figure 29 represents these findings:

Figure 29. Distribution of dimensions on Instagram (education)

3.3.2.1.3.1. Aim of the initiatives on Instagram

Instagram initiatives was mainly related to three objectives: awareness-raising, evidence-based actions, and the promotion of scientific literacy:

- **Awareness-raising:** The messages in which citizens used scientific contributions to raise awareness of the importance of educational research in the reduction of inequalities were found in all the hashtags. Despite the differences on the topics of the messages depending on the hashtag, the main topics addressed were school bullying, the impacts of COVID-19 on education and the importance of education for the promotion of health.
- **Evidence-based actions:** These messages included campaigns and individual initiatives that mainly aimed to address bullying using evidence-based approaches. Among the proposed actions, it is remarkable how users propose bystander intervention and the provision of social and mental support to victims of violence as effective strategies to overcome school violence. A common characteristic of these messages is that propose evidence-based actions linking these proposals to previous research that demonstrated their effectiveness and recognizing scientific contributions that made them possible.
- **Promotion of scientific literacy:** Some of the initiatives aimed to promote scientific literacy and although were mainly found in the hashtag #ScienceEducation, they were also present in the other hashtags. Two types of initiatives were identified in this group. First, there were initiatives that aimed to share the latest scientific advances in fields such as the environment, cancer, neurons, engineering, the universe and autism, among others, to increase the visibility

and awareness of the impact of scientific research. The format of these initiatives was diverse and included campaigns, videos, podcasts, infographics, and scientific facts. Second, there were initiatives where citizens played a more active role and included science festivals, contests, and conferences where participants could interact, discuss and join activities related to science education, the environment, chemistry, health education and computer science.

3.3.2.1.3.2. Promoting organization

Instagram is a social network with a relevant presence of citizen-led initiatives. Therefore, messages containing bottom-up initiatives (including citizens, NGOs, associations or schools) represented almost two-thirds of the messages (63.16%), as presented in Figure 30:

Figure 30. Promoting organization (Instagram – Education)

In this case, it is also relevant the presence of press and companies, which represent 15.79% and 12.28% respectively.

3.3.2.1.3.3. Level and field of information

The level of intervention of the identified interventions was mainly international, despite the presence of national, local, and even school-level interventions, as presented in Figure 31:

Figure 31. Level of intervention (Instagram – Education)

Figure 31 shows that on the one hand, more than 7 out of 10 messages (70.97%) corresponded to international initiatives, followed by national (17.74%). On the other hand, small-scale interventions, implemented in schools or cities represented 4.84% and 6.45%.

Regarding the field of intervention, the most common topic was bullying, as one of the hashtags was #StopBullying. As presented in Figure 32, other relevant topics addressed in the interventions were COVID-19 and vaccines, educational actions to preserve the environment, or diverse scientific contributions, such as artificial intelligence, neurones, chemistry, science, chemistry, the universe, animals, among others.

Figure 32. Topics addressed by the identified initiatives (Instagram)

These scientific contributions were mainly related to the hashtag #ScienceEducation, which was broadly used on March 14th, which is the Science Education Day in several countries, including USA and India. As mentioned in section 2, the period for the extraction of data collection was March 4th - March 17th. This could be one of the underlying reasons why most of the topics within this category were related to initiatives of science education.

3.3.2.1.3.4. Audience and access to scientific evidence

The target audience of the identified initiatives included youth, children, teachers, members of the educational community and schools. However, most of the initiatives did not include enough information to identify a specific target group within society. In most of the cases, the audience had no specific role. However, in the initiatives shared to celebrate Science Education Day, there were examples of contests, challenges, and activities that participants could join and take an active role in. This active role included home experiments for children, actions for scientists to increase the visibility of their research or science activities in educational contexts.

As mentioned before, the main aim of these initiatives was often to raise awareness about the prevalence and consequences of bullying or to involve children in science activities that increase the visibility of the impact of research. Therefore, the access of participants and the audience to scientific evidence was frequent in the identified initiatives and almost two thirds (64.28%) included access to some type of scientific evidence (supposed and certified scientific evidence), as presented in Figure 33:

Figure 33. Access to scientific evidence (Instagram – Education)

In most cases, the access to scientific evidence consisted of providing statistics or data from research in the post or in the image, which in some cases was complemented by a link to the scientific source. On the contrary, 35.71% of the messages included no access to scientific sources. It is important to mention that, in general terms, the use of scientific evidence is not widespread on Instagram and

therefore, it is significant that users included some type of scientific evidence on their messages. In most cases, these references were mainly statistics included in the image or the citation of official reports to reinforce the argument of the post.

3.3.2.1.4. Reddit

The SMA on Reddit included five communities: r/Teachers, r/Teaching, r/ApplyingToCollege, r/Science and r/Education. Three of these communities are mostly constituted by teachers or educational professionals that share debates related to their professional experience. One of the others is formed by students and the other includes citizens from all sectors and countries. It is important to mention that on Reddit communities there are two types of messages: posts and comments. Both types of messages are shared by individual users who can propose specific topics for the debate, ask for advice or share news with other members of the community.

Of the total of 206 messages that were analysed in this social network, only two messages (0.97%) included barriers to the awareness of the impact of scientific research related to the undervalue of science and thus, were classified as exclusionary (Figure 34).

Figure 34. Distribution of dimensions on Reddit (education)

As presented in Figure 34, 99.03% of the messages included examples of awareness of the impact of scientific research and were included in the transformative dimension. It is important to clarify that on Reddit communities users can vote or downvote other users' comments. The punctuation of the two exclusionary comments was -14, while the average of the transformative comments in the same community (r/science) was 19.

3.3.2.1.4.1. Aim of the initiatives on Reddit

The most common objective of the initiatives was to engage in evidence-based discussions, to ask and provide advice and to raise awareness about how research can improve education:

- **Evidence-based discussion:** Especially one of the communities (r/science) included examples of how citizen, who was aware of the social impact of scientific research promoted and joined discussions on Reddit communities based on scientific contributions of research and based their arguments on scientific claims.
- **Ask for evidence-based practices:** Two of the communities constituted spaces for teachers to ask for and provide advice and support. In this line, there was a group of messages that included teachers asking for evidence-based practices about topics such as the English language and students with special needs.
- **Awareness-raising:** The posts within this category aimed to raise awareness about how research is contributing to improving the quality of education for all students. In this line, there were examples of users that aimed to raise citizens' awareness about some theories that are not based on scientific evidence, such as "learning styles" or school segregation.

3.3.2.1.4.2. Promoting organization

As described before, Reddit communities are constituted by individual citizens who propose topics for discussion, interact with each other about the proposed topics or ask and provide advice. Therefore, all the analysed messages emerged from individual citizens, which implied that the SMA on Reddit was completely bottom-up and included the voices of the communities. Three of these communities were formed by teachers or educational professionals, another by students and the other includes citizens from all sectors and countries. In some of the cases, the users identified themselves as teachers, educational professionals, or health professionals but in all cases discuss with other citizens on equal footing.

3.3.2.1.4.3. Level and field of intervention

The selected communities included users from different countries and included topics and initiatives of international relevance. The following Figure 35, represents these topics:

Figure 36. Access to scientific evidence (Reddit – Education)

Unlike in other social networks, on Reddit communities it was important the proportion of users that reclaimed scientific evidence or discuss the reliability of the provided studies (3.07%). As mentioned before, on Reddit user vote or downvote other users' comments and the analysis of the punctuations of the comments in r/science point out that those comments with no access to scientific evidence obtained lower punctuations, in contrast with those that provided or reclaimed scientific evidence (see Table 18).

Table 18. Differences in the average punctuation by use of scientific sources.

Level of access to scientific evidence	Average in r/science
No scientific evidence	10.69
Certified scientific evidence	11.51
Supposed scientific evidence	19.21
Reclaimed scientific evidence	26.44

3.3.2.2. Bottom-Up

The bottom-up strategy was implemented on Twitter and included hashtags related to education that were retrieved from the daily trending topics in all European countries.

3.3.2.2.1. Twitter (bottom-up)

The SMA in Twitter using a bottom-up strategy consisted of the analysis of the hashtags #books, #Wikipedia, #FutureOfEurope, #DigitalDecade and #Schools. A total of **1182** tweets were included in the final analysis. Almost nine out of ten (88.66%) were retweeted at least once, with an average

number of 1147.29 retweets. Figure 37 presents the proportion of messages that were included in each dimension:

Figure 37. Distribution of dimensions on Twitter – Bottom-up (education)

As Figure 37 shows, more than 9 out of 10 of the messages (93.03%) were included in the transformative dimension because included examples of awareness of the impact of scientific research. The 6.97% that were considered exclusionary included voices that undervalued scientific contributions or that claimed that Wikipedia was not a trustworthy source, did not provide any argument and they attacked the encyclopaedia and all the people who use Wikipedia. Despite the existence of these exclusionary messages, citizens' responses to transformative and exclusionary messages were different. This way, the average number of retweets obtained by the messages included in the exclusionary dimension was 1.41 and the average of retweets of transformative messages was 1238.34.

3.3.2.2.1.1. Aim of the initiatives on Twitter (bottom-up)

This section presents the aims of the identified initiatives, which can be classified into 5 groups: awareness-raising initiatives, visibility of evidence-based policies, promotion of scientific literacy, evidence-based discussions, and value of open science:

- **Raise awareness:** The tweets in this group aimed to raise awareness about how research contributed to improving not only the quality of education but also citizens' lives in broader terms. In this line, there were examples of users that aimed to raise citizens' awareness about some scientific contributions that have been traditionally silenced or about female scientists that made possible scientific advances. These tweets were found in all the hashtags. It is important to mention that there was a campaign in #wikipedia that aimed to raise awareness about scientific contributions in gender violence and to promote bystander intervention and support to victims. This campaign shared the Wikipedia entry related to the gender violence help signal and obtained an average of approximately 174 retweets.
- **Visibility of evidence-based policies:** There were messages that aimed to promote and increase the visibility of evidence-based policies. These messages were mainly found in the

hashtags #FutureOfEurope and #DigitalDecade, which were the official hashtags used to launch the new European digital strategy. In addition, messages within this group aimed to promote evidence-based policies that include citizens' voices.

- **Promotion of scientific literacy:** Some of the initiatives aimed to promote scientific literacy among citizens and were mainly found in the hashtags #wikipedia and #learning, although they were present in all the hashtags. Most of the initiatives aimed to share the latest scientific advances in fields such as machine learning, artificial intelligence, gender violence, women contributions to scientific development, genetics, or COVID-19, among others. These messages contributed to increasing the visibility and the awareness of the impact of scientific research.
- **Evidence-based discussions:** tweets within this group were shared by individual users, who replied to existing debates using scientific contributions and highlighting how these contributions had improved citizens' lives. These tweets contained the argument with the scientific contribution and the evidence, which was a link to a Wikipedia article with access to a scientific source. These discussions addressed topics, such as energy, LGBT violence, freedom of speech, racism, music, law, wars, or health, among others.
- **Value of open science:** there were also discussions where users valued Wikipedia and open science for their accurateness and reliability. In these debates, there were users who undervalued science and Wikipedia, which represents a barrier to the awareness of scientific contribution. However, these users only based their arguments on personal opinions and attacks to encyclopaedia and all the people who use it. On the contrary, citizens who defend the accurateness of Wikipedia defended the value of the encyclopaedia as a source of open science and remarked the presence of certified scientific evidence at the end of each article.

3.3.2.2.1.2. Promoting Organization

The identified initiatives emerged from social actors from all sectors of society, as represented in Figure 38:

Figure 38. Promoting organization (Twitter – Bottom-up)

More than half of the messages (50.73%) were promoted by the press and included a few initiatives related to the use of gender-neutral pronouns that were intensively retweeted. More than one-quarter part of the messages emerged from citizens and included individuals and citizens' campaigns that aimed to reduce pollution near schools. It is also remarkable the presence of policymakers (14.01%), which include politicians, individual policymakers, and political parties. Finally, there were also initiatives led by academia, international organizations, NGOs, companies, and public administrations.

3.3.2.2.1.3. Level and field of intervention

Regarding the level of intervention, more than half of the messages (54.33%) corresponded to initiatives implemented at the local level, mainly due to the abovementioned example of a highly retweeted initiative about gender-neutral pronouns. International (32.94%) and national (12.74%) initiatives were also present in the analysed tweets (Figure 39):

Figure 39. Level of intervention (Twitter – Bottom-up)

The fields covered by the initiatives were also diverse and diverged from one hashtag to the others. The main topics that emerged from the analysis are represented in Figure 40:

Figure 40. Topics addressed by the identified initiatives (Facebook – Bottom-up)

Each hashtag provided examples of initiatives in different fields. This way, the hashtag #wikipedia contained examples of “open science” and “gender violence help signal”, #FutureOfEurope was centred on “AI” (Artificial Intelligence), #DigitalDecade on “Digital Transformation” and #schools on “gender language” and “COVID-19 & school”. This variety of topics was possible due to the bottom-up approach in the selection of the hashtags, which were retrieved from the daily trending topics.

3.3.2.2.1.4. Audience and access to scientific evidence

Most messages were addressed to the whole society and did not specify a target audience. However, those messages retrieved from the hashtags #FutureOfEurope and #DigitalDecade, which included the launch of the European digital strategy, also targeted policymakers, and governments. The expected role from the target audience was also diverse; while policymakers were supposed to take the scientific evidence and use it for the design and implementation of evidence-based policies, citizens were mainly supposed to join campaigns and mobilizations or to discuss with other citizens using scientific arguments. This is the case, for example of the discussions shared within the hashtag #wikipedia, in which citizens discussed several contributions of research, providing scientific arguments to the debate. However, not all the messages included this access to scientific sources, as presented in Figure 41:

Figure 41. Access to scientific evidence (Twitter – Bottom-up)

In this case it is especially remarkable that more than eight out of ten messages contained access to some type of scientific evidence. In this line, almost two thirds (62.96%) of the analysed messages contained access to certified scientific evidence published in journals indexed in Journal Citation Reports or Scopus and 23.08% of supposed scientific evidence, such as reports or statistical data. In addition, in 4 messages (0.32%) Twitter users reclaimed other users to base their statements on scientific data or to provide a scientific source to confirm their statements.

In addition, when messages include access to scientific evidence, citizens tend to interact more with the message and to value it positively. In consequence, the average number of retweets varies depending on the access to scientific evidence, as presented in Table 19:

Table 19. Average number of interactions by access to scientific evidence.

Level of access to scientific evidence	Average number of retweets
No scientific evidence	6.20
Supposed scientific evidence	55.04

Certified scientific evidence	1725.99
Reclaimed scientific evidence	2

3.4. Results of the Social Media Communicative Observation

The following are the results obtained from the Social Media Communication Observation on gender and education issues. These results are divided into three parts: the first part is an analysis of the comments identified in relation to the five themes related to the project objectives; the second part refers to the analysis of the posts of the users who participated in the debate and produced a change once the evidence of the social impact of the research was introduced; the third and final part shows the correlation between awareness of the social impact of the research and engagement with science.

3.4.1. Topic b) Citizen awareness of the impact of scientific research

The users who have participated in the analysed social media posts have participated by contributing ideas and arguments to the debates that have risen on education and gender. These contributions have often been supported by scientific articles indexed in Web of Science - in Journal Citation Reports or Scopus or by data provided by internationally recognised bodies such as the European Union. This search, reflection and argumentation have led to participation in scientific topics and virtual dialogue between users on concepts of education and/or gender, scientific evidence from past and present times, experiences, and practises that they are carrying out as professionals, family members or students.

The involvement of the participants has increased their awareness and interest in science, but also in the impact science has on their lives and everyday life. Some of these users point out that they are aware of what is scientifically based and what is not, which helps them to discern in their daily lives, especially those who are education professionals. They also point out that it helps them to overcome prejudices, to know what scientific evidence helps them to improve the lives of people who suffer social inequalities or are victims of aggression.

It is also observed that people with little scientific culture seek out and interact with people who have a high scientific culture, which shows the participants' interest in science in education and in gender. Some of the non-scientist participants indicate that they have participated in scientific activities and contributed their learning on social media and vice versa.

Many of the users of the social media analysed in their comments the information they had before learning about the scientific evidence; an example of this is that some teachers have questioned the concepts of Bourdieu or Ausubel. It is also observed that the users participating in the social media analysis, virtual interactions provide them with new ideas, motivate them to learn more and help them to open their minds as they learn about other ways of doing things with a scientific basis. Practises that help them or will help them in their work or daily life. Thus, participation in these social media has helped users to educate and self-educate themselves in scientific evidence.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Despite the scientific arguments, there are some exclusionary comments based on scientific evidence that do not help to overcome and to know the social relationship beyond statistics and to know the evidence that shows transformative studies. Or commentaries appear which are based on non-scientific bodies and subjective experiences or opinions.

Table 20. Results of the TOPIC b) Citizen awareness of the impact of scientific research.

TOPIC b) Citizen awareness of the impact of scientific research								
	Aim of the enhancing-participation action	Promoting organisation	Level of intervention	Field of intervention	Participants (targeted and real)	Type of participation (i.e., role of participants)	Level of access to scientific evidence	Social Impact
TD*	E1.1: The data are alarming: only 1.9% of the education budget is allocated to inclusive education in Latin America; 4 out of 10 children with disabilities do not participate in compulsory education. And in Spain, only 2.2% of people with disabilities have access to education (regular or special), and most of them are men (MECD, 2017). Considering this, it is necessary to identify those factors that favour academic success.	Public	International; bottom-up	Education	Real	Participant	Medium	No
	E1.1: At the same time, students must know what accommodations they will require in higher education and have access to them (Ju, Zeng, & Landmark, 2017).	Public	International; bottom-up	Education	Real	Participant	Medium	No
	E1.1: Another factor that favours academic success is the interactive groups in special education schools, which have been qualified by the European Union as ESAs (Successful Educational Actions).	Public	International; bottom-up	Education	Real	Participant	Medium	Yes
	E1.2: Evidence indicates that there are students who do not disclose their disability for a variety of reasons.	Public	International; bottom-up	Education	Targeted	Participant	Low	No
	E1.3: It is therefore necessary to avoid segregated education, since this is a major obstacle to the inclusion of children with disabilities in education (Stepaniuk, 2019). That obstacle can be visualised in the barriers that are generated in the interaction of children with disabilities and their classmates. Thus, according to the literature review by Ugalde et al. (2021), the importance of favouring this interaction is pointed out, since it favours the achievement of better learning in the classroom.	Public	International; bottom-up	Education	Targeted	Participant	Low	Yes
	E1.3: In summary, the collaborative work between Occupational Therapists and Teachers, and the avoidance of segregated education are aspects that positively influence the academic success of students with disabilities.	Public	International; bottom-up	Education	Targeted	Participant	Low	No

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

E1.4: This tells us that opportunities can be developed that allow access to inclusive programs and avoid school segregation, since to ensure success in inclusive education it is necessary "the remission of social barriers, starting with interpersonal relationships and the use of appropriate language" (Yupanqui et al, 2016, p. 163).	Public	International; bottom-up	Education	Targeted	Participant	Low	No
E1.7: On the other hand, according to Makoelle and Burmistrova (2020) dual education with special education that is seen as a separate component of education as such, prejudices people who are different. This cannot continue to happen, since education is a right for all, where we should receive quality, accessible and inclusive tools for people with disabilities.	Public	International; bottom-up	Education	Targeted	Participant	Low	No
E1.8: According to a study by Terras, Leggio and Phillips, online classes have helped the academic progress of a number of students with disabilities who participated in their experiment. This may be a good place to start if we want these children to one day be able to catch up with the rest (2015, p.329-340).	Public	International; bottom-up	Education	Targeted	Participant	Low	No
E1.9: ... scientific studies show without a doubt that their school performance improves when they are in school (regular or special), I wonder then, what are we doing? Where is the right to schooling for these people?	Public	International; bottom-up	Education	Targeted	Participant	Low	No
E1.10: In short, work must be done to create the conditions necessary to eliminate the deprivations suffered by many of these students. Because many of these injustices have a significant impact on the lives of these students.	Public	International; bottom-up	Education	Targeted	Participant	Low	No
E1.11: Making classes interactive, in groups rather than sitting one to one, and inclusive with children with and without SEN, creates diversity in the classroom and develops many values such as respect and companionship. This is the environment where young people with disabilities should be.	Public	International; bottom-up	Education	Targeted	Participant	Low	No
E2.16: Oliver, E. and Gatt, S. conducted a study on the subject, analysing the learning outcomes of interactive groups of heterogeneous learners who were guided by adults who accompanied them in their learning.	Public	International; bottom-up	Education	Targeted	Participant	Low	Yes
E2.16: On the other hand, the discipline of neuroscience indicates that one of the factors that positively influences learning is emotions. Learning that involves a dialogue between peers is easier to achieve and longer lasting, because it associates learning with a positive feeling.	Public	International; bottom-up	Education	Targeted	Participant	Low	No
E2.16: I believe that by combining the teacher's explanatory part with a part in which the student participates in dialogue, successful learning and less school failure are more likely to be achieved	Public	International; bottom-up	Education	Targeted	Participant	Low	Yes

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

E3.17: Its creator in 1969 (Althusser) already acknowledged that he was writing on the basis of books he had not read. Bourdieu, its best known representative, for his 1970 book entitled "The Reproduction", abandoned in the 1980s the defense of this model. The analyses with the greatest scientific impact make it clear that quality education is the best (and often the only) way for girls and boys from low socioeconomic levels to escape poverty.	Public	International; bottom-up	Education	Real	Participant	High	No
E1.18: From the scientific evidence I am involved in researching, but also from my own experience, I can affirm that Bourdieu's reproductionist model is surpassed every day from different corners of the world, from different neighbourhoods, from different families, like mine, and from so many educational communities that work hard to offer a quality education, a transformative education like the one my parents wished for me.	Public	International; bottom-up	Education	Real	Participant	High	Yes
E3.15: Now, as a teacher, I have been able to see how theories such as Ausubel's, Bourdieu's or Althusser's have "pulled children to the bottom of the sea" who needed a hand to push them upwards and not downwards. Now I am also aware of the transformative theories that are at the basis of the successful educational performances that are making it possible for students who come from uneducated families to achieve the success that some of us achieve. That is why, as a teacher, I will never again base my practice on reproductionist theories, even if they continue to be promoted at university or in training courses (which are not based on evidence).	Public	International; bottom-up	Education	Real	Participant	Medium	No
E3.21: The other day I was lucky enough to be with Sara at the same Tertulia and the evidence was overwhelming: no to ideas based on discrimination against people.	Public	International; bottom-up	Education	Real	Participant	High	Yes
E3.19. Income gaps are mainly due to the difference in early education investment. Subsidizing early education is the most effective public policy to release income inequality.	Public	International; bottom-up	Education	Real	Participant	Medium	No
E4.22: The role of bystanders against bullying. All members of the group are in agreement on this issue, as we believe that bystanders are an indispensable source to end bullying and all that goes with it.	Public	International; bottom-up	Education	Target	Participant	Medium	Yes
E4.23: Previous researchers have shown that many school-based anti-bullying programmes are effective. A previous meta-analysis (Gaffney, Ttofi & Farrington, 2019) found that intervention programmes are effective in reducing bullying perpetration by approximately 19-20% and bullying victimisation by approximately 15-16%. Gaffney, H., Ttofi, M.M. & Farrington, D.P. (2021). What works in anti-bullying programs? Analysis of effective intervention components. Journal of school Psychology, 85, 37-56.	Public	International; bottom-up	Education	Target	Participant	Low	Yes
E4.24: This paper outlines what bullying is and the devastating impact it can have on the mental health of those involved. It will outline the most common anti-bullying initiatives as well as the current psychological and educational	Public	International; bottom-up	Education	Target	Participant	Low	No

techniques, which could also be used to alleviate distress associated with bullying involvement. We conclude by arguing the need to investigate components relevant to both mindfulness and anti-bullying programmes (e.g., empathy, perspective-taking) as active ingredients for reducing the impact of bullying on mental health.							
E4.25: Therefore, I believe that bystander intervention is essential to stop bullying as long as it does not involve intervening in a bad way but rather by going to an adult who can stop the bullying, as sometimes victims do not defend themselves because they feel alone and sometimes they need someone who can help them or advise them on what to do in these situations.	Public	International; bottom-up	Education	Target	Participant	Low	No
E5.27: Research by Robert Manzano and others has found that when we expect a lot from our students, we treat them differently. We ask them more often, give them more time to respond and let them explain their answers. Therefore, we motivate them more, we increase interactions in quantity, quality and frequency, and with that we increase the results, as students are kept active and awake, the protagonist and author of their own learning.	Public	International; bottom-up	Education	Target	Participant	Low	No
E5.29: I agree with the post. I think that the teacher's expectations can influence an improvement in the student's results, this reminds me of what I studied in education theory about the Pygmalion effect. Low expectations on the part of the teacher attract low results on the part of the students, therefore, high expectations end up motivating the subjects and thus, achieving more positive results.	Public	International; bottom-up	Education	Target	Participant	Low	No
E5.1: Indeed, teacher expectations influence academic success, and this also includes students belonging to ethnic groups - the higher the expectations, the higher the achievement, and the lower the expectations, the lower the achievement. Flanagan, Cormier and Bulut (2020) show this in their research using 140 teacher surveys, even when teachers do not report different behaviour, they report lower expectations for indigenous students.	Public	International; bottom-up	Education	Real	Participant	Medium	No
E5.30: In line with what this article quotes we have decided to refer to this other article which refers to the influence of teachers' perceptions on pupils. It also deals with a large, representative, longitudinal study in the United States. Kellys,S. & Carbonaro,W.(2012).Curriculum tracking and teacher expectations: evidence from discrepant course taking models. Social psychology of education, 15,3, 271-294. http://10.1007/s11218-012-9182-6	Public	International; bottom-up	Education	Target	Participant	Medium	No
E5.33: In my case, these comments were able to make me rethink the decisions I had to make. That is why I agree with the statement that low expectations are associated with lower academic performance, but high expectations are associated with higher academic performance, higher academic achievement. (E5.Teachers expectations influence educational achievement - Sc, P. 6: 1276)	Public	International; bottom-up	Education	Target	Participant	Low	No

	<p>E5.34: I totally agree. If teachers from day one have a passion and love for what they do, they will have very high expectations of their students. Expectations of teachers influence educational performance.</p>	Public	International; bottom-up	Education	Target	Participant	Low	No
	<p>E5.34: For Marques (2006), the teacher functions as a mirror in which students can see their emotions, feelings and values. The teacher must be aware that the way he/she acts towards the student directly affects his/her self-concept and, as a consequence, his/her academic performance.</p>	Public	International; bottom-up	Education	Target	Participant	Low	No
	<p>E5.36: In my view, I believe that this is a very true statement, because whatever the teacher requires of his pupils, taking into account his own expectations, will cause this maximum effort in pupils or not. If a teacher has higher expectations of his pupils, he will seek to give the maximum of them so that they will achieve better academic results, and if that is the case, the results will be lagging behind.</p>	Public	International; bottom-up	Education	Target	Participant	Low	No
	<p>E5.38: From my point of view, it is true that students' academic performance is influenced by teachers' expectations. I will present two situations based on my experience as a student to demonstrate that the scientific evidence in the post is real.</p>	Public	International; bottom-up	Education	Target	Participant	Low	No
	<p>E5.39: I agree with the post. The expectations of teachers towards pupils is a direct influence on them.(...) That is why it is important that if such expectations are created, they are created in a healthy way, with different goals for each pupil, because no one is identical, and for everyone. In this way we can produce a positive effect on all children and thus achieve a positive, motivating, hard-working and creative attitude for the new generations.</p>	Public	International; bottom-up	Education	Target	Participant	Low	No
	<p>G1.152: I usually listen to different public debates that romantic relationships are the root of gender violence. But when I checked the scientific evidence, there is clear evidence that depends on the people that you choose to be involved, if they are violent the relationship will be violent independently if the relationship is a sporadic or long term relationship. And the people that you consider attractive depend on the type of socialization process experienced as it explained in the following article: Gender Violence Among Teenagers: Socialization and Prevention published in the most important international scientific journal on Violence Against Women.</p>	Public	International; bottom-up	Gender	Real	Participant	Hight	Yes
	<p>G1.17: The length of a relationship does not determine whether it will be violent or not. On the contrary, is the partner of choice who will lead to a violent or non-violent relationship. Since girls tend to prefer violent boys for sporadic relationships, and non-violent partners for long-term relationships, it is more likely that they are in a violent casual relationship than in a violent long-term relationship.</p>	Public	International; bottom-up	Gender	Real	Participant	Hight	No

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

	<p>G1.153: In my personal experience, romantic love has in no way been a root of gender violence. I have a very romantic relationship with my girlfriend and after several years together she has never felt involved in a violent relationship according to her.</p> <p>Now, according to the evidence that I know, the root of gender violence are the social interactions that make us desire and choose violent people. To back this assertion I share a peer reviewed paper below.</p>	Public	International; bottom-up	Gender	Real	Participant	Hight	Yes
	<p>G1.154: Romantic relationships are not the root cause of gender-based violence, but they can be decisive in helping to prevent future violent relationships. In my personal experience I had a long and romantic relationship with my first girlfriend, many years later she told me that due to that relationship we had, she has been able to clearly distinguish violet attitudes in boys who have claimed to have a relationship with her</p>	Public	International; bottom-up	Gender	Real	Participant	Hight	Yes
	<p>G1.156: The problem in these relationships is the difficulty in recognising threatening and/or risky situations that can lead to violence, as many of these are normalised and accepted by today's society. Therefore, the problem is not the fact of having relationships, whether sporadic or stable, nor the age of the participants, but the choice of the person or the permissibility of small everyday actions that can lead to violence in the future.</p>	Public	International; bottom-up	Gender	Target	Participant	Low	No
	<p>G2.15: There is evidence of the SOSH that exists in universities and the permissive dynamics installed in them towards this violence that can even make the victims feel guilty for thinking that they are the ones who have caused this situation. These university contexts where this type of violence is permitted make the victims feel isolated by their peers which leaves them even more unprotected. I totally agree that it is urgent to defend those who support the ending of the sexual violence that still persists in universities.</p>	Public	International; bottom-up	Gender	Real	Participant	Medium	Yes
	<p>G3.160: There is robust evidence which shows that pedophilia is not a sexual orientation. In this regard, American Psychological Association has considered it as a mental disorder.</p> <p>Similarly, there is also evidence about the nonexistent significant relation between pedophilia and homosexuality.</p>	Public	International; bottom-up	Gender	Real	Participant	Hight	No
	<p>G3.161: Sexual orientation tells us about the romantic, sexual or affective attraction towards people of the opposite sex or gender, of the sex or gender, or of both sexes or more, in this case we speak of love or simple preference, on the other hand when we speak of pedophilia we see control and violence, we speak of an age-related "preference", therefore we do not speak of love. You can find much more information through the following page where we can find an interesting article that studies pedophilia as a possible disorder.</p>	Public	International; bottom-up	Gender	Target	Participant	low	No

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872395

	<p>G4.12: The idea that children who have been victims of violence and have been exposed to it in their homes will be violent, has become a common belief of many education professionals, and this statement revictimizes these children and increases their suffering trajectories. It is not true that scientific evidence has found a consistent link with the perpetuation of violence.</p>	Public	International; bottom-up	Gender	Real	Participant	High	No
	<p>G4.12: Even the studies that did find some correlation in the 1990s do not provide any causal relationship, what they say is that it could be considered a logical theoretical link between the experience of physical abuse in early life and the later development of aggressive behaviour; they do not claim that it exists, but that this is the approach of some theorists.</p>	Public	International; bottom-up	Gender	Real	Participant	High	No
	<p>G4.14: This is so important for schools, educators and families, because it allows for more optimistic and transformative approaches and interventions. Thank you!</p>	Public	International; bottom-up	Gender	Real	Participant	Medium	No
	<p>G4.58: "Childhood exposure to violence and likelihood of adult perpetration of violence, particularly for boys"; please, if you have found this kind of evidence in some of the article you sent in your message, I would kindly like to ask you to point out which is this evidence and in which articles can be found. I have found correlations, but not causal relationships. I have also found statements about causal relations, but without support of scientific evidence. I was a victim of gender violence and I could transform myself into a survivor thanks to the help of men and women, some of whom had been exposed to violence when they were children. Children with exposure to violence are victims; projecting into them the suspicion that they will become perpetrators is revictimization. Besides, this projection also creates difficulties for the solidarity we need from them to transform ourselves from victims to survivors.</p>	Public	International; bottom-up	Gender	Real	Participant	High	Yes
	<p>G5.158: Bystander Intervention is one of the evidence based interventions that has proven to reduce and prevent violence in all its forms at educational institutions from schools to universities. Its approach focuses on the empowerment of the witnesses to speak up and report the possible violence and harassment situations as an effective action to protect the victims. Now, evidence goes beyond demonstrating the efficacy of the program to prove that Bystander Intervention does not only have immediate effects in the short term but also in the long run.</p>	Public	International; bottom-up	Gender	Real	Participant	High	Yes

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

ED*	<p>G1.157: According to the RAE dictionary, love is an intense feeling of the human being that needs and seeks, that completes us, makes us happy and gives us energy to live together, communicate and create (2020). Therefore, if love kills, if it hurts and if it annuls the previous defined characteristics, it is not love. Love kills when violence, scorn, insults, insults, threats, when they inhibit you, when they manipulate you and when they take over your mental health to empower themselves. Love kills if you don't stop these behaviours, if you don't nip them in the bud. Love is not putting up with it because it's your turn, nor is it putting up with it because the other person is like that, love is valuing each other.</p>	Public	International; bottom-up	Gender	Target	Participant	Low	No
	<p>G4.164: This account is out of date and inaccurate. A series of reviews have found that childhood exposure to domestic and family violence increases the likelihood of adult perpetration of violence, particularly for boys. See here for recent reviews and meta-analyses: https://xyonline.net/books/bibliography/27-violence-and-responses-violence/c-examinations-particular-factors-or-Childhoodexposure</p>	Public	International; bottom-up	Gender	Real	Participant	-	No

*TD = Transformative Dimension; ED= Exclusion Dimension

3.5. Conclusions

This section summarises the main conclusions of the Social Media Analytics and Social Media Communicative Observation

3.5.1. Conclusions of the Social Media Analytics

Main Findings between social networks

- The social networks where citizens have more opportunities to interact with their peers were Facebook and Reddit. For this reason, in these social networks there were more discussions and debates among users or professionals or users asking for help and advice.
- On Facebook, the administrators of the page choose and publish the posts (e.g., press articles and blog entries). On the contrary, on Reddit all users are invited to post and propose a topic for the debate.
- Twitter and Instagram did not stand out for their community discussions. However, Twitter users interacted with other users through retweets and replies to previous messages.

Main Findings between strategies

- No relevant differences were found between the Top-Down and Bottom-Up strategy in any of the categories (aim of the initiative, promoting organization, level of intervention, field of intervention, target audience, role of the target audience or access to scientific evidence). The most significant differences were found across different social networks.
- The selection of hashtags following a twofold strategy (top-down and bottom-up) brought different results.
- Hashtags obtained from the bottom-up strategy were related to specific recent events and news. Whereas hashtags obtained from the top-down strategy were related to general topics and included, not only the voices of citizens but also NGOs, governments, policymakers, companies, experts and associations, among others.

Main Findings about categories

- **Aim of the initiatives:** although the objectives of the initiatives were diverse, a great extent of the initiatives aimed to promote scientific literacy among citizens through diverse formats. In addition, these initiatives included how citizens were aware of the social impact of scientific research in gender and education and used scientific contributions to identify and overcome social problems.

- **Promoting organization:** Reddit was the only social network where all the initiatives were promoted by individual citizens. A common finding across social networks was that, despite the presence of diverse promoting organizations, individual citizens, press and academia were always present in high proportions.
- **Level of intervention:** Globally, most of the messages included initiatives at international level. One of the underlying reasons could be the internationalization of social media.
- **Field of intervention:** The fields of intervention were diverse and not limited to topics related to gender and education. This finding points to the increasing interdisciplinarity of scientific research that includes contributions from all scientific fields.
- **Target audience:** Most of the initiatives did not target specifically any group. However, some of the interventions were addressed to specific social actors, such as teachers and school professionals, children and youth or policymakers.
- **Role of the target audience:** In most of the initiatives, the target audience did not play an active role. However, in those initiatives in which participants were actively engaged, they could join discussions, interact and participate in challenges and in workshops.

Main Findings between dimensions

- In all social networks, citizens tended to share transformative examples of how citizens' benefit from research. The proportion of exclusionary messages ranged from 0 -6.97%.
- Specific results were found on Reddit, where users tended to downvote more exclusionary comments, and Twitter, where exclusionary tweets were less retweeted than transformative tweets.

Main Findings in the use of scientific evidence

- In all the cases except one (Facebook, education), more than half of the messages included the access to some type of scientific evidence (including supposed and certified evidence).
- On Instagram, citizens' use of scientific evidence was mainly through the provision of data or statistics about the cases of bullying or gender-based violence and it was not common to find evidence from articles of journals indexed in JCR or Scopus.
- On Reddit and Twitter, users tended to react differently to the messages, depending on the source provided. Therefore, messages with no evidence obtained the lowest punctuations and retweets, and comments with some type of scientific evidence (including Scopus and JCR, but also official data, statistics and report) the highest.

3.5.2. Conclusions of the Social Media Communicative Observation

TOPIC b) Citizen awareness of the impact of scientific research

- The search in JCR or SCOPUS and data provided by internationally recognized organisations have allowed users to reflect and argue on scientific issues.
- Scientific argumentation has fostered participation and virtual dialogue among users on concepts of education and/or gender, scientific evidence from the past and present, experiences and practises and virtual dialogue between users on concepts of education and/or gender, scientific evidence from the past and present, experiences and practises they are carrying out as professionals, family members or students.
- The involvement of the participants has increased their awareness and interest in science.
- Some of the non-scientist participants indicate that they have participated in scientific activities and contributed their learning on social media and vice versa

4. Focus Groups

4.1 Overview

All partners have worked keeping in mind that a Focus Group (FG) “is a group of individuals selected and assembled by researchers to discuss and comment on, from personal experience, the topic that is the subject of the research” (Powell & Single, 1996, p. 499)⁷.

Focus groups in gender include the selection of different profiles of participants: Women (including vulnerable women) from a women’s group; Members of an LGBTQI group; Women (including Young women) from a women’s group. Focus groups in education include the selection of different profiles of participants: Parents; Teachers; Students.

The section is divided into three parts: **The first one**, methodology of the focus, which explains the main characteristics of the implementation and analysis of FG; **the second section**, which focuses on the results of the FG on gender and education; and **the third and final section**, where we present the conclusions obtained on the “Topic b) Citizen awareness of the impact of scientific research”.

4.2. Methodology: Focus Group

The focus groups conducted by the UOXF, ISCSP-ULISBOA, UNIMIB, UB, UH, and RUG followed the guidelines established in the Focus Group protocol of the project, as well as the individual and collective protection measures based in the country due to the COVID-19 pandemic.

⁷ Powell, R. A., & Single, H. M. (1996). Focus groups. *International journal for quality in health care*, 8(5), 499-504.

4.1.1. Implementation of the Focus groups.

Table 4.1. Distributed of the focus groups among partners of the Consortium:

Gender			Education		
Profile of participants	Partner	C/E	Profile of participants	Partner	C/E
Women (including vulnerable women) from women's group	UOXF	C/E	Parents	UB	C/E
Member of LGBTQI group	ISCSP-ULisboa	C/E	Teacher	UH	C/E
Women (including young women) from a women's group	UNIMIB	C/E	Students	RUG	C/E

All participants have received written and oral information about the project and have signed a consent document, translated into the national language, to participate in the project. The guidelines are set out in terms of format, language and time in Deliverable D9.1H. Procedures and Criteria to Identify and Recruit Research Participants.

The methodological procedure used for each of the population groups studied is detailed below:

4.2.1.1. Gender

- **Women (including vulnerable women) from women's group**

In line with the objective of the ALLINTERACT project to widen and diversify citizens' engagement in science, participants were recruited via the Public and Community Involvement, Engagement and Participation leads at NIHR Oxford Biomedical Research Centre and the NIHR Applied Research Collaboration for Oxford and the Thames Valley with a specific focus on including participants from diverse ethnic groups. One participant required English language translation, which was provided by their family member. Several participants identified themselves as neurodiverse.

Altogether, 33 people expressed interest in participating in FGs. Based on the availability of the majority of the participants, 18 people were invited to participate in two FGs, one participant declined an invitation, and one participant did not attend. As a result, 16 people participated in two FGs.

During recruitment, potential participants were asked if they would be potentially interested in participating 1) in an intervention aimed at raising citizens awareness in order to promote and diversify citizens engagement in science, and 2) in a followed-up focus group. Only those who indicated their potential interest in participating in the intervention were allocated to the Experimental Group. Those who did not indicate their potential interest in participating in the intervention were allocated to the Control group.

In line with the Deliverable D9.1H. Procedures and Criteria to Identify and Recruit Research Participants, all potential participants signed a consent form to participate in the FGs and prior to that had an opportunity to ask researchers questions regarding their potential participation.

The socio-demographic characteristics of the participants and their pseudonyms are detailed in Table 4.2 below.

Table 4.2. Socio-demographic characteristics and pseudonyms of participants, UOXF.

Focus Group number and type	Pseudonym	Age	Race/ethnicity
FG1 (Experimental)	P1	51-60	White (British, Irish, or any other White background)
FG1 (Experimental)	P2	51-60	Mixed (White and Black Caribbean, White and Black African, White and Asian, any other Mixed background)
FG1 (Experimental)	P3	61-70	White (British, Irish, or any other White background)
FG1 (Experimental)	P4	20-30	White (British, Irish, or any other White background)
FG1 (Experimental)	P5	51-60	Black or Black British (Caribbean, African, or any other Black background)
FG1 (Experimental)	P6	20-30	White (British, Irish, or any other White background)
FG1 (Experimental)	P7	51-60	Other
FG1 (Experimental)	P8	61-70	White (British, Irish, or any other White background)
FG1 (Experimental)	P9	70+	Asian or Asian British (Indian, Pakistani, Bangladeshi, any other Asian background)
FG1 (Experimental)	P10	20-30	Asian or Asian British (Indian, Pakistani, Bangladeshi, any other Asian background)

FG 2 (Control)	P11	70+	Asian or Asian British (Indian, Pakistani, Bangladeshi, any other Asian background)
FG 2 (Control)	P12	51-60	White (British, Irish, or any other White background)
FG 2 (Control)	P13	70+	White (British, Irish, or any other White background)
FG 2 (Control)	P14	61-70	White (British, Irish, or any other White background)
FG 2 (Control)	P15	51-60	White (British, Irish, or any other White background)
FG 2 (Control)	P16	20-30	Black or Black British (Caribbean, African, or any other Black background)

- **Member of LGBTQI group**

The Gender Team at University of Lisbon was in charge of conducting two FG sessions, one for an Experimental Group and one for a Control Group. Regarding the Experimental Group, 7 people voluntarily participated in the session, while the Control Group was composed by 8 people.

WP2 followed the recommendation provided by Deliverable D9.1H. Procedures and Criteria to Identify and Recruit Research Participant, based on high standard criteria: a free and voluntary participation and avoidance of any kind of coercion which may have a negative impact on their involvement during the FG. Also, researchers from the WP2 informed the participants that they will not receive any type of reward for their time and presence during the session, as well as the confidentiality on the information analysis and dissemination of results.

Tables 4.3 and 4.4 include the information from participants of the two FG conducted at this stage. This process has followed the guidelines set out in the Deliverable D4.8. Anonymisation/pseudonymisation techniques.

Table 4.3. Pseudonymous participant in Focus Group – Experimental Group conducted by WP2.

Focus Group	Pseudonym	Characteristics	Role
FG1 – EG	P1	Portuguese, 20-29 y.o.	Participant
FG1 – EG	P2	Portuguese, 30-39 y.o.	Participant

FG1 – EG	P3	Portuguese, 30-39 y.o.	Participant
FG1 – EG	P4	Portuguese, 20-29 y.o.	Participant
FG1 – EG	P5	Brazilian, 20-29 y.o., resident in Portugal	Participant
FG1 – EG	P6	Chilean, 40-49 y.o., resident in Portugal	Participant
FG1 – EG	P7	Brazilian, 30-39 y.o, resident in Portugal	Participant
FG1 – EG	F1	WP Member	Facilitator
FG1 – EG	F2	WP Member	Facilitator

Table 4.4. Pseudonymous participant in Focus Group – Control Group conducted by WP2.

Focus Group	Pseudonym	Characteristics	Role
FG1 – CG	P1	Brazilian, 20-29 y.o., resident in Portugal	Participant
FG1 – CG	P2	Portuguese, 20-29 y.o	Participant
FG1 – CG	P3	Brazilian, 20-29 y.o., resident in Portugal	Participant
FG1 – CG	P4	Portuguese, 20-29 y.o.	Participant
FG1 – CG	P5	Brazilian, 20-29 y.o., resident in Portugal	Participant
FG1 – CG	P6	Argentinean-Portuguese, 20-29 y.o.	Participant
FG1 – CG	P7	Portuguese, 30-39 y.o.	Participant
FG1 – CG	P8	Portuguese, 30-39 y.o.	Participant
FG1 – CG	F1	WP Member	Facilitator
FG1 – CG	F2	WP Member	Facilitator

Topics addressed in both sessions were taken from the list included in Allinteract Protocol, according to the objectives in which WP2 has been working throughout the project: b) Citizen awareness of the impact of scientific research.

Both facilitators welcomed participants and explained the stage of the project in which FG are being conducted. Facilitator 1 (F1) had the role of carrying the conversation along the session and invited participants to express their opinions regarding the topics. F1 encouraged an egalitarian intervention from all participants and promoted an open dialogue.

According to the Focus Group Protocol, FG sessions were conducted in the country's official language (Portuguese), in order to assure comprehension and interaction among participants. However, according to the instructions provided by the Central Team, opinions from participants included in this report were translated into English. The records of the FG, as well as the full transcripts of both

sessions, have been stored by the CIEG-ISCSP, who collected the data in the dispositive approved by our ethical board.

- **Women (including young women) from a women's group**

The UNIMIB team had to carry out two focus groups involving “women/including young women” that are part of a national association dealing with gender/feminist issues.

After a careful analysis of the Italian associative landscape, the UNIMIB team selected “Casa delle donne”, because of its long history of feminist activism (more than 30 years), in particular on gender violence. It is a *“social promotional association that looks without discrimination at the aspirations and needs of women of all ages and sexual orientations, who (...) live in our city (Milan). The association is linked to other women's associations (...) that share our goals to fight gender-based violence, promote talents and enhance women's knowledge”*⁸.

UNIMIB team selected this association for two main reasons: 1) this association involves women not only of various ages, but also with different characteristics in terms of nationality, education, socio-economic status, job *etc.*; 2) the association is based in different Italian cities; therefore, it was possible to guarantee a geographical mix.

Members of the UNIMIB team illustrated the project's goals, the methodology, the research expectations to the main stakeholders of this association. They indicated the criteria for correctly selecting our participants: they searched people with different ages, with a particular attention to young women (20-29 years old), as indicated by the Protocol; people with different education, so preferably not all people with a degree or a master's degree (coherently with the spirit of the project that wants to engage social disadvantage people or people that historically don't participate to science). The team excluded people with STEM education and academics for the same reasons.

UNIMIB team contacted “Casa delle donne di Milano”, “Casa delle donne di Pisa” and, finally, “Casa delle donne di Parma”, which are located in the North and in the Center of Italy. They contacted “Casa delle donne di Roma” too, but no participants were selected from there, because the participants' characteristics didn't match with UNIMIB team's criteria. They selected these cities because they are representative of the Italian small/medium/large cities, and they have a different but relevant history in terms of feminist activism.

A very long and meticulous work has been done both to find people interested in the participation in our project and to compose balanced groups.

⁸ The quotation is taken from: <https://www.casadonnemilano.it/chi-siamo/>

“Casa delle donne” is present in different Italian cities.

At the end of the selection's process, the list was composed by 17 people; UNIMIB team composed the final groups with 10 people: 5 for the first FG (the experimental group) and 5 for the second FG (the control one). They excluded 5 people because of their characteristics; the other 2 didn't accept to participate for personal reasons. In the following table (Table 4.5) there is a summary of all the women's characteristics.

Table 4.5. Characteristics of the participants in the focus groups.

Focus Group (n. 1/n. 2)	Participant's initial name	Characteristics (nationality, age, education)	Association (geographical area)	Group (experimental/control)
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	L.	Italian; 20-29 years; graduate	Casa delle donne Pisa	EG
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	I	Italian; 20-29 years; high school diploma	Casa delle donne Parma	EG
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	T.	Italian; 20-29 years; graduate	Casa delle donne Pisa	EG
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	E.	Italian, but with foreign parents; 40-50 years; 8 th grade diploma	Casa delle donne Milano	EG
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	P.	Italian; 60-70 years; high school diploma	Casa delle donne Milano	EG
Focus Group 2 (FG2)	G.	Italian; 20-29 years; high school diploma;	Casa delle donne Parma	CG
Focus Group 2 (FG2)	M.	Italian; 20-29 years; graduate	Casa delle donne Parma	CG
Focus Group 2 (FG2)	C.	Foreign origin; 40-50 years; graduate	Casa delle donne Milano	CG
Focus Group 2 (FG2)	S.	Italian, 50-60 years old; graduate	Casa delle donne Pisa	CG
Focus Group 2 (FG2)	A.	Italian; 50-50 years; graduate	Casa delle donne Pisa	CG

Selected participants have received written and oral information about the project. UNIMIB team informed that participants did not receive any type of reward, and the participation did not suppose a cost for them. Researchers communicated that all participants will be informed about the evolution of the ALLINTERACT project. All the participants signed an informed consent document. All participants' informed consent documents are uploaded in a specific folder on the ALLINTERACT workspace.

In line with the national directives in terms of collective safety, the UNIMIB team carried out the FGs online through the WEBEX platform. We conducted the two focus groups in Italian in the following dates:

- Focus Group 1: On Tuesday, the 12th October 2021 from 10.00 to 11.30 a.m. (without a pause); since they didn't finish to discuss all the stimuli, another brief meeting on Wednesday the 20th October from 1.30 to 2.00 p.m was scheduled.
- Focus Group 2: on Thursday, the 14th October 2021 from 6.30 to 8.00 p.m. (without pause).

The UNIMIB team conducted all the FGs in Italian to guarantee the full participation of people. In each of the FGs there were two researchers (Prof. Carmen Leccardi and Dr. Zenia Simonella) who played the role of facilitators of the discussion. The researchers presented themselves. One of the two researchers briefly illustrated: a) the goals of the FGs; b) the possibility for each participant to freely expresses her opinion without fear; c) the ethical principles related to the protection of all FGs' participants in terms of privacy/anonymity. The other researcher conducted the FGs proposing the selected pool of stimuli (on gender topic) that were reported in the Protocol Document. Every researcher was in charge of involving all the participants, in particular those who participated less to the discussion.

All focus groups and interviews have been audio/video-recorded and literally transcribed. These recordings are uploaded in a specific folder on the ALLINTERACT workspace.

4.2.1.2. Education

- **Parents**

At the University of Barcelona, the team conducted one the one hand four in-depth interviews with family members of vulnerable groups who have taken part in Scientific Dialogue Gatherings and two FG with families (15 mothers exactly, and 3 teachers accompanying them). These families did not used to participate in scientific activities. Thus, it will be these families that we will carry out the implementation of the scientific activities carried out by the project.

Here below are the pseudonyms and roles of the participants in the FG and interviews so far. This process has followed the guidelines set out in the Deliverable D4.8. Anonymisation/pseudonymisation techniques.

Table 4.6. Pseudonymous participant in focus groups and interviews undertaken by UB.

Focus Group/ Interview	Pseudonym	Rol
Interview 1 (I)	Maria	Family
Interview 2(I)	Sofia	Family
Interview 3 (I)	Cristina	Family
Interview 4(I)	Francisca	Family

Focus Group 3 (FG3)	Elena	Family
Focus Group 3 (FG3)	Laura	Family
Focus Group 3 (FG3)	Angela	Family
Focus Group 3 (FG3)	Laia	Family
Focus Group 3 (FG3)	Nerea	Family
Focus Group 3 (FG3)	Estefania	Family
Focus Group 3 (FG3)	Carolina	Family
Focus Group 3 (FG3)	Matilde	Family
Focus Group 3 (FG3)	Carmen	Teacher
Focus Group 3 (FG3)	Lucia	Teacher
Focus Group 4 (FG4)	Hayat	Family
Focus Group 4 (FG4)	Mariana	Family
Focus Group 4 (FG4)	Mariya	Family
Focus Group 4 (FG4)	Silvia	Family
Focus Group 4 (FG4)	Esther	Family
Focus Group 4 (FG4)	Victoria	Family
Focus Group 4 (FG4)	Josefa	Family
Focus Group 4 (FG4)	Diana	Teacher

Regarding this O2 report, FG and interviews followed section 2) Exploration of the initiatives to foster

societal actors' awareness of the connection between the solutions they appreciate and the scientific research leading to them (O2).

One of the interviewers had the role of facilitator of the focus groups and was in charge of giving turns to participants who want to intervene in the discussion. The facilitator prioritized those participants who intervened less in order to ensure egalitarian participation. The facilitator also encouraged everyone to join the conversation and ensured an egalitarian dialogue among participants, in which participants intervened to provide validity claims instead of power claims.

- **Teachers**

In this topic the UH team has implemented two focus groups held with educators/teachers. Likewise, the Barcelona team conducted two FG with teachers (17 people) who have taken part in Scientific Dialogue Gatherings.

Here below are the pseudonyms and roles of the participants in the FG with teachers.

Table 4.7. Pseudonymous participant in focus groups undertaken by UB.

Focus Group/ Interview	Pseudonym	Rol
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	Antonia	Teacher
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	Dolores	Teacher
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	Sara	Teacher
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	Antonio	Teacher
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	Javier	Teacher
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	Miguel	Teacher
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	Elena	Teacher
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	Raquel	Teacher
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	Alejandro	Teacher
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	Lucia	Teacher
Focus Group 2 (FG2)	Juan	Teacher
Focus Group 2 (FG2)	Mateo	Teacher
Focus Group 2 (FG2)	Alba	Teacher
Focus Group 2 (FG2)	Mónica	Teacher
Focus Group 2 (FG2)	Laura	Teacher
Focus Group 2 (FG2)	Jesús	Teacher

Focus Group 2 (FG2)	Emilio	Teacher
---------------------	--------	---------

- **Students**

At the University of Groningen, the team conducted two FG with undergraduate students (12 people). All the people participated voluntarily throughout the process, and researchers followed the recommendation provided by Deliverable D9.1H. Procedures and Criteria to Identify and Recruit Research Participant, which is based on high standard criteria: all conversations between researchers and potential participants about the possibility of participating in the research occurred in a place where the participants felt comfortable and safe to avoid any possible coercion and to ensure that the decision was taken with absolute freedom. The team informed that participants did not receive any type of reward, and the participation did not suppose a cost for the participants. Researchers have also explained the possible risks and benefits of participating. The recruitment process was never conducted by someone who may have an unduly influence on potential participants. The language employed ensured comprehension for the participant.

Table 4.8. Pseudonymous participant in focus groups and interviews undertaken by RUG.

Focus Group/ Interview	Pseudonym	Rol
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	Lucas	Student
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	Julia	Student
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	Yara	Student
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	Kostas	Student
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	Kelly	Student
Focus Group 1 (FG1)	Liam	Student
Focus Group 2 (FG2)	Mary	Student
Focus Group 2 (FG2)	Mateo	Student
Focus Group 2 (FG2)	Sophie	Student
Focus Group 2 (FG2)	Eleni	Student
Focus Group 2 (FG2)	Anika	Student
Focus Group 2 (FG2)	Emma	Student

One of the interviewers had the role of facilitator of the focus groups and was in charge of giving turns to participants who want to intervene in the discussion. The facilitator prioritized those participants who intervened less in order to ensure egalitarian participation. The facilitator also encouraged everyone to join the conversation and ensure an egalitarian dialogue among participants, in which participants intervene to provide validity claims instead of power claims.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

4.2.2. Data collection

All focus groups and interviews were audio-recorded and literally transcribed, substituting all names for pseudonyms for scientific use for later analysis. Later on, we translated into English. The records of the FG were stored by each partner who collected the data in the dispositive approved by our ethical board on their institutions.

4.2.3. Analysis

The Allinteract team has followed the dimensions and initial categories emerged from project topics (a-e), each partner being in charge of the same topic as in the literature review:

Table 4.9. Definitions of dimensions and categories for Focus Groups.

Dimensions	Transformative dimension includes those messages that evidence what facilitates the social/political/scientific impact mentioned.
	Exclusionary dimension includes those messages that show obstacles hindering the achievement of the targeted social/political/scientific impact.
Category	b) Citizen awareness of the impact of scientific research

4.3. Results of the Focus Groups: TOPIC b) How citizens benefit from scientific research

4.3.1. Results on Gender

The results obtained by gender are presented below:

- **Women (including vulnerable women) from women's group**

Respondents described a wide range of experiences with regard to their awareness of the impact of scientific research. Many participants described becoming aware of the impact of scientific research via social media. Participants of younger ages appeared to rely on social media more often than participants of older ages. Importantly, the Covid-19 pandemic has led to the use of Zoom and Teams by community activists for connecting communities with scientists internationally.

Respondents also spoke of becoming aware of the impact of scientific research through newspapers, radio, TV, and science festivals.

Respondents discussed the need to acknowledge that different generations get their information in different ways and agreed about the importance of social media and other digital information. Respondents acknowledged that for many citizens there could be a barrier to accessing scientific research digitally. Language appeared to be another important barrier. This included both people whose first language wasn't English and people who did not understand scientific language. One respondent suggested that getting rid of the term "science" could help engage citizens in science. One respondent acknowledged a lack of interest in scientific research among the younger generation.

Table 4.10. Results of the TOPIC b) Citizen awareness of the impact of scientific research

TOPIC b) Citizen awareness of the impact of scientific research								
	<i>Aim of the awareness-raising initiative</i>	<i>Promoting organization</i>	<i>Level of intervention</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Audience</i>	<i>Role of the targeted audience</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
TD*	<p>"I would definitely say that my age group, so I'm technically a millennial, so I definitely get a lot of my information from social media, but also from the daily news. And actually, that sort of presents some issues, doesn't it? Because usually those forms of communication are snapshots. They don't give you the context or the detail. And I suppose you'd need to be have some level of curiosity or interest in science to really delve deeper. Want to go into sort of scientific journals, which I suppose would give you a wider understanding, a little bit more information into whatever the subject matter is? So yeah, that's how I sort of digest the information usually really quick headline news type things, but I wonder whether that presents issues." P16 FG2</p>	Self-organization	Local//Bottom-up	Scientific research in general	Citizens interested in science	Participant	Low	Yes
	<p>"I am usually made aware of scientific research via social media, Twitter, Facebook, YouTube... A lot of it gets tweeted into my timeline audits from organizations like Cancer Research UK that I follow on Facebook because it works on algorithms. Once you've read one bit of research, it kindly feeds you lots of other bits of research, so I find about some really bizarre things that I would never normally go looking for. ... I don't normally like the algorithms on social media, but I quite like how it's introducing me to lots of things I wouldn't normally I wouldn't normally know about. And then when it comes up, I will click into it. And I don't read the scientific journals usually, but I do read the articles, you know, kind of summarizing them." P15 FG2</p>	Self-organization	Local//Bottom-up	Health, Scientific research in general	Citizens interested in science	Participant	Low	Yes

<p>“reading the national press or London newspapers in the sections they often have about science... you know, general articles about all sorts of aspects of science. And I just, you know, tear them out and keep them.” P12 FG2</p>	Self-organization	Local//Bottom-up	Scientific research general	in interested in science	Participant	Low	Yes
<p>“And also with science to do with the natural world and history and so on, I might attend in societies and talks and learn about it that way. I'm not really on social media” P12 FG2</p>	Self-organization	National /Bottom-up	Scientific research general	in interested in science	Participant	Medium	Yes
<p>“I go to Twitter and Facebook and all that bit. But what Zoom and Teams have done in the last two years is connected as worldwide. So for our community, we have got a lot of scientists... in our community. So what we are doing is every week we have something about health, environment, space, whatever. So worldwide we are connecting with each other and seeing. So it's not just British research. It is worldwide research we are looking at.” P11 FG2</p>	Self-organization	Local/Bottom-up	Scientific research general	in interested in science	Participant	Medium	Yes
<p>“A documentary is a really big way that I learn about research -- Netflix, BBC iPlayer. I'll just go into the category and just scroll until I think, well, that sounds quite interesting. That's something I... don't know anything about, and I'll just watch it. And then, you know, you just kind of learn random things. I love it. And then that becomes a topic of conversation with, you know, friends and family.” P15 FG2</p>	Self-organization	Local//Bottom-up	Scientific research general	in interested in science	Participant	Low	Yes
<p>“Science festivals, Cheltenham Science Festival I've been to and Oxford Science Festival.” P1 FG1</p>	Science Festivals	National /Bottom-up	Scientific research general	in interested in science	Participant	Medium	Yes

	<p>"I access sort a lot of things through social media. So, for example, on YouTube and other sort of video platforms, that's where I might hear about research." P4 FG1</p>	Self-organization	Local//Bottom-up	Scientific research general	in interested in science	Participant	Low	Yes
	<p>"I tend to look up things that I'm interested in and I Google things and I go to the source. But also Radio4 does a lot of programs. I think it's called the science hour and all in the mind where they tend to update you on the latest research." P7 FG1</p>	Self-organization	Local//Bottom-up	Scientific research general	in interested in science	Participant	Low	Yes
ED*	<p>"It's possible that some people may not speak English. As well as someone who does and can understand when they're reading about something in a newspaper listening to a documentary, I know myself that my mother doesn't understand the English language as well because she comes from another country. So when we watch something that is a serious subject on TV or if I'm reading a newspaper on my iPad to her, I have to explain, you know, in far simpler language." P14 FG2</p>							
	<p>"I was going to say again thinking about the younger members of my family. I think a lack of interest in research is a barrier because a lot of them, unless it would personally affect them, they're just not interested." P15 FG2</p>							
	<p>"So to me, it is [important to] get rid of the word science because science seems to be up there where you are supposed to be very intelligent and think about science... So I wonder whether we should be thinking about how do we engage people who are trying to engage the citizens? But the citizens think that if you talk about science, you need to have big brains for that and a whole lot of us have only small brains." P11 FG2</p>							
	<p>"I think we need to acknowledge that different generations get their information in different ways. ...P5</p>							

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

<p>and I were talking about information in newspapers and the 35 year old put their hand up and said the last paper he bought was when the London Olympics were on, which was about ten years earlier. And so there's no one way of getting to everybody." P3 FG1</p>	
<p>"...these [digital] platforms are great for all of us as long as we are fluent in reading and writing and speaking English. Secondly. There are good platforms if you are digital competent, because nowadays most things come in the form of emails and attachments, not hard copies in the post. And then third thing is how they are not suitable for others like my mom. The first thing is they don't even know that they exist." P9 FG1</p>	

*TD = Transformative Dimension; ED= Exclusion Dimension

- **Member of LGBTQI group**

Participants of the Control Group agreed on the importance of science and scientific research and their benefits for society. In their words, they not only help people to move forward in terms of specific researches related to health or engineering, for example, but also because due to science and scientific research, societies can evolve towards new paradigms and ways of living and thinking. They are aware of the impact in different aspects of their daily lives. However, they stressed the fact that science and scientific research need to find their own way to better engage with population in general. This is seen as one of the main obstacles when it comes to make science and research more accessible to people. In addition, there is a consensus in terms of how is this impact measured in today's societies. It was said that most of the times researches in fields like Social Sciences, which do not 'produce' something tangible, compared to engineering for example, may seem not too impactful for societies. Therefore, it is important to leverage the impact that scientific research has in people's daily life in order to generate a stronger engagement with it and with science in general.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Table 4.11. Results of the member of LGBTIQI group on TOPIC b) Citizen awareness of the impact of scientific research. Control Group.

TOPIC b) Citizen awareness of the impact of scientific research							
	<i>Aim of the awareness-raising initiative</i>	<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private / public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local/national/international; bottom-up/top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Audience (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Role of the targeted audience</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>
<p>Case 1: It is commonly believed that the academic sector does not generate enough value for society. However, others maintain that academic research generates benefits in many ways. Applying a new version of the 'technological innovation system' framework to nanotechnology in Sweden, researchers found a rich pattern of impact, including substantial commercialisation. However, the effect of academic activities</p> <p>*TD</p>	<p>P1: "(...) For me it is a little absurd to think that the academic sector does not generate value for society, because I think that everything that we have to advance in many things goes through the academic sector, through research, right? So, I think that sometimes there is a challenge to penetrate society. So, if we think from social studies to engineering studies, these things, after being researched and structured, need to penetrate societies, culture, production, I think this is a challenge, right? We could even think, study new ways of living the city, but then it has to be accepted by the city, implemented, right? And it needs to penetrate the political layer, and I think this is a great challenge. And the same thing with technology, for example. Sustainable technologies, car technologies... have been around for a long time and had to penetrate the automotive lobby and the oil industry in order to get there and become mainstream. So I think the problem is not what is generating value, but how are we taking advantage of it, right?"</p>	Public	National / Top-Down	Nanotechnology	<p>Targeted: Academics, scientific researchers</p> <p>Real: Academics, scientific researchers</p>	To evaluate the impact of R&D activities and specifically the NTIS (New Technological Innovation System)	High

	<p>P1: "(...) I think that the very access to Science, to research, it is already transformative and this has an impact on the non-market society. So many times, you understand a new subject or see some research that has been done can transform your mind and transform the way you relate to society. And I think we can use Political Science as an example, right? This is not a product, but it has a very strong transformative power, even if it is the transformation of the people it touches, right? It is when you understand that and start to think in a different way, and suddenly you are transformed, you will see society in a different way. And this is always super valuable. It is not a marketable product, but I think that more and more we are seeing how much it is not a product, it doesn't exist, it is nothing. It's not given value, I think."</p>						
	<p>P4: "(...) it's a bit of steering both sides: to make the case that science is needed not only for military or health purposes, it has many other applications, some more utilitarian than others, and also that science and academia can do a better job in communicating how those investments translate into concrete applications."</p>						
	<p>P4: "(...) all knowledge is great knowledge and I think it's great to ground the curiosity to ask and question a little bit further. It's normal that when there's money involved people go on a purely utilitarian principle and I think it makes sense to prioritize some of those things, but knowledge doesn't have to be just that and science is perfectly valid for just to answer the most basic whys of all, like why does it rain, are we alone in the universe. All these questions are valid and are worthy of it. And I think Science can extol that, I think we all benefit from that."</p>						

	<p>P3: "(...) how can I talk about projects and projects of human areas, biological, exact, whatever, I think they all have their importance at a certain point because, of course, it is important to develop a source of wind energy, it is very important, man. Let's do it. We need that for a sustainable world, but it is also important for me to go to a community in the Lato neighborhood and talk to the residents there, help them to have a strengthened local economy, help them to know how to make a house, because they don't have access, you know? So that's also important."</p>						
	<p>P3: "(...) the research process is also very important, right? Because there you will see, you accept the possibilities, impossibilities and that will open your eyes sometimes to other things, in a holistic view of the fact. Researching one thing, in the middle of the way I even discover another. Then I will work with this other thing too, I will later research this other thing too, because it appeared in the middle of my research. And with that you will be able to improve people's lives."</p>						
	<p>P3: "(...) I think this is a cool thing, you know? From Science and research, this power to always do more, this power to always help people and to be able to... I don't know, to change as a society. We, if we compare what we were, I don't know, two thousand years ago and what we are today, totally different realities, you know? And in the last years, the last 100 years, if we stop and think about it, we can see, we can, I don't know, see a change... not in the last 100 years, but I will speak after the industrial revolution, mainly, we can see the leap that society took, from what it had until then, until that point, and what it has been building since then. And this was with Science, with Technology, with the development of new energies, new things, everything else... the economic changes. So, I think that the road is long, there is still a lot to be done, and Science, without a doubt, is in the middle of it, and we have to use this to make things happen, right? Both in the exact area, as well as biological, as well as human, everything that we can do."</p>						

* ED	<p>P1: "(...) Sometimes academia is a very closed bubble and sometimes it is too much research for research's sake, right? And there are a thousand projects that are just for the researcher's portfolio and to keep the research going and get the name out there..."</p>	
	<p>P4: "(...) The exogenous factors are the usual ones: political interest, funds, what is the interest of the moment for that, for example. Historically we know that Science was the target of investment when it served military purposes, for example, the race to the Moon, between the United States and the Soviet Union, as a proof of strength, somehow, as a proof of capability from a meritocratic point of view. Billions of dollars were invested for that. When the focus is not so militarized perhaps, science falls to a more secondary plane or a more health-oriented plane, for example."</p>	
	<p>P4: "(...) I think that those who are in academia, have to try to break the bubble that is created and the way that often conferences are for the same people who always go there and already know the topics and have their perspectives on things, and invest more and more in communicating science to everyone and everyone who is outside of science and who might be a little bit captured for a little bit of that almost juvenile curiosity, because everyone is curious to a certain extent."</p>	

	<p>P6: "(...) not speaking of my opinion, but of the general opinion that I have heard, that the academic sector is elitist. That is, also because of the language issue, because of the issue for example they do debates that are often repetitive or that effectively not everybody can attend or see, but I think that nowadays also this is rebounding especially with the teaching part."</p>	
	<p>P6: "(...) everything that is knowledge ends up being a little bit limited, so to speak, by the policies of each country, giving for example, someone wants to do a... wants to get a degree, right? There are countries where, for example, you don't have to pay for an academic degree, which means that you can easily access higher education. There are others like for example America you have to be working like until a certain age to be able to have that degree and get to knowledge."</p>	

*TD = Transformative Dimension; ED= Exclusion Dimension

Participants of the Experimental Group (EG) expressed their opinions in different areas. Firstly, it was discussed the way science and scientific research is measured by society and the impact of its commodification. This is an aspect that needs to be addressed, especially in fields like Social Sciences, which does not produce something tangible or for trade, but is really important to understand different processes throughout history. Another aspect that emerged during the dialogue among participants was the fact that society must be aware of who uses science and for what purposes – that is, the importance of debating ethical issues that, most of the time, are hidden by what seems to be the concern with social and political impact of science mostly measured by a utilitarian understanding of science. This was mainly linked to some historic periods of humanity in where science was used for atrocities against different groups of people. Also, the importance of creating a stronger relationship between academia and society through activities where students can get in touch with situations in real life. This, in exchange, will create a positive way to put into practice what is studied and learnt at universities, for example. In the same sense, participants recognized the importance of universities and researchers and their contribution to society. However, they stressed the fact that it is highly important to disseminate research results and scientific information to population at a large scale, providing truthful and verified content, fighting against fake news, which was identified as one of the main problems in today's information era.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Communication of Science, in this sense, represents a challenge to be addressed. Finally, opinions pointed to the responsibility of institutions like governments and academia to create a stronger bond between science and population in general.

Table 4.12. Results of the member of LGBTQI group on TOPIC b) Citizen awareness of the impact of scientific research. Experimental group.

TOPIC b) Citizen awareness of the impact of scientific research							
		<i>Promoting organization (i.e. aim; private / public)</i>	<i>Level of intervention (i.e. local/national/international; bottom-up/top-down)</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Audience (targeted and real)</i>	<i>Role of the targeted audience</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>
<p>Case 1: It is commonly believed that the academic sector does not generate enough value for society. However, others maintain that academic research generates benefits in many ways. Applying a new version of the 'technological innovation system' framework to nanotechnology in Sweden, researchers found a rich pattern of impact, including substantial 'commercialisation'. However, the effect of academic</p>	<p>*TD</p>	<p>Public</p>	<p>National / Top-Down</p>	<p>Nanotechnology</p>	<p>Targeted: Academics, scientific researchers Real: Academics, scientific researchers</p>	<p>To evaluate the impact of R&D activities and specifically the NTIS (New Technological Innovation System)</p>	<p>High</p>
<p>P1: "(...) if we had a government, as it was the case in Sweden, with the whole Covid issue, which was that disaster that we know it was, they used science as a basis, which is that issue of group immunity that was used, which was achieved if people got sick. It went wrong, but it was based on certain scientific evidence that could have been refuted later, but that part of the research was probably left unreviewed or reviewed and they thought it was worth the risk.</p>							

	<p>P1: "(...) Of course I think that it can make a very big contribution to society, but it always depends, I think, on who is in charge of that society, right? Because we also know that scientific production has already been used for the greatest atrocities in the history of humanity. I think that there is always that potential, it always depends on who is going to use it, doesn't it, a little bit... but I think so, I think that Science has that potential. Now, I think it's very limited by several things: this issue they're talking about here of commercialization is, for me, one of the main ones, and here in Portugal, in addition to this, in addition to the process of publishing Science, we also have an academy that is also very aging and this, in the short term, is going to generate major problems because then there are no open competitions, there are entire departments closing or being left without teachers and researchers, so there's a whole... and that of course, yes, the academy unfortunately doesn't depend only on it, right?"</p>						
	<p>P7: "(...) one of the bases of higher education in Brazil is that research and extension are taught. And since I entered the university, I have always participated in extension projects, which is the possibility that the university gives a... establishes a contact, has to work together with the community, as if it were a way of giving back to the university of Brazil, which is the real public university, the possibility of me having a contact with the community to give back what I receive as a student in a higher education course, isn't it? So, I remember going through several courses, several Extension projects where we realized how much what we were doing in areas that were not very well regarded, in the sense of financial issues, that will generate profit or whatever, merchandise, in short, but we realized how much it could reach people and do this process of us trying to promote some area of society that needed, for example, a contribution... I think of a help and some social issue there.</p>						

	<p>P7: "(...) I believe very much that the academy... I think there comes a moment... that is why I think Extension is so beautiful, which is the possibility for you to leave that universe that you are within a specific course. And you go, in fact, to a place where ideas can emerge, where you can think strategies, because in fact you get out of a logic "I am studying about a specific theme, I am studying a specific reality", but I have no way to have contact with it. And if I don't have contact, it is difficult to stay only in that very theoretical question of if I don't go to a more practical question (...) So I believe very much in this possibility in the academy. And of us being able to create community within that process."</p>						
	<p>P4: "(...) universities have a lot of work, that researchers do as well, but it's also part of the role of someone who studies to share that training not only in academic circles, but also to the general population, to all kinds of people."</p>						
	<p>P5: "(...) If you think about it, Internet covers more people and I think that these are two possibilities that make Science has this capacity to be understood and absorbed by people that are not inside the academy. And I think that's the point. It's not that it is useful how and that it can be useful to society, how does it reach or not reach... how do we communicate Science so that it is perceptible, so that it is reliable and all these other issues. I think it's more in that sense."</p>						

	<p>P2: "(...) Science needs to reach the common citizen more and more, only then for Science to reach the common citizen, obviously we have to use the platforms and see the possibilities, Instagram, Facebook, etcetera, etcetera, etcetera, however there are two points for me that are essential, which are: the language, how it reaches (people), it has to be a language accessible to the common citizen. Not everyone has a college degree or... and maybe that's the danger, the danger of spreading fake news, as we all know, is to a less literate public, if you can put it that way. Maybe you have to know how to reach them, in what way... what discourse to use, and taking what P1 said almost at the beginning, which was that the... the academy, the pages of these social networks directly linked to the academy, should be verified."</p>						
	<p>P6: "(...) people's approach to Science has many responsibilities: governmental responsibilities, media responsibilities, responsibilities of ourselves (...)"</p>						
	<p>P6: "(...) It's like the whole society, whether it's government, academia, and citizenship in general, how do we manage to make this connection so that Science is more accessible to everybody, that the research it has is not more important than those researches that generate more money for companies or for governments or for big economic groups, and that researches that help the community directly like... I don't know, vegetable gardens or sustainable energy, etcetera, etcetera, could have the opportunity to reach more with economic support for societies in general."</p>						

	<p>P3: "(...) ideally accessible to everybody, with everybody's understanding. I think the best way for that to reach everybody and to inform. And obviously the ideal would be to be verified. It might be a little bit difficult, but I think ideally it would be verified and then be heard more as well."</p>						
	<p>* ED P1: "(...) "I think this is a particularly difficult problem for the Humanities and Social Sciences (...) this part of commercialization and the part of being useful to society in a quantifiable way, is very much turned to the sciences, to exact sciences, and less to Social Sciences and less to Humanities (...) I think that can be a very big challenge for academia, the whole market part, isn't it?, because we already know also that publishing, the whole publishing part is also very, it's all very much behind paywalls, which makes it difficult to access information, etcetera. "</p>						

*TD = Transformative Dimension; ED= Exclusion Dimension

- **Women (including young women) from a women’s group**

The analysis shows that participants have a different degree of citizen’s awareness about the impact of scientific research.

Most of them declare to carry out communication and awareness activities, especially in their social circle and within the network of “Casa delle donne”. They participate in public discussion, sharing and discussing scientific results – related to gender issues – investigating the topics.

These participants are aware of the importance of the scientific research, so they use it to criticize, sometimes to demolish social stereotypes, and, accordingly to their points of view, to reestablish “the truth” (for instance, the 8th March is interpreted erroneously as a party: in particular, it is considered as an occasion to offer flowers to women in Italy the “mimosa” — and, for women, an occasion to stay with other women; it is not considered a day of feminist struggle). But this is not the experience of all the participants to the FGs: some of them sustain that they are “ordinary people”, that they don’t know, or they don’t investigate the scientific topics because of the distance between science and their daily life. In other words, they

recognize the importance of scientific research for people (for instance, the importance of medical science), but without a real or a deep awareness, because of the lack of social inclusion of these people to the scientific enterprise.

At the same time, FGs participants underline the obstacles to the generation of citizen awareness: one of the obstacles is linked to the superficiality with which people approach the scientific information, combined with the flow of information that generates confusion and apathy.

Table 4.13. Results of the Women (including young women) from a women's group on TOPIC b) Citizen awareness of the impact of scientific research

TOPIC b) Citizen awareness of the impact of scientific research								
	<i>Aim of the awareness-raising initiative</i>	<i>Promoting organization</i>	<i>Level of intervention</i>	<i>Field of intervention</i>	<i>Audience</i>	<i>Role of the targeted audience</i>	<i>Level of access to scientific evidence</i>	<i>Social Impact</i>
*TD	I follow the social campaigns related to feminism, or those that have to do with my work as a historian. I have always taken a critical approach, that is, looking at them through the lens of the researcher. So what I enjoyed was finding errors in some campaigns (e.g. March 8 is usually considered a party and not a day of struggle), or to criticize the distorted history of gender violence. The ones I supported had an impact on the people around me. (M., FG_2). (M., FG_2).	Individual	Local/bottom-up	Gender violence	Citizens interested in gender issue	Participant	High	Yes
	I participate to "Casa delle donne" ... I support the initiatives or others' campaigns and perhaps I am less inclined to start something or to analyze deeply the phenomenon (C., FG_2).	Individual	Local/bottom-up	Gender violence	Citizens interested in gender issue	Participant	Medium-Low	Yes

<p>I don't look for the source. I don't use often social media. I did some campaigns, but I don't know if they can be linked to the scientific field because they were more audio-visual. For example. With "Casa delle donne", we did a photographic campaign for November 25th. In the end, we used images to render concepts. (G., FG_2)</p>	Individual	Local/bottom-up	Gender violence	Citizens interested in gender issue	Participant	Low	Yes
<p>Most of my social activity is this: I don't share information about my personal life. If I read interesting articles, I re-share them, without commenting on them. (...) If I find something interesting that can stimulate conversation among people, friends, family, I share it.... I was part of a group of girls ... with whom we spread information about gender ... before we were called "Glimpses of gender" ... during the university we organized collective meetings in free classrooms but then, due to Covid, we moved to the social media space... so, yes, I use scientific papers, I use articles on gender culture, gender violence and I spread them (L., FG_1)</p>	Individual/Group	Local/bottom up	Gender violence	Citizens interested in gender issue	Participant	Low	Yes
<p>I talk with other people about various articles. Then, as E. said, at the "Casa delle Donne" we organize numerous meetings, even with those of "Nonunadimeno". We select sources and we read articles on gender/gender-based violence. (P., FG_1)</p>	Public	Top-down	Gender violence	Citizens interested in gender issue	Participant	High	Yes
<p>I had shared an article on autism. But I'm not going to check the sources. On the basis of my feeling, I share ... I am an ordinary person; I have no specific skills. Yes, I read articles on climate change, I am in favor of science... But I haven't really investigated scientific topics (E., FG_1).</p>	Individual	Local/bottom-up	Autism	Personal network	Participant	Low	Not evident

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

	<p>In 1999, I had a sarcoma ... I have been under treatment and thanks to the doctors ... I still do follow up... I am an ordinary person. I don't know anything about science and research. (...) Thanks to them, I am alive today. If they hadn't made progress in research, I wouldn't have been here. There was another time when I shared an article from the Cancer Institute and there many people spoke to me because they knew about my past. So I talked about my experience (E., FG_1).</p>	Individual	Local/bottom-up	Cancer	Personal network	Participant	Low	Yes
ED*	<p>The approach is superficial, you read the titles of the campaigns and then you decide. Unless there is a very succinct but effective summary of the content of the publication to which I am referring, it is often difficult to open a debate because it is limited to a very superficial reading. (A., FG_2)</p> <p>M: There is a low-level of awareness of the theme of violence; people don't look at the sources and don't reflect about what it means to join a campaign and to have a civil and political commitment in general. (M., FG_2).</p>							

*TD= Transformative Dimension; ED= Exclusion Dimension

4.3.2. Results on Education

The results obtained by education are presented below:

- **Parents**

People who have taken part in the Scientific Dialogic Gatherings explain that, after taking part in this educational activity, they have increased their awareness and also their immediate environment to the impact of scientific research. They also show how their interest in science has improved. In all the interviews, people say that their interest in science has increased, in some cases they have become more informed through external sources and have even attended science outreach events. Participation has led them to delve more deeply into scientific topics and understand words that they did not understand before, such as quantum science.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Participation in the focus groups enables both parents and teachers to distinguish between practices that are not scientifically based and those that are. In the case of family members, for example, a teacher explains how a mother of a gifted child informs the mothers that she leaves her child at school because the school has a scientific basis. Likewise, another mother at the end of the course points out that they have learnt one thing from science, which is that violence appears in the first stages of life, which is why she thinks it is important to put an end to aggressions from the age of 0. The family member's knowledge of science increases when they participate in the discussion and offers them argumentative tools that they did not discuss and offers them argumentative tools that they did not have before, all of which helps the family members to develop self-confidence.

The reading of the articles as well as the interactions established through the focus groups, have led teachers involved to engage with science on education and gender in their schools. One of the interviewed teachers specifically said that "It has helped me to be able to transfer scientific evidence to my place of work at the centre, to analyse what we were doing and what we were not doing in terms of scientific evidence and to improve this linkage of applying scientific evidence in education. So it has a direct impact on me". An impact that teachers say has improved them as professionals and has caused scientific arguments and knowledge to permeate people in their working and social environment. Raquel, a teacher, put it like this "I would also like to add the impact that this cycle of gatherings has had on me personally, the satisfaction that this cycle of discussions has had on me as a professional, which is that I feel much more satisfied in terms of professional ethics and now I am developing this scientific culture among my colleagues and families".

This educational practice has been one of the scientific training activities, especially on education and gender issues for both families and teachers that have been carried out before, during and after the confinement caused by the pandemic.

Family members who were not used to participating in science activities beforehand reported that: museums about science make them aware of the impact science can have on life and that having personal health problems make them aware of what science can help them. As for the difficulties they show is the lack of science competitions, especially for their children to participate in.

Table 4.14. Results of the parents on TOPIC b) Citizen awareness of the impact of scientific research.

TOPIC b) Citizen awareness of the impact of scientific research								
<i>Aim of the awareness-raising initiative</i>	<i>Promoting</i>	<i>Level</i>	<i>of Field</i>	<i>of Audience</i>	<i>Role of the</i>	<i>Level of Social</i>		

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

		organization	intervention	intervention		targeted audience	access to scientific evidence	Impact
TD*	I Francisca: I think there is an interest. When we talk about climate change and all this, we are more agile to understand because everyone is involved. We know, and they tell us things, researchers who have worked here and there. I think more people than me don't understand enough either.	Self-organization	Local//Bottom-up	Adult Education	Family	Participant	Low	Yes
	I Cristina: On Wednesdays, one thing they do at the Clínic are talks, they also do them online, and they talk about illnesses.	Public	Local/Top-down	Adult Education	Family	Participant	Low	Yes
	FG1. Lucia: I explain that we have been doing the training and it is all very well planned, so we are obedient and we are doing it despite the lockdown. We have said: we don't have to stop. To do it step by step without stopping, when we got the confirmation, we said: Oops!, it's time to start pedagogical discussions with the teachers, and that's when we started with the zero violence from zero years old and with the construction of the norm. This year we couldn't see each other either, so we said we would do it with the parents. Next year we want to do it with the lunchroom monitors group because, generally, 70% of the conflicts appear in the lunchroom, little by little.	Self-organization	National /Bottom-up	Teacher Training	Teacher	Participant	Medium	Yes
	FG1: Marta: Well, it has helped me to be able to transfer scientific evidence to my place of work at the centre, to analyse what we were doing and what we were not doing in terms of scientific evidence and to improve this linkage of applying scientific evidence in education. So it has a direct impact on me. You really know in the centre what you are doing that is evidenced, and we still have things that are being done that are not evidenced. At least we have marked out the path that we need to follow to give the best education to students.	Self-organization	National /Bottom-up	Teacher Training	Teacher	Participant	Medium	Yes
	FG1 Dolores: In the article that we shared by Ausubel, a lot of people, who participate in the Dialogic Gathering, are trying to transform and improve their educational practice. And I was amazed that I had believed that I was improving the educational practice, following the principles of quite a lot of prior knowledge. And it was amazing	Self-organization	National /Bottom-up	Teacher Training	Teacher	Organizer /Participant	Medium	Yes

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

	<p>to see that no, that you are doing with the best of intentions, the opposite of what the scientific evidence says.</p>						
	<p>FG1 Lucia: At school, the <i>AMPA (Parent Association)</i> has already started the scientific discussion groups. And from there, from the topics that came up in the discussion groups, we have science discussions with articles from the cycles. One topic that was of great concern and with the paper we read about how technology affects children's attention span, we were able to discuss how to deal with this situation at home.</p>	Self-organization	National /Bottom-up	Teacher Training	Teacher	Participant	Medium Yes
	<p>FG1 Dolores: Besides, there was a lot of sharing in this Dialogic Gathering, like, "oh, what happened?" and How did I know now? And this article was very clear that we had to do the opposite and that we had to change the practices that were happening in that.</p>	Self-organization	National /Bottom-up	Teacher Training	Teacher	Organizer /Participant	Medium Yes
	<p>FG1 Miguel: I think it has helped both those of us who participated and the centres where we work to bring ideas that we could not have, that we could only transfer from the evidence. I am thinking about many of the articles, and there are many things. Still, one of the things that happened, for example in our case is that after Gathering on Ausubel , we held an Ausubel Gatherings between two cloisters online from the same population, who were interested in sharing this type of evidence. I think that this has happened in many cases.</p>	Self-organization	National /Bottom-up	Teacher Training	Teacher	Organizer /Participant	Medium Yes
	<p>FG1 Raquel: about the impact on professional life in addition to what you say comes from the impact on the student body that is making it brutal and on the families. I am also very impressed by how this has transformed our staff room. And not just in the staff room of the high school where we work, but I dare say in the professional culture in Asturias. You often hear people talking about whether this is evidence-based. The discussions are extended, as Miguel also said, beyond the discussions we used to have. That is, at the national level, within the Institute or within Asturias. In our seminar, topics or ideas dealt with in the discussion groups came out, which is a good thing because it has an important impact. I would also like to add the impact that this cycle of gatherings has had on me personally, the satisfaction that this cycle of discussions has had on me as a professional, which is that I feel much more satisfied in terms of professional ethics and now I am developing this scientific culture among my colleagues and families.</p>	Self-organization	National /Bottom-up	Teacher Training	Teacher	Teacher	Medium Yes

<p>FG1 Raquel: On social networks, we collected precious evidence of a mother who says on her personal Facebook page how she felt. She is a mother of a child with high abilities and she told other mothers how she felt and she answered other mothers who asked her, "Why do you go to that institute? , why don't you take your child to a more elite school?" and she explained that it was an institute where they did things based on evidence. It's very satisfying to see people standing in line at the grocery store talking about evidence in education.</p>	Self-organization	National /Bottom-up	Teacher Training	Teacher	Teacher	Medium	Yes
<p>FG1 Lucía: I wanted to share with you that we have started with the dialogic discussions with parents this year, and we started with articles on "zero violence from zero years old". At that time, as we were still in the consolidation training, they came to explain the dialogic model of conflicts to us. The first question they asked us was when there was more violence in children. We all said that it was in the upper cycle, but a scientific study shows more violence in the youngest children. We were talking about it. At the end of the course, a mother who had not been in training said: we have learned a great thing, a piece of evidence! It is what scientists tell you. For example, one of the things is that young children generate more violence, and that is where we have to go down, and that is very clear to us.</p>	Self-organization	National /Bottom-up	Teacher Training	Teacher	Teacher	Medium	Yes
<p>FG1 Lucía: You have an obvious argument and from here we can already talk and we are already at another level where we are all learning and we can start to build the house and of course more in the creation of the standard and so on. We have to move on to the evidence in order to take firm steps to achieve something strong together.</p>		National /Bottom-up	Teacher Training	Teacher	Teacher	Medium	Yes
<p>FG1 Alejandro: The language of possibility is noticeable if we have already created that environment in which we talk to build. Concerning this colleague involved in thousands of things, she works a lot, but in things that are not directly related to evidence. So this colleague in a School Council said: I believe that the Educational Success Actions have a lot to do with this. Suddenly another teacher and another mother reinforced this opinion and told us from their point of view. They saw that these successful educational actions are closely related to these good results. So the language of possibility and celebration extends even beyond where you are.</p>	Self-organization	National /Bottom-up	Teacher Training	Teacher	Teacher	Medium	Yes
<p>I Raquel: To involve citizens in science, I am finding that we have to let them benefit from the first moment or allow ourselves to benefit from science's benefits. Because if we get families and neighbours to come to our schools, it</p>	Self-organization	National /Bottom-up	Teacher Training	Teacher	Teacher	Medium	Yes

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

	<p>is because from day one, they already benefit from having participated, and there is no greater hook than the truth. Once you see that something works, you have no competition. Science offers benefits from the first moment. That is what makes successful educational actions attractive, all of them: dialogic discussions, interactive groups,... that work, is that they are science and that is what makes citizens interested in it.</p>							
	<p>FG2 Jesús: The pedagogical Gatherings usually have a very big impact on the teaching staff, it is not an obvious thing. In some cases we have shared faculty meetings in different commissions in areas, perhaps more academic and organizational of the school, and there are always topics that raise debates.</p>	Self-organization	National /Bottom-up	Teacher Training	Teacher	Teacher	Medium	Yes
	<p>FG2 Jesús: More and more pedagogical gatherings are taking place in different areas of the school. When everyone is obliged to read that article and arrive at that meeting, that discussion group with the text already read and you start to interact. I have the feeling that you reach an almost emotional confluence in which everyone is very comfortable, the dialogue is very fluid, and normally in most cases, everyone feels identified with the text and agrees, it's like thanks to the reading, and I don't know if the format of the gathering, it helps things to come out and people agree in most cases, like a change of attitude or atmosphere. Without a doubt, it's very positive. Every time we try to include the talks, we go wherever we can. So I think the impact it has on the teaching staff is potent.</p>	Self-organization	National /Bottom-up	Teacher Training	Teacher	Teacher	Medium	Yes
	<p>FG2 Monica: The families are secure and confident, as they have many tools, and they put forward their arguments. When we have had discussions with them, we see that the families also defend with confidence that what we are doing is really what is transforming and what is helping. For example, I talk to the children a lot, we have worked a lot on coexistence, and they are very confident. Even other school contacts, when they go out to the park or different contexts, defend and assure that what is being done is backed up by science.</p>	Self-organization	National /Bottom-up	Teacher Training	Teacher	Teacher	Medium	Yes
	<p>FG2 Monica: A mother who went to her daughter's new school and saw that they weren't implementing anything similar to a conflict resolution model. The mother got involved in the AMPA (Parent Association) to transform the school a little bit and be able to transfer what she saw we were doing in our school to the secondary school and generate a little bit of influence to open up a little bit.</p>	Self-organization	National /Bottom-up	Teacher Training	Teacher	Organizer /Participant	Medium	Yes

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

<p>FG2 Emilio: At my son's school, we created a space for coexistence related to the dialogic model. In this space for families, where we read articles that concern us, a mum who is a local police officer is the person who deals with issues of coexistence and bullying prevention within the local police force. It's very cool how when she plans an intervention or is called to intervene in a centre or talk about these issues, she asks the group and extracts a bit of everything that we read and everything we build up. And based on this, she does her training or plans her interventions.</p>	Self-organization	National /Bottom-up	Teacher Training	Teacher	Organizer /Participant	High	Yes
<p>FG2 Alba: In a video forum we watched a film about science and from this film I later passed on to the children. The families of the school asked me why this film and not another one.</p>	Self-organization	National /Bottom-up	Teacher Training	Teacher	Organizer /Participant	Medium	Yes
<p>FG1: Dolores: Actually, there is a complete transformation in the roles, and there are people retired, mothers or teachers or volunteers from others from other origins, who have been extremely important both in action and in the operation of the cycle and after the launch of our Asturias AEBE seminar and the successful educational actions.</p>	Self-organization	National /Bottom-up	Teacher Training	Teacher	Organizer /Participant	Medium	Yes
<p>FG1 Rosa: An impact that I have valued and that has been in our school, obtained from the cycle of gatherings and specifically from the articles "The open doors" and that of "Mapping", is how it made us more aware of the important thing: that nobody misses us, that we are pending. See that everyone is learning, that everyone has a healthy life in every way.</p>	Self-organization	National /Bottom-up	Teacher Training	Teacher	Participant	Medium	Yes
<p>FG4 Esther: CosmoCaixa It's an easy way to get to science and they even make it easy for them (the children) to discover, for example, the clock, magnetism, etc. Well, they see that and it is an easy way to get to science.</p>	Family Association	Local	Family training	Family	Participant	medium	Yes
<p>FG4 Victoria: I think they should do something similar to the Museum of Arts and Sciences in Valencia. I have been with my big one in the Museum and it is brutal. My son was all the time with his eyes open.</p>	Family Association	Local	Family training	Family	Participant	medium	Yes

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

	<p>FG4 Esther: I am in a community of moms, because my son has a problem. We talk and look at different ways to solve the problem. Moms say: look, this doctor has posted such and such a thing. Of course I participate, because I read it, I study it and I go to my child's family doctor and I say: look, this is what this is. Is this good for me or is this not good for me? Of course, it is something of yours that makes me involve you.</p>	Family Association	Local	Family training	Family	Participant	medium	Yes
	<p>FG3 Elena: We also have many families in the school who are fighting against childhood cancer. During the year we were collaborating with the Family Association and it was very touching because several families had learned a lot and they passed it onto the other families. It was very emotional and at the same time we understood many things about rare diseases and diseases such as cancer or leukemia.</p>	Family Association	Local	Family training	Family	Participant	low	Yes
ED*	<p>FG4 Silvia: More contests on science are needed. (The person proposes an increase in the it easier for people around them to participate)</p>	Family Association	Local	Family training	Family	Participant	medium	No

*TD = Transformative Dimension; ED= Exclusion Dimension

- **Teachers**

The teachers interviewed in the focus groups carried out by the University of Helsinki on the topic b) Citizen awareness of the impact of scientific research. Regarding the control group, the information collected points to the fact that is a hard question. How do we put in public domain as teachers? Many people do not believe in science. And many do not understand the scientific method. In this sense, it was said that much will depend on people's belief in science. The example of illicit drugs and pregnancy is a good example. Would it pass the ethics committee and if it did, should we share all the information with the public? Does it have a negative impact and if so, how this is translated to mothers? Another good example raised by the participants was the Sputnik. It is partly about the science behind it but also political for whether it is approved by the EMEA.

In general terms, it was stated that showing the social impact of science is important. Everyone has an opinion. However, this may not help in encouraging more participation.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

In the case of the experimental group, two main areas were discussed. Firstly, regarding benefits of examples, such as on climate change, it was said that we need to raise the issue of impact in the debate with the public. However, the public is not interested in all the impacts or will even understand them. In this sense, KPIs are not really understood by the public or even academics. We need to find impact measures that are appropriate. On the other hand, Education Finland and Business Finland might use the idea of impacts but not relevant for the public but perhaps the business community. Teachers expressed that we seem to be obsessed with global rankings so it is possible to look at impact more objectively. For the public we need them to be more organic and less mechanic. That is the problem with impacts. And secondly, regarding the use of scientific evidence in debates, information collected points to specific questions, such as: What impacts are relevant for the public? It is not just profit but the impact of teaching and education goes far beyond simply money. What is valued in terms of evidence?

- **Students**

The focus groups of the students have allowed us to find out that as a transformative dimension, it was easier for the participants to identify how citizens benefit from research in everyday life and especially from medical science. Some of the main topics addressed during the focus group included: citizens are aware of improvements for daily life, research is important for society to move forwards, taking the opinion of citizens into account is important, research is needed as evidence/source for statements, and research is interesting, intrinsic motivation.

However, it was also discussed that there are some issues that were categorized as an exclusionary dimension. In this sense, participants had difficulty to identify impact from scientific research in education. Especially the participants of the second focus group were very resistant to acknowledge the impact shown by the scientific evidence provided by the moderator and assistant moderator. They were mostly sceptical towards scientific research in education, questioning who is benefit from that and pointing out that it does not reach public schools. Other opinions heard during the focus group included: Citizens don't realize that there are actual people behind research; most inventions are so normal, that citizens don't realize that research has preceded it; science has a bad image, it is too far away from society and citizens think it is too hard for them to understand and therefore is not interesting; scientific research is not reaching the citizens, because they are not using the right platform of medium; science is just for their own benefits. The media is too biased, so you don't get a good idea of scientific outcomes; education is not taking into account a lot of things regarding to science and presents only the outcomes; awareness depends on your country, current life state and social economical background, and research is not interesting; some subjects are not interesting.

Table 4.16. Results of the students on TOPIC b) Citizen awareness of the impact of scientific research.

TOPIC b) Citizen awareness of the impact of scientific research							
	Aim of the awareness raising initiative	Promoting organization	Level of intervention	Field of intervention	Audience (targeted and real)	Level of access to scientific evidence	Social impact
*TD	Kostas: Yes, so, yes, I think we need the research in everyday life because if you take for example the smallest thing a bottle of water, let's say, they do many research of what kind of ingredients, what kind of filters they will use [...] so, yes, I think it's very, very important because with that we can make improvements.	public	local/topdown	society	citizens	high	yes
	Yara: Yes, I think what I started thinking about was the [dutch word] we have it in the Netherlands and as a researcher I do believe that research is important for citizens and that it can improve our lives.	public	international/bottom-up	science	scientists	low	no
	Lucas: Yes, I think research is the base for societies to move forward. Cause I think if they do no research, it kind of stops. And I think it's also important for like countries and like the societies within the countries to move forward, because if for example would stop doing research now, we would just like stay the way it is right now. (...) I think it's important for the society in near future, but more important for the society if you look, I don't know, in 20 years from now. So, I think it's like the base for society to move forward.	public	international/topdown	society	citizens	medium	yes
	Julia: Yes, I agree especially on the part where he said that its so important for society to move forward (...) So I think that it's really important.	public	international/topdown	society	citizens	medium	yes
	Kelly: I think that what I am taking from this session to process in the next days or time period, is how important citizens are in contributing and engaging in science.	public	international/bottom-up	society	citizens	medium	yes

Yara: I agree with Kelly that it's interesting to think about it. And I have never really thought about engaging people in science as something to do but I think it's really important that we do that more often.	public	international/bottom-up	society	citizens	medium	yes
Lucas: I think the thing I am taking from most is that research is something that you can think okay its happening they found this and this, but I never thought that okay there are people involved and that I myself just by contributing in a study or a research can like help people or like help the society to move forward. So, like the importance of, hm, even though it might be sometimes inconvenient, you don't always get something out of it, to see like the bigger picture of participating in the study and to see like others can help on the long term.	public	international/ bottom-up	society	citizens	medium	yes
Yara: Yes, that's me. I just thought about my mom because she was sending me all these videos about the vaccinations and that you might get infertile when you get one and she was like "are you sure you want to do this? " And was really towards my mom and like "okay, I know that you saw this but where is your evidence? You know, these are just people claiming this and this. If I just... I don't believe that its true without any scientific evidence. So, that's when I kind of asked her if she had validated her source.	private	local/ bottom-up	family	family	high	yes
Lucas: Yeah, I think it's fake news and also like the importance of seeing if someone refers to an article to research like to see and have an idea of how research must look like, cause if you do a study of 5 persons and you find out something that happens to all of these persons, like obviously research has found out. So, I think it's also very important to distinguish between the quality of research and to like have an eye on research if it's appropriate or if it's just there... ?	public	national/ topdown	society	citizens	high	yes
Emma: And the reason why I participate is? Well, because I would like to...to help the research, I think it's an interesting subject and I wanted to contribute to the research.	private	local/ bottom-up	students	students	medium	no
Sophie: And I do part I do participate in the study because I thought it will [not clear] to the opinions of others and to share my own opinion about topics.	private	local/ bottom-up	students	students	medium	no

	Mateo: And I'm participating in this study because first of all, I like to talk, I like to speak [laughs]. And in this topic, in this topic, science education, science in general, politics, these kind of things, I love to discuss about this, this kind of stuff. So, for the for this reason, I am participating. And of course, I want to help you. So.	private	local/ bottom-up	students	students	medium	no
	Anika: And why I take part of this investigation research is because I think it's really important that people get to know more about these subjects and why it's important to that every layer of the society takes part in this kind of stuff.	private	local/ bottom-up	students	students	medium	no
	Eleni: And so, the reason that I'm here, first of all, say, like, I like the methodological approach. So, I want to learn more about focus groups and how focus groups work. And on the one hand is this, on the other hand, it's okay to talk a little bit about science and discuss things with other people. And, yes, that's why I'm here.	private	local/ bottom-up	students	students	medium	no
	Emma: Yeah. So I'm an example of it awareness in daily life. So I had a family member who had breast cancer, and then she went to the hospital. And then she went for a second opinion to another hospital. And there was a new treatment. This was also in investigation. And well partially because of that new treatments that she decided to try. See, recovered. So that really increased my awareness of scientific research in health, healthcare.	private	local/ bottom-up	family	family	high	no
	Sophie: Yes, well, I use a sheet for example, for my lifestyle and what I eat every day and so I try not to eat as much sugar. It's not always easy, of course, because I love chocolate. But I really try to have a healthy lifestyle, because science says that a healthy lifestyle is better.	private	local/ bottom-up	student	student	high	no
*ED	Kelly: Yes, well, regarding this I thought about something while you were talking. Judging from my experience for example before attending this premaster, I never actually took some time to think who is doing the research. I mean, I knew that somebody out there, I don't know, companies, governments, does the research. But I never actually made the connection. Maybe I was always very busy or bothered by other things, more important, I don't know. (...) One year ago I was also not aware about the whole procedure of the PhDs,	public	national/ /topdown	students	students	medium	yes

	the research conducting at the universities, how they help with the scientific research, people, society and evolution [...] So, I don't think everybody is completely aware, not at the same degree about how research is conducted and by who [...] I don't think everybody recognizes how for example this solution now exists, for example like the ones we mentioned before about the covid, about the vaccines, about the water. I think that everybody knows that there is, somebody behind it, but I don't think people analyze the steps and the procedure.						
	Kelly: I think depending where people live, maybe the country or depending on the stage they are in their life or depending on the educational background, I think some people are aware and others are not so much aware.	public	international/bottom-up	society.	citizens	medium	yes
	Julia: Yes. Well, I totally agree with what was said just now because from my experience what I heard a lot before I went to university was that everyone go to university, that you're not doing anything, you're just reading and writing and that is not beneficial for society because I still sometimes get it when I am back home. Like they say like oh why would you go to university why would you do that? You're not benefiting anyone, so I don't think that a lot of people are mindful that everything that is around them stems from some scientific evidence and that that is the reason why everything is so good for us now.	public	national/ /topdown	students	students	medium	yes
	Yara: Yes, I also agree with what they said, and I think that especially in the news and the newspapers sometimes they just say "oh, research finds..." and that's all they say about the research and then they go immediately to the results so maybe also make people understand more what research is and how research is conducted. I think that would help maybe for the awareness that is actually the job that people do, its not just some magic that generates random results.	public	national/top down	society.	citizens	medium	yes
	Julia: Yes, I would like to add that one of the things why people are also unaware of it is because for a lot of people and I know that because of my environment. They think "oh, its university, there are a lot of smart people, and I don't want to like get into scientific knowledge because I don't understand it, it's too hard for me. They are all scientists, so I don't have to do anything with it because I won't understand anyway".	public	national/bottom up	society.	citizens	medium	yes

	<p>Julia: It's like a really big threshold for them to even think about "oh, let me read a research paper or let me think about that" because I know from that experience that people are a little bit too afraid, or they see that the threshold is too high to even consider that they have something to do with it themselves in a daily life. So, I think that is one of the things why people are not aware of it, and they really don't feel like getting into that subject at all.</p>	public	national/bottom up	society.	citizens	low	yes
	<p>Mateo: I don't want to be negative in this regard. But, I really think that science, scientific research is not reaching the citizens. Why I tell, why I tell this? Because, honestly, I think we are right now in a moment in which we, we believe what WE [emphasis] want to believe. I mean, if there is something that it's, it's not, I don't like it, It's more, it's a, it's more likely that I don't believe it. So, I think right now science is not getting is not, It's not. Yeah, it's getting to reach normal people. Besides, I think science is not in, for example, in, in apps for young people are on in these types of things. So, it's difficult to reach young people if you are not using in their media, the correct media. So, I think there are several factors that are getting the things more difficult for science to reach people.</p>	public	national/ top down	students	students	low	no
	<p>Sophie: Yeah, well, I think that we are very biased. From the science, I think that there is a lot of good science. There's also a lot of bad science because, for example, publication by though a lot of research that is done, we never read. And I think like the media is really biased because they only publish what they want, what is good in their opinion. And there is also a lot researchers, there are only done to research because it's for their own benefits. And it's foreign and regions to earn money have to get money for their own... ah..profit. And I think with us, like a pure researcher, and that really wants to find a true, it's always good, and we can all benefit. And we can all benefit from it. (...) Well, I want to give an example. We, I had, I had college a from X a few years ago. And she told a story about your [not clear]. And there was leaking a PowerPoint from him where he did, he did research on a medicine, I guess it was X that is a medicine for children who are psychotic. And he, and he said in his PowerPoint, that he will show which ratio for the study that was already done. So he was really biased. And I read more examples for that. Sometimes, like in Big Pharma, there's a lot of there is done a lot of research in benefit before that's and for that medicine, that it's much better than it really does.</p>	private	local/topdown)	students	students	low,	no

	<p>Mateo: Yeah. In this regard, in education, I think there is a big problem regarding to, to the scientific, in the scientific view. I mean, at least in Spain, what we receive in, for example, in primary education or in secondary education, we only memorize the big ideas of science, how to explain the things we only memorize. But we don't take into account the other part of science, for example, how science works in order to get these big ideas to explain to explain the our reality. So, in my opinion, at least in Spain, education is not taking into account a lot of things regarding to science. And for this reason, the students don't understand a lot of things that they, they all day, all of this happening a in our in our life. So more or less, I think I explained. (...) Now, when, obviously they take, they take something, but if you present them an exam, in which you only have to repeat a part of a text, you are going to do only need to memorize, and unfortunately, this is what happens a lot of times in science education in primary. So, if you if you, if you encourage them to memorize, they are going they are going to do is to do this. So...</p>	private	national/topdown	teachers	teachers	low	yes
	<p>Sophie: Another thing is that if we, if we have the awareness of it, so because of we see all these benefits every day, a lot of people don't realize them don't realize that they exist. So this is how they're relevant problem to take into account.</p>	public	national/topdown)	society	citizens	high	yes
	<p>Sophie: But I don't see really that it is doing that for a lot of people. Because in Holland, we say it's, it's a far from my bed show. Really, because for example, when I talk with my parents, or my grandparents about science, they really don't understand what I mean. And so that's really not interesting for a lot of people.</p>	public	national/ bottom-up	society.	citizens	low	yes
	<p>Emma: Well, I think that only for high educated people, they are interested in science. And for a lot of, like, middle or low educated people,maybe that they are interested.</p>	public	local/topdown	society.	citizens	medium	yes
	<p>Emma: But they don't really understand what it's saying and how research is done. So it's, so I think that it's too difficult for them.</p>	public	national/ bottom-up	society.	citizens	low	yes
	<p>Mary: Yeah. I would like to say that, of course we have benefits from science in our daily life. For example, I don't know if you realize, but in this pandemic era,</p>	public	national/ bottom-up	society.	citizens	high	yes

	we use it a lot of times. I think this is not related to medicine, it's other kind of science. But I think the problem is that one thing is that we benefit from science. Another thing is that we have the awareness of it, so because of we see all these benefits every day, a lot of people don't realize that they exist. So this is a relevant problem to take into account.						
	Sophie: Yeah, but because we all see these benefits in our daily life. So we don't realize that they exist, because they exist from our beginning in the morning.	public	national/ bottom-up	society.	citizens	high	yes
	Emma: Yes. She asked something about the time that we are going through, like the pandemic I assume. And I just think that as a citizen, it is important to always maintain the critical view. Also, on media, because there's a lot of like XX says, bias and framing. And also, when you look at medical science, I think as a citizen, do you benefit a lot, because, for example, surgery, and medicine, but in my opinion, I think it's sometimes forgotten that there there is, for example, in this time, there is also an underlying pandemic, because a lot of people do not have a healthy lifestyle. But well, in the media, I don't hear a lot about this subject to improve healthy foods. For example, because for Big Pharma, with with medicine and vaccines don't doesn't have benefits from that kind of news in media, they have a lot of interests in purchasing of medicine and vaccines. So. So my point is always remain a critical view on science, for example, medical science, and what the media tells you, you can do research yourself.	public	national/ top down	society.	citizens	low	yes
	Anika: And with other subjects, I'm not really interested or I don't care about that subject as much as other subjects. So then it's like, yeah, okay. Not really bothered by this. And sometimes I really hope to learn new things and to get more information. And when doing it, it's a bit of a disappointment, so my hopes were too high. And then I'm, like, led down. So that can be frustrating at times as well.	private	local/bottom-up	students	students	low	no
	Sophie: And I really want to say something about what Mateo said and I said it before but what I read in a standard media like the NOS it's only like a lot of good things about vaccination, but when I read like other media you also read like more critical things about vaccination. So and for that, I really think that a lot of people really think that there is a lot of good research but yeah, what I	public	national/topdown	society	citizens	high	yes

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

	wanted to say is that I think it's really difficult for people to stay critical about research.						
	Sophie: Well, I think that only for high educated people, they are interested in science. And for a lot of, like, middle, low educated people, it's, maybe they are interested, but they don't really understand what it's saying and how research is done. So it's, so I think that it's too difficult for them.	public	international/top down	society	citizens	low	yes

*TD = Transformative Dimension; ED= Exclusion Dimension

4.4. Conclusions of the Focus Groups: TOPIC b) Citizen awareness of the impact of scientific research

Detailed findings by domain, gender and education are shown below.

4.4.1. Conclusions on Gender

The main conclusions out of the focus groups on Gender establish that there are different experiences and degrees of knowledge when it comes to the awareness of the impact of scientific research.

Science and scientific research are perceived as ways societies can evolve towards new paradigms and ways of living and thinking. In general terms, there is a recognition about the importance of scientific research for people in fields such as medicine science. However, there are still signs of lack of awareness of its impact, mainly because science is still observed from a distance, since there is still a lack of social inclusion of regular people in the field. It is important, though, to be aware of who uses science the purposes behind it. This came up as a reflection in one of the LGBTI Groups (Experimental), in particular when looking to some historic periods of society, in which science was used as a tool to exterminate people.

Although the term “science” may not be well received by younger generations, which could have an impact in the way they engage with it, scientific research is perceived as a key element to re-configure some social beliefs, like what it really means the commemoration of Women’s International Day, for example. Thanks to the dissemination of scientific results, people can actually understand what this day means and, as a consequence, change their mind.

Another conclusion is the fact that the impact of science and scientific research is still measured by an economic impact. This needs to be addressed, as there are other fields, like Social Sciences, which create knowledge and have an impact in people’s lives, but the outcomes are difficult to be quantified.

Another key aspect is the role social media are playing (or may play) when it comes to the dissemination of the impact of scientific research. Women, for instance, declared that they rely more on social media compared to people from older ages. This, as a consequence, can be identified as a challenge to address, since older generations do not have the same access or digital alphabetization to use ‘non-traditional’ media. Connected to this, LGBTI Group stressed the fact that it is key to disseminate research and scientific information and results at a large scale, which in turn will help to stop fake news. In this sense, the publication of verified content is key.

Although not at the same level of importance, TV, radio and newspapers are still channels of communication that help people to get in touch with science and also to become aware of the impact of scientific research. In terms of initiatives, science festivals are also an effective way to engage people.

It is important to create a stronger bond between academia and society through activities where students can get apply what they learn to solve daily problems. There is an important recognition of the role of universities and researchers in today's society.

Finally, the pandemic opened an important space for people to get in touch with more science in general or scientist, on an international level, which was pointed out as an advantage in this regard.

4.4.2. Conclusions on Education

Participation in activities such Focus Groups or Scientific Dialogic Gatherings are an effective way to increase interesse and awareness of the role of science and the impact of scientific research in fields like Medicine, for example. As a consequence, this may encourage people to participate more actively in science-related activities or topics.

Science is perceived as an effective way to address every day topics like the importance of school or when is the time that violence starts to impact in people's lives. And research is also important for the evolution of society. In this sense, participation in the discussion of these topics increases self-confidence in people who are not used to get involved in these matters or do not have the right tools or platforms to get access to. It is clear, therefore, that disseminating the social impact of science is important.

Since science also brings improvements for people's daily life, people are becoming aware of this. However, the lack of scientific initiatives targeted to children, for example, appears as a factor that has a negative impact in the aim of engaging people with science and scientific research.

A stronger link between people and science helps to have better tools to explain, from a scientific point of view, issues concerning Education or Gender. This, in turn, help people to acquire a new role as professionals.

There are still some challenges in terms of how can scientific research become mainstream or in the public domain, since there are people who do not believe in science and do not understand the scientific method. In this sense, the awareness of the importance of scientific research is directly connected with the degree of people's trust in the field.

Another challenge is to help people identifying the impact of scientific research in Education or the people behind a project. In terms of inventions, for example, people have difficulties to identify the research that led to a specific result. In this sense, it is important to bring science closer to citizens so they can understand its impact and benefits and use the right platforms to do so.

5. Survey

5.1 Overview

The data from the survey provide us with valuable information to meet the objective of this first report on the use of statistical data. Specifically, objective 1 establishes the following: Identify in both, face to face interactions and social media interactions, how societal actors, including young citizens and vulnerable groups, benefit from the social impact of scientific research in gender and education.

The exploitation of the data was divided into three blocks. A first block addressed the sociodemographic questions; a second block focused on the questions of block one related to education and gender and a third block aimed at deepening the role of interactions in having a more excellent knowledge of scientific evidence against hoaxes on gender and education.

5.2. Exploitation of the data

5.2.1. Sociodemographic questions

The total sample is 7507 cases, whose distribution by gender, as shown in the table below, shows 51.1% of women and 48.9% of men.

Gender

Table 5.1. Distribution by gender

	Frequency	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
Women	3839	51,1	51,1	51,1
Men	3668	48,9	48,9	100,0
Total	7507	100,0	100,0	

The highest proportion of cases is found in the 35 to 49 age group, with 31.8%, followed by the 50 to 60 age group with 25.5%. We will pay special attention to young citizens as a group of particular interest, as reflected in objective one. Young people between 16 and 34 account for 24.6%, with the youngest (16 to 24 years) accounting for 7.8%.

Age

Table 5.2. Distribution by age

	Frequency	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
16-24	582	7,8	7,8	7,8
25-34	1261	16,8	16,8	24,6
35-49	2385	31,8	31,8	56,3
50-64	1917	25,5	25,5	81,9
+65	1362	18,1	18,1	100,0
Total	7507	100,0	100,0	

The distribution of the sample by country shows how Germany, Spain and France are the most represented with 13,3% the first two countries and with 13,5% the third one. That means the 40,1% of the total sample.

Country

Table 5.3. Distribution by country

	Frequency	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
Germany	1000	13,3	13,3	13,3
Cyprus	200	2,7	2,7	16,0
Croatia	205	2,7	2,7	18,7
Slovakia	694	9,2	9,2	28,0
Spain	999	13,3	13,3	41,3
Finland	703	9,4	9,4	50,6
France	1011	13,5	13,5	64,1

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Ireland	208	2,8	2,8	66,9
Italy	203	2,7	2,7	69,6
Luxemburg	200	2,7	2,7	72,2
Netherlands	686	9,1	9,1	81,4
Portugal	705	9,4	9,4	90,8
Romania	693	9,2	9,2	100,0
Total	7507	100,0	100,0	

The level of education indicates a low percentage of the population with slighter than lower secondary education, 18.6%. This same percentage in the case of the mother's level of studies increases to 51.7%. In turn, the percentage of the population with a master's degree or doctorate is 16.8%. The mother's level of studies is much lower in this case, at 6.1%. The highest percentage is found among those with upper secondary education, at 25.2%.

Indicate the highest course or educational level you have completed

Table 5.4. Distribution by level of education.

	Frequency	%	Valid %	Cumulated %
Educational development during early childhood or preschool education	100	1,3	1,3	1,3
Basic education	303	4,0	4,0	5,4
Lower secondary education	1000	13,3	13,3	18,7
Upper secondary education	1895	25,2	25,2	43,9
Post-secondary non-tertiary education	406	5,4	5,4	49,3
Short cycle tertiary education	446	5,9	5,9	55,3

Bachelor's degree or equivalent	1709	22,8	22,8	78,0
Master or equivalent	1080	14,4	14,4	92,4
Doctorate or equivalent	183	2,4	2,4	94,9
I do not know	221	2,9	2,9	97,8
Prefer not to answer	164	2,2	2,2	100,0
Total	7507	100,0	100,0	

What level of education does (or did) your mother have?

Table 5.5. Distribution by mother's level of education.

	Frequency	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
Educational development during early childhood or preschool education	230	3,1	3,1	3,1
Basic education	2134	28,4	28,4	31,5
Lower secondary education	1518	20,2	20,2	51,7
Upper secondary education	1346	17,9	17,9	69,6
Post-secondary non-tertiary education	321	4,3	4,3	73,9
Short cycle tertiary education	325	4,3	4,3	78,2
Bachelor's degree or equivalent	611	8,1	8,1	86,4
Master or equivalent	357	4,8	4,8	91,1
Doctorate or equivalent	94	1,3	1,3	92,4

I do not know	407	5,4	5,4	97,8
Prefer not to answer	164	2,2	2,2	100,0
Total	7507	100,0	100,0	

The percentages for belonging to an ethnic minority group and a religious group are low, at 7% and 8.6%, respectively. Of those surveyed, 14.8% stated that at least one of their parents was born in another country. However, slightly more surprising is the percentage of people who claim to have disabilities or medical condition that limits their daily activities, reaching the 17,1%.

Do you consider yourself to belong to an ethnic minority group?

Table 5.6. Distribution by ethnic minority group.

	Frequency	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
Yes	523	7,0	7,0	7,0
No	6439	85,8	85,8	92,7
I do not know	443	5,9	5,9	98,6
Prefer not to answer	102	1,4	1,4	100,0
Total	7507	100,0	100,0	

Do you consider yourself to belong to a religious minority group?

Table 5.7. Distribution by religious minority group.

	Frequency	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
Yes	645	8,6	8,6	8,6
No	6442	85,8	85,8	94,4

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

I do not know	328	4,4	4,4	98,8
Prefer not to answer	92	1,2	1,2	100,0
Total	7507	100,0	100,0	

Do you have a disability or medical condition that limits your daily activities?

Table 5.8. Distribution by people with disabilities.

	Frequency	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
Yes	1284	17,1	17,1	17,1
No	5924	78,9	78,9	96,0
I do not know	194	2,6	2,6	98,6
Prefer not to answer	105	1,4	1,4	100,0
Total	7507	100,0	100,0	

Was one of his parents born in a foreign country

Table 5.9. Distribution by people whose parents were born in a foreign country.

	Frequency	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
Yes one of them	605	8,1	8,1	8,1
Yes, both	502	6,7	6,7	14,7
No, none of them	6213	82,8	82,8	97,5
I do not know	135	1,8	1,8	99,3
Prefer not to answer	52	,7	,7	100,0

Total **7507** **100,0** **100,0**

In terms of employment, it is noteworthy that practically 20% of the people surveyed are retired. The level of unemployment stands at 5.8%. Also noteworthy is the 45.7% percentage of full-time employment among the participants.

What is your current employment status?

Table 5.10. Distribution by employment status.

	Frequency	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
Full time employee	3427	45,7	45,7	45,7
Part-time employee	637	8,5	8,5	54,1
Unemployed	438	5,8	5,8	60,0
Voluntarily unemployed	80	1,1	1,1	61,0
Student	302	4,0	4,0	65,1
Student with job	102	1,4	1,4	66,4
Retired, disabled	1478	19,7	19,7	86,1
Housewife	384	5,1	5,1	91,2
I do not know	86	1,1	1,1	92,4
Prefer not to answer	573	7,6	7,6	100,0
Total	7507	100,0	100,0	

Regarding employment, both in the present and the past. 21.6% of those surveyed have worked or are working in the education sector related to professions related to the education sector. Therefore, practically one out of every four persons surveyed works in education. This percentage decreases to 8.8% when referring to professions or job positions related to gender issues.

Practices (work) or as practiced (has worked in) any profession in the education sector

Table 5.11. Distribution by professional practices in the educational sector

	Frequency	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
Yes (in the past)	1041	13,9	13,9	13,9
Yes (at the present)	577	7,7	7,7	21,6
No	5666	75,5	75,5	97,0
I do not know	145	1,9	1,9	99,0
Prefer not to answer	78	1,0	1,0	100,0
Total	7507	100,0	100,0	

Practices (works) or has practiced (has worked in) any profession or position in gender matters

Table 5.12. Distribution by professional practices in gender matters

	Frequency	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
Yes (in the past)	376	5,0	5,0	5,0
Yes (at the present)	282	3,8	3,8	8,8
No	6618	88,2	88,2	96,9
I do not know	160	2,1	2,1	99,1
Prefer not to answer	71	,9	,9	100,0
Total	7507	100,0	100,0	

30.2% of the people surveyed have a gross annual income of less than €1,043. Approximately one-third of the people surveyed have a net monthly income of at most one thousand euros.

Gross annual household income in euros

Table 5.13. Distribution by gross annual household income.

	Frequency	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
Less than 10562€	1202	16,0	16,0	16,0
Between 10562€ and 16043€	1069	14,2	14,2	30,3
Between 16043€ and 23.295€	1180	15,7	15,7	46,0
More than 23.295€	2654	35,4	35,4	81,3
I do not know	363	4,8	4,8	86,2
Prefer not to answer	1039	13,8	13,8	100,0
Total	7507	100,0	100,0	

5.2.2. Analysis of the questions related to education

To analyze citizens' awareness of the impact of scientific research on education, we have introduced two questions in the questionnaire:

- Have you received any information on results of educational research published in scientific journals such as Harvard, Cambridge or others, from any initiative launched through the following media/communication tools?
- What kind of initiative do you know that helps distinguish scientific evidence from educational hoaxes well?

In both cases, several response options are provided to participants and include the following communication tools: post mail, e-mail, phones, SMS/Text message, video conference and web

conference, social networks, G Suite and Microsoft 365/Office and online Collaboration/Productivity Tools and the following initiatives: news, applications (apps), online platforms, scientific journals, scientific books, universities and web pages.⁹

Question 1

Regarding the question “Have you received any information on results of educational research published in scientific journals such as Harvard, Cambridge or others, from any initiative launched through the following media/communication tools?”, we can see that more than half (52.6%) of the responders have not received information of scientific research on education from any of the communication tools. However, 12.7% of the respondents received this information from social networks.

Table 5.14. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence “Have you received any information on results of educational research published in scientific journals such as Harvard, Cambridge or others, from any initiative launched through the following media/communication tools?”

	Frequency	Percentage	Accumulated percentage
Post mail	220	2,4%	2,4%
E-mail	738	8,2%	10,6%
Phones	356	4,0%	14,6%
SMS/Text message	252	2,8%	17,4%
Video conference and web conference	258	2,9%	20,2%
Social networks	1142	12,7%	32,9%
G Suite and Microsoft 365/Office	152	1,7%	34,6%
Online Collaboration/Productivity Tools	294	3,3%	37,9%
Others	56	0,6%	38,5%
None	4739	52,6%	91,1%
I do not know	734	8,1%	99,2%
I prefer not to answer	68	0,8%	100,0%
TOTAL	9009	100,0%	100,0%

The response of people from vulnerable groups

As we have seen, more than half of participants had not received information about results of scientific research on education from any communication tool and the most common communication tool from which participants had received information about these results were social networks. If we look at possible differences across vulnerable groups, we see that, in general, this is not the case.

⁹ The questions are multi-answer. The percentages are calculated on the total number of participants but taking into account the possibility that multiple answers may have been provided.

For example, if we analyse the differences by gender, we can see that of the 3815 women who participated in the survey, 2433 (63.77%) had not received any information about scientific research on education, while 2261 of the 3608 men (62.67%) responded in this line. In addition, the most selected communication tool was social media (14.84% in women and 15.72% in men).

Table 5.15. Percentage of respondents according to their answers to the question “Have you received any information on results of educational research published in scientific journals such as Harvard, Cambridge or others, from any initiative launched through the following media/communication tools?”, by gender.

	Woman	Man	Trans	Non binary	Fluid	Others	Prefer not to answer	Total
Post mail	2,62	3,22	28,57	16,67	0,00	0,00	0,00	2,93
E-mail	8,26	11,70	14,29	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	9,83
Phones	4,22	5,27	0,00	8,33	16,67	0,00	9,09	4,74
SMS/Text message	3,04	3,66	0,00	0,00	16,67	3,85	6,06	3,36
Video conference and web conference	2,94	3,94	0,00	8,33	16,67	3,85	3,03	3,44
Social networks	14,84	15,72	28,57	8,33	16,67	7,69	9,09	15,21
G Suite and Microsoft 365/Office	1,81	2,27	14,29	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	2,02
Online Collaboration/Productivity Tools	3,59	4,27	0,00	8,33	0,00	3,85	3,03	3,92
Others	0,73	0,75	0,00	0,00	0,00	3,85	0,00	0,75
None	63,77	62,67	28,57	33,33	33,33	80,77	48,48	63,13
I do not know	10,62	8,73	0,00	41,67	16,67	7,69	18,18	9,78
prefer not to answer	1,00	0,72	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	12,12	0,91

If we focus on the gender vulnerable groups, we can observe the proportion of participants from the LGBTIQ had not received information about results of educational research was slightly lower (56.86%).

Table 5.16. Percentage of respondents according to their answers to the question “Have you received any information on results of educational research published in scientific journals such as Harvard, Cambridge or others, from any initiative launched through the following media/communication tools?”, by vulnerable gender groups.

	Woman	LGBTI+	Prefer not to answer
Post mail	2,62	7,84	0,00
E-mail	8,26	1,96	0,00
Phones	4,22	3,92	9,09
SMS/Text message	3,04	3,92	6,06
Video conference and web conference	2,94	5,88	3,03
Social networks	14,84	11,76	9,09
G Suite and Microsoft 365/Office	1,81	1,96	0,00
Online Collaboration/ Productivity Tools	3,59	3,92	3,03
Others	0,73	1,96	0,00
None	63,77	56,86	48,48
I do not know	10,62	15,69	18,18
prefer not to answer	1,00	0,00	12,12

The following is an analysis of the response by the age of respondents:

Table 5.17. Percentage of respondents according to their answers to the question “Have you received any information on results of educational research published in scientific journals such as Harvard, Cambridge or others, from any initiative launched through the following media/communication tools?”, by age groups.

	16-24	25-34	35-49	50-64	+65	Total
Post mail	6,53	4,36	3,14	2,09	0,88	2,93
E-mail	15,81	15,86	11,07	6,31	4,48	9,83
Phones	11,34	8,33	4,74	2,40	1,91	4,74
SMS/Text message	7,39	5,79	3,44	2,09	1,03	3,36
Video conference and web conference	7,22	5,71	3,48	2,30	1,25	3,44
Social networks	25,09	23,24	15,51	11,22	8,66	15,21
G Suite and Microsoft 365/Office	5,50	3,25	2,22	0,99	0,51	2,02
Online Collaboration/ Productivity Tools	8,42	6,66	4,11	2,24	1,47	3,92
Others	1,37	0,16	0,42	0,94	1,32	0,75
None	42,27	50,83	61,01	72,30	74,23	63,13
I do not know	9,45	8,72	10,78	8,76	10,57	9,78
prefer not to answer	1,37	1,03	0,92	0,99	0,44	0,91

This analysis points out that the proportion of youth (participants aged 16-34), who had not received information about scientific research on education was lower (42.27% for respondents aged 16-24 and 50.83% for those aged 25-34) than the rest of the age groups. In this line, we can see how the proportion of participants who received information about scientific research on education decreases with the age of the participants. In addition, a higher proportion of youth (approximately 23-25%) received this type of information from social networks. In the same vein, the analyses concludes that youth aged between 16-34 represented between 38.44%

and 48.03% of the total of respondents who received information about educational research from all the communication tools:

Table 5.18. Percentage of respondents according to their answers to the question “Have you received any information on results of educational research published in scientific journals such as Harvard, Cambridge or others, from any initiative launched through the following media/communication tools?”, by age groups and communication tools.

	Post mail	E-mail	Phones	SMS/Text message	Video conference and web conference	Social networks	G Suite and Microsoft 365/Office	Online Collaboration/ Productivity Tools	Others	None	I do not know	prefer not to answer
16-34	42,27	39,57	48,03	46,03	44,19	38,44	48,03	45,24	17,86	18,72	22,48	30,88
35-49	34,09	35,77	31,74	32,54	32,17	32,40	34,87	33,33	17,86	30,70	35,01	32,35
50-64	18,18	16,40	12,92	15,87	17,05	18,83	12,50	14,63	32,14	29,25	22,89	27,94
+65	5,45	8,27	7,30	5,56	6,59	10,33	4,61	6,80	32,14	21,33	19,62	8,82
TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

Regarding participants from low SES group, which includes a gross income below 16043€ per year, the results are the following.

Table 5.19. Percentage of respondents according to their answers to the question “Have you received any information on results of educational research published in scientific journals such as Harvard, Cambridge or others, from any initiative launched through the following media/communication tools?”, by low level of SES¹⁰.

	Low SES	Total
Post mail	3,74	2,93
E-mail	11,76	9,83
Phones	6,65	4,74
SMS/Text message	4,23	3,36

¹⁰ Low SES is defined as having gross income below 16,043 Euros per year.

Video conference and web conference	4,01	3,44
Social networks	17,53	15,21
G Suite and Microsoft 365/Office	2,69	2,02
Online Collaboration/ Productivity Tools	4,49	3,92
Others	0,57	0,75
None	59,49	63,13
I do not know	8,94	9,78
prefer not to answer	0,62	0,91

As seen in the table less than 6 out of 10 the respondents (59.49%) from SES expressed that they had not received any information about scientific research on education. This result is similar to the 63.13% of the total respondents. The main communicative tool in this case are also social networks (17.53%).

In the case of ethnic minorities, we observe that the proportion of people from ethnic minorities who had not received information about research on education is lower than the total of respondents. Specifically, we can observe that 37.09% of respondents from ethnic minorities had not received any information about educational research, in comparison with the 63.13% of the total respondents. The most reported communication tool in which respondents from ethnic minorities had received this information were social networks (28.11%), followed by e-mail (22.75%).

Table 5.20. Percentage of respondents according to their answers to the question “Have you received any information on results of educational research published in scientific journals such as Harvard, Cambridge or others, from any initiative launched through the following media/communication tools?”, for belonging to an ethnic minority group.

	Yes	No	I do not know	I prefer not to answer	Total
Post mail	10,90	2,30	2,71	2,94	2,93

E-mail	22,75	8,84	9,93	5,88	9,83
Phones	16,44	3,76	5,42	3,92	4,74
SMS/Text message	12,43	2,53	5,19	0,98	3,36
Video conference and web conference	12,43	2,56	5,42	3,92	3,44
Social networks	28,11	14,29	15,12	7,84	15,21
G Suite and Microsoft 365/Office	7,27	1,48	3,61	2,94	2,02
Online Collaboration/ Productivity Tools	14,53	3,06	4,29	1,96	3,92
Others	1,15	0,76	0,23	0,00	0,75
None	37,09	67,01	41,99	43,14	63,13
I do not know	5,74	9,02	23,25	19,61	9,78
prefer not to answer	0,19	0,61	1,81	19,61	0,91

It is also important to remark that, despite representing a 6.97% of the participants, the proportion of participants from ethnic minority groups who received results of educational research from all communication tools ranges between 12.87% to 25.91%

Table 5.21. Percentage of respondents according to their answers to the question “Have you received any information on results of educational research published in scientific journals such as Harvard, Cambridge or others, from any initiative launched through the following media/communication tools?”, by ethnic minorities and communication tools.

	Post mail	E-mail	Phones	SMS/ Text message	Video conference and web conference	Social networks	G Suite Microsoft 365/ Office	Online Collaboration/ Productivity Tools	Others	None	TOTAL
Yes	25,91	16,12	24,16	25,79	25,19	12,87	25,00	25,85	10,71	4,09	6,97
No	67,27	77,10	67,98	64,68	63,95	80,56	62,50	67,01	87,50	91,05	85,77

I do not know	5,45	5,96	6,74	9,13	9,30	5,87	10,53	6,46	1,79	3,92	5,90
Prefer not to answer	1,36	0,81	1,12	0,40	1,55	0,70	1,97	0,68	0,00	0,93	1,36
TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

The same trend is observed in the analysis by religious minorities. Approximately one quarter of the respondents (41.26%) had not received information about results from educational research and the most common communication tools were social networks (25.27%) and e-mail (22.02%).

Table 5.22. Percentage of respondents according to their answers to the question “Have you received any information on results of educational research published in scientific journals such as Harvard, Cambridge or others, from any initiative launched through the following media/communication tools?”, for belonging to a religious minority group.

	Yes	No	I do not know	I prefer not to answer	Total
Post mail	8,84	2,41	2,13	1,09	2,93
E-mail	22,02	8,71	9,45	4,35	9,83
Phones	15,35	3,60	6,71	3,26	4,74
SMS/Text message	9,15	2,73	4,88	1,09	3,36
Video conference and web conference	9,77	2,79	3,96	2,17	3,44
Social networks	25,27	14,42	11,28	14,13	15,21
G Suite and Microsoft 365/Office	7,13	1,51	2,13	2,17	2,02
Online Collaboration/ Productivity Tools	11,47	3,26	2,74	1,09	3,92

Others	0,78	0,78	0,30	0,00	0,75
None	41,86	66,52	42,99	46,74	63,13
I do not know	5,27	9,36	25,91	13,04	9,78
prefer not to answer	0,31	0,68	1,52	18,48	0,91

The impact of interactions

The objective of this section is to analyse whether the interactions of respondents from vulnerable with science have an impact on receiving or not information about scientific research on education. The two interactions are:

- Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?
- Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?

Among women who responded that something happened to her or her family that made her change her mind about science, the proportion of women who had not received information about educational research was lower (53.36% compared with the 63.77% of the total of women). Also in this case, social networks were the communication tool most used to receive information, with a total of 22.46% of responses from women with interactions with science (compared with 14.84% of the total of women). Similar results were found in all the communication tools

Table 5.23. Percentage of respondents who answered “YES” to the question “Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science” according to their answers to the question “Have you received any information on results of educational research published in scientific journals such as Harvard, Cambridge or others, from any initiative launched through the following media/communication tools?”, by gender.

	Woman	Man	Non binary	Fluid	Others	Prefer not to answer	Total
Post mail	4,80	7,20	16,67	0,00	0,00	0,00	5,86
E-mail	12,76	20,39	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	15,99

Phones	8,16	11,36	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	9,49
SMS/Text message	5,85	7,69	0,00	0,00	20,00	0,00	6,66
Video conference and web conference	5,28	8,06	16,67	0,00	20,00	0,00	6,56
Social networks	22,46	26,86	16,67	0,00	40,00	33,33	24,41
G Suite and Microsoft 365/Office	3,36	4,76	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	3,94
Online Collaboration/ Productivity Tools	6,53	9,89	0,00	0,00	20,00	0,00	8,00
Others	1,25	0,85	0,00	0,00	20,00	0,00	1,12
None	53,36	47,74	33,33	0,00	40,00	33,33	50,75
I do not know	8,54	5,86	33,33	100,00	0,00	0,00	7,46
prefer not to answer	0,67	0,12	0,00	0,00	0,00	33,33	0,48

If we look closer to the members of the LGBTI+ community, we find the same trend. In this case 33.33% of the individuals from the LGBTI+ community who expressed that they had changed their mind about science because something happened to them or their families, expressed that they had not received any information about scientific research on education, compared with the 56.86% of the total.

Table 5.24. Percentage of respondents who answered “YES” to the question “Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science” according to their answers to the question “Have you received any information on results of educational research published in scientific journals such as Harvard, Cambridge or others, from any initiative launched through the following media/communication tools?”, by vulnerable gender groups.

	Woman	LGBTI+	Prefer not to answer
--	-------	--------	----------------------

Post mail	4,80	8,33	0,00
E-mail	12,76	0,00	0,00
Phones	8,16	0,00	0,00
SMS/Text message	5,85	8,33	0,00
Video conference and web conference	5,28	16,67	0,00
Social networks	22,46	25,00	33,33
G Suite and Microsoft 365/Office	3,36	0,00	0,00
Online Collaboration/ Productivity Tools	6,53	8,33	0,00
Others	1,25	8,33	0,00
None	53,36	33,33	33,33
I do not know	8,54	25,00	0,00
prefer not to answer	0,67	0,00	33,33

When we analyse the impact of following a scientific person in social networks, we find that, among women following a scientific person in social networks, the proportion of those who had not received information about educational research was lower (52.90% compared with the 63.77% of the total of women), being social networks the most used communication tool (24.84%):

Table 5.25. Percentage of respondents who answered “YES” to the question “Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?” according to their answers to the question “Have you received any information on results of educational research published in scientific journals such as Harvard, Cambridge or others, from any initiative launched through the following media/communication tools?”, by gender.

	Woman	Man	Non binary	Fluid	Others	Prefer not to answer	Total
--	-------	-----	------------	-------	--------	----------------------	-------

Post mail	4,47	5,98	0,00	20,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
E-mail	13,71	18,42	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
Phones	7,05	8,30	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	28,57
SMS/Text message	5,09	6,06	0,00	0,00	0,00	11,11	0,00
Video conference and web conference	5,49	7,39	0,00	20,00	0,00	11,11	0,00
Social networks	24,84	27,39	0,00	0,00	33,33	11,11	14,29
G Suite and Microsoft 365/Office	3,13	4,32	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
Online Collaboration/ Productivity Tools	6,66	6,97	0,00	0,00	0,00	11,11	0,00
Others	1,57	1,16	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
None	52,90	49,88	100,00	20,00	66,67	77,78	14,29
I do not know	7,84	6,14	0,00	60,00	0,00	0,00	28,57
prefer not to answer	0,47	0,17	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	14,29

However, if we look closer to the members of the LGBTI+ community, we do not find this trend. On the contrary, among people from the LGBTI+ community who followed a scientific person in social networks, the percentage of respondents who had never received information about scientific results in education was 61.11%, slightly above the 56.86% of the total of the LGBTI+ community.

Table 5.26. Percentage of respondents who answered “YES” to the question “Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?” according to their answers to the question “Have you received any information on results of educational research published in scientific journals such as Harvard, Cambridge or others, from

any initiative launched through the following media/communication tools?”, by vulnerable gender groups.

	Woman	LGBTI+	Prefer not to answer
Post mail	4,47	5,56	0,00
E-mail	13,71	0,00	0,00
Phones	7,05	0,00	0,00
SMS/Text message	5,09	5,56	11,11
Video conference and web conference	5,49	11,11	11,11
Social networks	24,84	11,11	11,11
G Suite and Microsoft 365/Office	3,13	0,00	0,00
Online Collaboration/ Productivity Tools	6,66	5,56	11,11
Others	1,57	0,00	0,00
None	52,90	61,11	77,78
I do not know	7,84	16,67	0,00
prefer not to answer	0,47	0,00	0,00

The analysis of the interactions across age groups, indicates that, on the one hand, the proportion of youth who changed their mind about science due to previous experience with science and had not received information about scientific research in education was less than one third for youth 16-24 (32.49%) and 40.15% in youth (25-34). On the other hand, the impact of interactions with science in social networks shows that, 37.88% of youth aged 16-24 and 44.14% of youth 25-34 who follow a scientist on social media had never received information about scientific results in education. On the contrary, as abovementioned, the total proportion of youth who had never received information about educational research was 42.27% and 50.83% in youth 16-24 and 25-34. In both cases, as well as in the total of participants, the proportion of respondents who received information about educational research decreases with

age. Finally, in both interactions, nearly one third of youth with interactions with science received information about scientific research in education from social networks.

Table 5.27. Percentage of respondents who answered “YES” to the question “Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science” according to their answers to the question “Have you received any information on results of educational research published in scientific journals such as Harvard, Cambridge or others, from any initiative launched through the following media/communication tools?”, by age groups.

	16-24	25-34	35-49	50-64	+65	Total
Post mail	9,64	8,37	5,23	5,25	1,24	5,86
E-mail	17,77	22,91	17,20	11,64	7,85	15,99
Phones	17,77	11,82	10,46	5,48	3,72	9,49
SMS/Text message	12,18	10,59	6,58	3,42	1,65	6,66
Video conference and web conference	10,66	9,36	7,59	3,20	2,07	6,56
Social networks	34,52	30,79	24,79	19,18	14,05	24,41
G Suite and Microsoft 365/Office	7,11	5,42	5,23	1,14	0,83	3,94
Online Collaboration/ Productivity Tools	16,24	11,82	7,59	3,88	3,31	8,00
Others	3,05	0,00	0,84	1,37	1,65	1,12
None	32,49	40,15	48,23	63,47	66,53	50,75
I do not know	7,61	5,91	8,77	6,62	8,26	7,46
prefer not to answer	0,51	0,25	0,34	0,68	0,83	0,48

Table 5.28. Percentage of respondents who answered “YES” to the question “Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?” according to their answers to the question “Have you received any information on results of educational research published in scientific journals such as Harvard, Cambridge or others, from any initiative launched through the following media/communication tools?”, by age groups.

	16-24	25-34	35-49	50-64	+65	Total
Post mail	8,19	6,96	4,48	4,78	1,88	5,19
E-mail	18,77	20,33	16,73	11,85	9,72	15,84
Phones	12,97	10,44	7,39	4,59	3,76	7,66
SMS/Text message	7,85	7,33	5,33	4,59	2,51	5,55
Video conference and web conference	9,22	7,88	6,91	4,40	3,45	6,42
Social networks	33,11	31,14	25,09	20,27	21,94	25,94
G Suite and Microsoft 365/Office	6,83	4,21	4,12	2,10	1,25	3,67
Online Collaboration/ Productivity Tools	10,58	9,71	7,03	4,02	2,19	6,78
Others	2,39	0,37	0,73	2,10	2,51	1,36
None	37,88	44,14	51,52	62,14	58,31	51,40
I do not know	7,17	6,04	8,24	5,74	8,46	7,14
prefer not to answer	0,34	0,37	0,24	0,57	0,31	0,36

Regarding people from socioeconomic status, almost six out of ten (59.49%) of the total of respondents from low socioeconomic status not received information about scientific evidence on education. When deepening on the impact of interactions with science, we find that on the one hand, the results among people from low SES who had changed their mind about science because something happened was 46.98% and on the other hand, the percentage among people from low SES who followed a scientific person on social media was 46.13%. This way, while 17.53% of the formers received scientific evidence on education through social networks, in the people from low SES who had

interacted with science the proportion was more than one quarter (26.59%) in the first interaction 28.93% in the second.

Table 5.29. Percentage of respondents who answered “YES” to the question “Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science” according to their answers to the question “Have you received any information on results of educational research published in scientific journals such as Harvard, Cambridge or others, from any initiative launched through the following media/communication tools?”, by low level of SES¹¹.

	Low SES	Total
Post mail	6,80	5,86
E-mail	17,67	15,99
Phones	12,24	9,49
SMS/Text message	6,95	6,66
Video conference and web conference	7,10	6,56
Social networks	26,59	24,41
G Suite and Microsoft 365/Office	5,44	3,94
Online Collaboration/ Productivity Tools	8,76	8,00
Others	0,60	1,12
None	46,98	50,75
I do not know	5,74	7,46
prefer not to answer	0,60	0,48

Table 5.30. Percentage of respondents who answered “YES” to the question “Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?”

¹¹ Low SES is defined as having gross income below 16,043 Euros per year.

according to their answers to the question “Have you received any information on results of educational research published in scientific journals such as Harvard, Cambridge or others, from any initiative launched through the following media/communication tools?”, by low level of SES².

	Low SES	Total
Post mail	6,36	5,19
E-mail	18,08	15,84
Phones	11,10	7,66
SMS/Text message	6,23	5,55
Video conference and web conference	7,23	6,42
Social networks	28,93	25,94
G Suite and Microsoft 365/Office	5,49	3,67
Online Collaboration/ Productivity Tools	7,61	6,78
Others	1,00	1,36
None	46,13	51,40
I do not know	5,99	7,14
prefer not to answer	0,50	0,36

The same trend is observed in the case of ethnic minorities. As mentioned before, within the total of ethnic minorities, the percentage of respondents who had not received information about scientific results in education was 37.09%. When we include the impact of interactions with science, we find that the proportion of people from ethnic minorities who had not received information on results of educational research was lower. In this line 25.36% of people from ethnic minorities who changed their mind about science because something happened and 21.67% of those who followed a scientific person in social networks had not received information on results of educational research. This way, in this case the proportion of respondents who received this information through social networks was almost one third (32.42%) and through e-

mail (28.52%) in the case of the first interaction and 37.64% through social networks and 30.04% through e-mail in the second.

Table 5.31. Percentage of respondents who answered “YES” to the question “Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science” according to their answers to the question “Have you received any information on results of educational research published in scientific journals such as Harvard, Cambridge or others, from any initiative launched through the following media/communication tools?”, by ethnic minority group.

	Yes	No	I do not know	I prefer not to answer	Total
Post mail	17,19	3,97	6,32	0,00	5,86
E-mail	28,52	14,10	13,68	7,14	15,99
Phones	25,39	7,08	6,32	0,00	9,49
SMS/Text message	16,41	4,77	11,58	0,00	6,66
Video conference and web conference	17,97	4,70	6,32	0,00	6,56
Social networks	32,42	23,03	26,32	14,29	24,41
G Suite and Microsoft 365/Office	10,16	2,85	5,26	0,00	3,94
Online Collaboration/ Productivity Tools	21,48	5,82	7,37	0,00	8,00
Others	1,56	1,06	1,05	0,00	1,12
None	25,39	56,52	30,53	28,57	50,75
I do not know	3,52	7,21	20,00	21,43	7,46
prefer not to answer	0,00	0,33	0,00	28,57	0,48

Table 32. Percentage of respondents who answered “YES” to the question “Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?” according to their answers to the question “Have you received any information on results of educational research published in scientific journals such as Harvard, Cambridge or others, from

any initiative launched through the following media/communication tools?", by ethnic minority group.

	Yes	No	I do not know	I prefer not to answer	Total
Post mail	15,21	3,85	6,12	12,50	5,19
E-mail	30,04	14,37	12,24	0,00	15,84
Phones	23,57	5,87	5,10	0,00	7,66
SMS/Text message	16,73	4,04	9,18	0,00	5,55
Video conference and web conference	19,77	4,56	10,20	12,50	6,42
Social networks	37,64	24,28	31,63	18,75	25,94
G Suite and Microsoft 365/Office	10,27	2,72	6,12	6,25	3,67
Online Collaboration/ Productivity Tools	21,29	5,03	6,12	6,25	6,78
Others	1,14	1,41	1,02	0,00	1,36
None	21,67	55,75	37,76	43,75	51,40
I do not know	4,18	7,37	10,20	6,25	7,14
prefer not to answer	0,00	0,23	0,00	25,00	0,36

The impact of interactions with science is also perceived in people from religious minorities. In this case, among people from religious minorities who changed their mind about science because something happened to them or their families, less than three out of ten (29.68%) expressed not having received information about results of educational research and among those who followed a scientific person of social media, a similar proportion (29.66%) expressed the same. Within the total of people from religious minorities, the proportion was 41.86%. The most common communication tools in this case were social networks (31.45%), e-mail (26.86%) and phones (25.44%) in the first interaction and social networks (33.94%), e-mail (26.30%) and phones (22.32%) in the second.

Table 5.33. Percentage of respondents who answered "YES" to the question "Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?"

according to their answers to the question “Have you received any information on results of educational research published in scientific journals such as Harvard, Cambridge or others, from any initiative launched through the following media/communication tools?”, for belonging to a religious minority group.

	Yes	No	I do not know	I prefer not to answer	Total
Post mail	12,84	4,05	4,69	0,00	5,19
E-mail	26,30	14,25	18,75	0,00	15,84
Phones	22,32	5,48	6,25	0,00	7,66
SMS/Text message	13,46	4,29	7,81	0,00	5,55
Video conference and web conference	15,90	5,00	4,69	5,88	6,42
Social networks	33,94	24,74	25,00	23,53	25,94
G Suite and Microsoft 365/Office	10,40	2,67	3,13	0,00	3,67
Online Collaboration/ Productivity Tools	15,60	5,58	3,13	0,00	6,78
Others	0,92	1,43	1,56	0,00	1,36
None	29,66	55,10	37,50	64,71	51,40
I do not know	2,45	7,72	14,06	0,00	7,14
prefer not to answer	0,31	0,29	0,00	11,76	0,36

Table 5.34. Percentage of respondents who answered “YES” to the question “Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science” according to their answers to the question “Have you received any information on results of educational research published in scientific journals such as Harvard, Cambridge or others, from any initiative launched through the following media/communication tools?”, for belonging to a religious minority group.

	Yes	No	I do not know	I prefer not to answer	Total
Post mail	13,43	4,62	3,13	0,00	5,86
E-mail	26,86	14,26	12,50	0,00	15,99
Phones	25,44	6,80	4,69	0,00	9,49
SMS/Text message	14,13	5,21	9,38	0,00	6,66
Video conference and web conference	17,31	4,69	4,69	0,00	6,56
Social networks	31,45	23,50	15,63	21,43	24,41
G Suite and Microsoft 365/Office	10,25	2,77	4,69	0,00	3,94
Online Collaboration/ Productivity Tools	18,02	6,40	3,13	0,00	8,00
Others	0,35	1,25	1,56	0,00	1,12
None	29,68	55,18	39,06	50,00	50,75
I do not know	3,89	7,59	17,19	21,43	7,46
prefer not to answer	0,00	0,53	0,00	7,14	0,48

Therefore, in almost all cases we observe how when citizens from vulnerable groups have interactions with science, they tend to express having received information about results of educational research. The only exception was found in the LGBTI+ community in the second interaction. In all cases, the main source were social networks.

Question 2

Regarding the question “What kind of initiative do you know that helps distinguish scientific evidence from educational hoaxes well?” we can see that 79.9% of the participants knew at least one initiative to distinguish scientific evidence from hoax. The most commonly initiatives identified by respondents were scientific magazines (16.6%), followed by universities (14.0%) and scientific books (13.6%) and the less common were applications (3.3%).

Table 5.35. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence "What kind of initiative do you know that helps distinguish scientific evidence from educational hoaxes well?"

	Frequency	Percentage	Accumulated percentage
Initiative through the news	1414	10,3%	10,3%
Applications (apps)	460	3,3%	13,6%
Online platforms	1419	10,3%	23,9%
Scientific magazines	2288	16,6%	40,5%
Scientific books	1880	13,6%	54,1%
Universities	1925	14,0%	68,1%
Websites	1560	11,3%	79,4%
Others	66	0,5%	79,9%
None	1462	10,6%	90,5%
I do not know	1252	9,1%	99,6%
Prefer not to answer	60	0,4%	100,0%
TOTAL	13786	100,0%	100,0%

The response of people from vulnerable groups

According to the data, it appears that more than half of the respondents identify this second statement as scientific evidence. When we review the data according to gender, we see that this trend is reversed. The gender variable does change the results. In the case of women, 43.2% say that the statement "The school can overcome inequalities and achieve educational success for students from families with low levels of income" is a hoax (compared to 31.4% who recognize it as scientific evidence).

Table 5.36. Percentage of respondents according to their answer to the question "What kind of initiative do you know that helps distinguish scientific evidence from educational hoaxes well?", by gender.

	Woman	Man	Trans	Non binary	Fluid	Others	Prefer not to answer	Total
Initiative through the news	18,43	19,48	0,00	25,00	0,00	15,38	3,03	18,84
Applications (apps)	5,64	6,74	0,00	0,00	0,00	3,85	3,03	6,13

Online platforms	18,32	19,76	28,57	8,33	33,33	3,85	3,03	18,90
Scientific magazines	29,41	31,93	42,86	33,33	16,67	11,54	9,09	30,48
Scientific books	24,38	25,89	57,14	33,33	33,33	7,69	12,12	25,04
Universities	24,95	26,66	42,86	16,67	33,33	7,69	6,06	25,64
Websites	19,27	22,48	14,29	16,67	16,67	19,23	15,15	20,78
Others	0,73	0,97	0,00	8,33	0,00	3,85	3,03	0,88
None	19,61	19,15	0,00	25,00	0,00	50,00	21,21	19,48
I do not know	18,19	14,94	0,00	8,33	33,33	11,54	39,39	16,68
Prefer not to answer	0,79	0,75	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	9,09	0,80

If we look closer to these data, taking into account the vulnerable gender groups, we see that the proportion of LGBTI+ individuals who do not know any initiative is higher than the total (31.37% VS 19.48%). This way, the most common initiative known by LGBTI+ participants were scientific books (23.53%).

Table 5.37. Percentage of respondents according to their answer to the question “What kind of initiative do you know that helps distinguish scientific evidence from educational hoaxes well?”, by vulnerable gender groups.

	Woman	LGBTI+	Prefer not to answer	Total
Initiative through the news	18,43	13,73	3,03	18,84
Applications (apps)	5,64	1,96	3,03	6,13
Online platforms	18,32	11,76	3,03	18,90

Scientific magazines	29,41	21,57	9,09	30,48
Scientific books	24,38	23,53	12,12	25,04
Universities	24,95	17,65	6,06	25,64
Websites	19,27	17,65	15,15	20,78
Others	0,73	3,92	3,03	0,88
None	19,61	31,37	21,21	19,48
I do not know	18,19	11,76	39,39	16,68
Prefer not to answer	0,79	0,00	9,09	0,80

Regarding youth, the results point out that the proportion of youth aged between 16 and 34 who did not know any initiative to distinguish scientific evidence from hoax was lower than in other age groups (10.82% in 16-24 years old and 12.69% in 25-34 years old, compared with the total of 19.48%). In the same line, the percentage of respondents who do not know any initiative increases across age groups. Universities are the most known in the case of 16–24-year-old youth (35.57%) and scientific magazines in the case of 25-34-year-old youth (32.12%).

Table 5.38. Percentage of respondents according to their answer to the question “What kind of initiative do you know that helps distinguish scientific evidence from educational hoaxes well?”, by age groups.

	16-24	25-34	35-49	50-64	+65	Total
Initiative through the news	18,56	16,49	19,08	19,98	19,09	18,84
Applications (apps)	12,20	9,83	6,00	4,12	3,16	6,13
Online platforms	28,01	24,58	20,67	15,86	10,94	18,90
Scientific magazines	31,96	32,12	30,40	30,26	28,78	30,48

Scientific books	31,79	29,26	25,12	22,64	21,51	25,04
Universities	35,57	30,21	25,66	22,74	21,22	25,64
Websites	28,35	29,74	21,59	17,27	12,78	20,78
Others	0,34	0,56	0,88	1,04	1,17	0,88
None	10,82	12,69	17,11	24,31	26,80	19,48
I do not know	10,48	13,01	17,82	18,31	18,43	16,68
Prefer not to answer	1,03	1,19	0,67	0,68	0,73	0,80

When we look at these data according to the SES group, we find that 17.31% of the respondents expressed not knowing any initiative, and scientific magazines were the most known (28.89%).

Table 5.39. Percentage of respondents according to their answer to the question “What kind of initiative do you know that helps distinguish scientific evidence from educational hoaxes well?”, by low level of SES.

	SES (level 2 and below)
Initiative through the news	18,76
Applications (apps)	7,88
Online platforms	22,37
Scientific magazines	28,89
Scientific books	25,67
Universities	26,24
Websites	22,99
Others	0,75
None	17,31

I do not know	15,76
Prefer not to answer	0,57

Less than 10% (9.56%) of participants from ethnic minorities state that they do not know any initiative to distinguish scientific evidence from hoax, in comparison with 19.48% of the total of respondents. Scientific magazines (30.59%) and scientific books (29.64%) are the most commonly known initiatives:

Table 5.40. Percentage of respondents according to their answers to the question “What kind of initiative do you know that helps distinguish scientific evidence from educational hoaxes well?”, for belonging to an ethnic minority group.

Ethnic minority group	Yes	No	I do not know	I prefer not to answer	Total
Initiative through the news	24,67	18,95	13,09	6,86	18,84
Applications (apps)	18,74	5,08	6,32	6,86	6,13
Online platforms	28,11	18,57	14,22	12,75	18,90
Scientific magazines	30,59	31,71	16,93	10,78	30,48
Scientific books	29,64	25,70	12,87	12,75	25,04
Universities	28,87	26,56	11,74	11,76	25,64
Websites	28,49	20,45	18,74	10,78	20,78
Others	0,57	0,93	0,68	0,00	0,88
None	9,56	20,58	15,12	19,61	19,48
I do not know	7,65	16,17	31,83	29,41	16,68
Prefer not to answer	0,57	0,50	1,58	17,65	0,80

Similar results are found when looking by religious minorities: people tend to know at least one initiative to distinguish between scientific evidence and hoax and only 12.87% of the participants from religious minorities say they do not know any.

Table 5.41. Percentage of respondents according to their answers to the question “What kind of initiative do you know that helps distinguish scientific evidence from educational hoaxes well?”, for belonging to a religious minority group.

Religious minority group	Yes	No	I do not know	I prefer not to answer	Total
Initiative through the news	22,02	19,05	10,98	9,78	18,84
Applications (apps)	14,88	5,26	7,01	2,17	6,13
Online platforms	27,29	18,52	12,50	9,78	18,90
Scientific magazines	32,09	31,34	13,41	19,57	30,48
Scientific books	28,84	25,49	12,50	11,96	25,04
Universities	28,99	26,06	14,33	13,04	25,64
Websites	27,29	20,41	17,68	11,96	20,78
Others	1,09	0,90	0,30	0,00	0,88
None	12,87	20,46	14,63	14,13	19,48
I do not know	9,46	16,36	35,06	23,91	16,68
Prefer not to answer	0,62	0,51	1,83	18,48	0,80

The impact of interactions

The objective of this section is to analyse whether the interactions of respondents from vulnerable with science have an impact on receiving or not information about scientific research on education. The two interactions are:

- Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?

- Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?

According to the data, while 19.61% of the total of women expressed do not know any initiative to distinguish educational evidence from hoaxes, the proportion of women among those who have interacted with science is lower. For example, within the women who express that they changed their mind about science because something happened to her, the percentage is 11.23%, and within those who follow a scientific person in social networks 8.86%. In both cases, scientific magazines were the most common (39.06% of women in the first case and 41.69% in the second).

Table 5.42. Percentage of respondents who answered “YES” to the question “Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science” according to their answers to the question “What kind of initiative do you know that helps distinguish scientific evidence from educational hoaxes well?”, by gender.

	Woman	Man	Trans	Non binary	Fluid	Others	Prefer not to answer	Total
Initiative through the news	24,66	24,66	33,33	0,00	0,00	0,00	24,57	24,66
Applications (apps)	9,50	10,38	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	9,81	9,50
Online platforms	26,30	26,74	16,67	0,00	0,00	0,00	26,33	26,30
Scientific magazines	39,06	40,42	33,33	0,00	0,00	33,33	39,50	39,06
Scientific books	31,48	34,19	50,00	0,00	20,00	0,00	32,62	31,48
Universities	31,19	35,04	16,67	0,00	20,00	0,00	32,73	31,19
Websites	26,39	31,14	16,67	0,00	40,00	33,33	28,46	26,39
Others	1,06	1,59	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	1,28	1,06
None	11,23	10,38	33,33	0,00	20,00	0,00	10,93	11,23
I do not know	11,04	8,18	0,00	100,00	40,00	33,33	9,91	11,04

Prefer not to answer	0,29	0,61	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,43	0,29
----------------------	------	------	------	------	------	------	------	------

Table 5.43. Percentage of respondents who answered “YES” to the question “Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?” according to their answers to the question “What kind of initiative do you know that helps distinguish scientific evidence from educational hoaxes well?”, by gender.

	Woman	Man	Trans	Non binary	Fluid	Others	Prefer not to answer	Total
Initiative through the news	24,45	23,32	0,00	20,00	0,00	11,11	14,29	23,78
Applications (apps)	9,40	10,37	0,00	0,00	0,00	11,11	0,00	9,82
Online platforms	29,39	31,78	0,00	0,00	33,33	11,11	0,00	30,33
Scientific magazines	41,69	45,73	100,00	40,00	33,33	22,22	28,57	43,54
Scientific books	35,27	36,85	100,00	60,00	66,67	22,22	14,29	36,03
Universities	37,23	38,92	100,00	40,00	66,67	22,22	14,29	37,99
Websites	29,78	32,78	0,00	0,00	33,33	33,33	28,57	31,17
Others	1,10	1,08	0,00	20,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	1,12
None	8,86	9,79	0,00	20,00	0,00	44,44	14,29	9,46
I do not know	10,42	6,56	0,00	0,00	0,00	11,11	28,57	8,58
Prefer not to answer	0,31	0,25	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,28

If we look closer to these data, taking into account the vulnerable gender groups, we see that the total proportion of LGBTI+ individuals who do not know any initiative is 31.37%. The analysis by interactions shows slightly lower percentages. In the case of members of the LGBTI+ community who changed their mind about science because something happened to them, the

proportion of respondents who do not know any initiative is 20.00% and among those who follow a scientific person on social media is a 27.78%. This, way, the most common initiative known by LGBTI+ participants were scientific books and websites in the first interaction (26.67% each) and scientific books in the second (44.44%).

Table 5.44. Percentage of respondents who answered “YES” to the question “Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science” according to their answers to the question “What kind of initiative do you know that helps distinguish scientific evidence from educational hoaxes well?”, by vulnerable gender groups.

	Woman	LGBTI+	Prefer not to answer	Total
Initiative through the news	24,66	13,33	24,57	24,66
Applications (apps)	9,50	0,00	9,81	9,50
Online platforms	26,30	6,67	26,33	26,30
Scientific magazines	39,06	20,00	39,50	39,06
Scientific books	31,48	26,67	32,62	31,48
Universities	31,19	13,33	32,73	31,19
Websites	26,39	26,67	28,46	26,39
Others	1,06	0,00	1,28	1,06
None	11,23	20,00	10,93	11,23
I do not know	11,04	26,67	9,91	11,04
Prefer not to answer	0,29	0,00	0,43	0,29

Table 5.45. Percentage of respondents who answered “YES” to the question “Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?” according to their answers to the question “What kind of initiative do you know that helps distinguish scientific evidence from educational hoaxes well?”, by vulnerable gender groups.

	Woman	LGBTI+	Prefer not to answer	Total
Initiative through the news	24,45	11,11	14,29	23,78
Applications (apps)	9,40	5,56	0,00	9,82
Online platforms	29,39	11,11	0,00	30,33
Scientific magazines	41,69	33,33	28,57	43,54
Scientific books	35,27	44,44	14,29	36,03
Universities	37,23	38,89	14,29	37,99
Websites	29,78	22,22	28,57	31,17
Others	1,10	5,56	0,00	1,12
None	8,86	27,78	14,29	9,46
I do not know	10,42	5,56	28,57	8,58
Prefer not to answer	0,31	0,00	0,00	0,28

Regarding youth, the results point out that, while the total proportion of youth aged between 16 and 34 who do not know any initiative to distinguish scientific evidence from hoax ranges from 10.82% in 16-24 years old to 12.69% in 25-34 years old, among youth with interactions with science the percentage is lower. This way, among youth who changed their mind about science because something happened to them or their families, the percentage of those who do not know any initiative is 6.60% in youth 16-24 and 7.39% in youth 25-34. In the same line, the results among youth who follow a scientific person in social networks indicate that only 6.14% and 7.88% of youth aged 16-24 and 25-34 do not know any initiative to distinguish scientific evidence on education from hoaxes. As happened in other questions, the percentage of respondents who do not know any initiative increases across age groups. In both interaction, universities are the most known initiative in the case of 16–24-year-old youth (35.57%) and scientific magazines in the case of 25-34-year-old youth (32.12%).

Table 5.46. Percentage of respondents who answered “YES” to the question “Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or

become interested in science” according to their answers to the question “What kind of initiative do you know that helps distinguish scientific evidence from educational hoaxes well?”, by age groups.

	16-24	25-34	35-49	50-64	+65	Total
Initiative through the news	23,86	21,18	24,79	25,11	29,34	24,57
Applications (apps)	14,21	13,79	10,46	6,85	3,31	9,81
Online platforms	33,50	30,30	29,34	23,29	11,98	26,33
Scientific magazines	31,98	38,92	41,65	41,78	37,19	39,50
Scientific books	34,01	35,96	34,06	29,00	28,93	32,62
Universities	36,04	36,45	35,08	29,45	23,97	32,73
Websites	31,98	36,21	29,68	23,06	19,42	28,46
Others	0,00	1,23	1,01	1,60	2,48	1,28
None	6,60	7,39	9,44	14,16	18,18	10,93
I do not know	6,09	8,13	9,95	11,87	12,40	9,91
Prefer not to answer	0,51	0,49	0,34	0,23	0,83	0,43

Table 5.47. Percentage of respondents who answered “YES” to the question “Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?” according to their answers to the question “What kind of initiative do you know that helps distinguish scientific evidence from educational hoaxes well?”, by age groups.

	16-24	25-34	35-49	50-64	+65	Total
Initiative through the news	25,26	19,23	25,70	24,67	23,82	23,78
Applications (apps)	15,70	12,64	10,18	6,88	3,45	9,82

Online platforms	36,86	34,62	31,15	27,34	19,75	30,33
Scientific magazines	37,54	41,94	43,64	48,18	43,89	43,54
Scientific books	38,57	36,63	35,76	36,33	32,92	36,03
Universities	44,71	39,56	36,00	37,86	34,48	37,99
Websites	33,45	38,64	31,88	26,39	22,26	31,17
Others	0,00	0,73	1,09	1,53	2,19	1,12
None	6,14	7,88	8,24	12,43	13,48	9,46
I do not know	5,46	6,04	9,94	10,13	9,72	8,58
Prefer not to answer	0,00	0,55	0,36	0,00	0,31	0,28

The results by low socioeconomic status also indicate that although 17.31% of the total of respondents from low SES did not know any initiative to distinguish scientific evidence on education from hoax, interactions with science contribute to lower this proportion. In this case, among people who changed their mind about science because something happened to them, the proportion of those from low socioeconomic status who did not know any initiative was 7.85%. In the same line, among those who follow a scientific person on social media the percentage was more than ten points lower than the that in people without interactions with science (6.61%). The most known initiative were in both cases scientific magazines with nearly 4 out of ten of the respondents (37.46% in the first interaction and 40.77% in the second).

Table 5.48. Percentage of respondents who answered “YES” to the question “Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science” according to their answers to the question “What kind of initiative do you know that helps distinguish scientific evidence from educational hoaxes well?”, by low level of SES.

	SES (level 2 and below)
Initiative through the news	25,23
Applications (apps)	13,14

Online platforms	31,42
Scientific magazines	37,46
Scientific books	32,48
Universities	32,63
Websites	31,57
Others	1,36
None	7,85
I do not know	9,67
Prefer not to answer	0,15

Table 5.49. Percentage of respondents who answered “YES” to the question “Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?” according to their answers to the question “What kind of initiative do you know that helps distinguish scientific evidence from educational hoaxes well?”, by low level of SES.

	SES (level 2 and below)
Initiative through the news	23,82
Applications (apps)	12,59
Online platforms	33,79
Scientific magazines	40,77
Scientific books	36,03
Universities	38,03
Websites	32,42

Others	0,87
None	6,61
I do not know	7,86
Prefer not to answer	0,37

Similar trends were found when looking at data for belonging to an ethnic minority group. In this case, among respondents who expressed that something happened to them that made them change their mind about science, the proportion of those from ethnic minorities who did not know any initiative was 5.08%. Also among respondents who follow a scientific person in social media, only 4.56% of individuals from ethnic minorities did not know any initiative. The proportion of people who did not know any initiative among the total of respondents from ethnic minority groups was 9.56%. Regarding the most known initiative among people from ethnic minorities with previous interactions with science, websites were the most selected initiative (32.42% in the first interaction and 35.36% in the second).

Table 5.50. Percentage of respondents who answered “YES” to the question “Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science” according to their answers to the question “What kind of initiative do you know that helps distinguish scientific evidence from educational hoaxes well?”, for belonging to ethnic minorities.

Ethnic minority group	Yes	No	I do not know	I prefer not to answer	Total
Initiative through the news	28,52	24,22	22,11	7,14	24,57
Applications (apps)	25,00	7,61	5,26	0,00	9,81
Online platforms	32,03	25,88	22,11	0,00	26,33
Scientific magazines	30,47	42,16	26,32	7,14	39,50
Scientific books	30,08	34,02	20,00	14,29	32,62
Universities	31,64	33,95	18,95	14,29	32,73
Websites	32,42	27,93	28,42	14,29	28,46

Others	0,00	1,52	1,05	0,00	1,28
None	5,08	12,31	4,21	14,29	10,93
I do not know	4,30	9,93	20,00	42,86	9,91
Prefer not to answer	0,00	0,40	2,11	0,00	0,43

Table 5.51. Percentage of respondents who answered “YES” to the question “Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?” according to their answers to the question “What kind of initiative do you know that helps distinguish scientific evidence from educational hoaxes well?”, for belonging to ethnic minorities.

Ethnic minority group	Yes	No	I do not know	I prefer not to answer	Total
Initiative through the news	27,00	23,67	18,37	18,75	23,78
Applications (apps)	23,95	8,13	8,16	12,50	9,82
Online platforms	32,70	30,20	30,61	6,25	30,33
Scientific magazines	32,70	45,51	34,69	12,50	43,54
Scientific books	34,22	36,78	29,59	6,25	36,03
Universities	33,46	39,64	20,41	0,00	37,99
Websites	35,36	30,95	28,57	6,25	31,17
Others	0,00	1,27	1,02	0,00	1,12
None	4,56	10,00	8,16	25,00	9,46
I do not know	3,42	8,92	12,24	25,00	8,58
Prefer not to answer	0,00	0,28	0,00	6,25	0,28

Finally, the analysis by belonging to religious minority groups also points to this trend. The proportion of respondents who did not know any initiative to distinguish evidence and hoax was 12.87% among people from religious minority groups. On the contrary, among people who changed their mind about science because something happened to them, only 7.07% did not know any initiative. Among those who follow a scientist on social media, the proportion of respondents from religious minorities who did not know any initiative was lower even (5.50%). In the first case, the most known initiatives were online platforms and websites (with 34.28% each) and in the second, scientific magazines (38.23%).

Table 5.52. Percentage of respondents who answered “YES” to the question “Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science” according to their answers to the question “What kind of initiative do you know that helps distinguish scientific evidence from educational hoaxes well?”, for belonging to religious minorities.

Religious minority group	Yes	No	I do not know	I prefer not to answer	Total
Initiative through the news	27,21	24,16	26,56	7,14	24,57
Applications (apps)	22,61	7,59	7,81	0,00	9,81
Online platforms	34,28	25,21	20,31	14,29	26,33
Scientific magazines	33,57	41,32	18,75	57,14	39,50
Scientific books	32,16	33,14	23,44	28,57	32,62
Universities	31,80	33,73	14,06	28,57	32,73
Websites	34,28	27,33	28,13	35,71	28,46
Others	0,71	1,45	0,00	0,00	1,28
None	7,07	11,75	10,94	0,00	10,93
I do not know	4,95	10,43	17,19	21,43	9,91
Prefer not to answer	0,35	0,46	0,00	0,00	0,43

Table 53. Percentage of respondents who answered “YES” to the question “Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?”

according to their answers to the question “What kind of initiative do you know that helps distinguish scientific evidence from educational hoaxes well?”, for belonging to religious minorities.

Religious minority group	Yes	No	I do not know	I prefer not to answer	Total
Initiative through the news	25,69	23,69	21,88	5,88	23,78
Applications (apps)	21,10	8,15	9,38	0,00	9,82
Online platforms	35,78	29,74	26,56	11,76	30,33
Scientific magazines	38,23	44,71	35,94	29,41	43,54
Scientific books	36,09	36,42	32,81	0,00	36,03
Universities	37,31	38,85	20,31	11,76	37,99
Websites	35,78	30,79	23,44	17,65	31,17
Others	0,92	1,19	0,00	0,00	1,12
None	5,50	10,10	4,69	23,53	9,46
I do not know	3,98	8,96	17,19	17,65	8,58
Prefer not to answer	0,00	0,29	0,00	5,88	0,28

Therefore, in all cases the results show that when citizens from vulnerable groups have interactions with science, they tend to know initiatives to distinguish scientific evidence on education from hoaxes. Among the most known initiatives, we highlight scientific magazines.

5.2.3. Analysis of the questions related to gender

To analyze citizens’ awareness of the impact of scientific research in gender we have introduced two questions in the questionnaire:

- Have you received any information on results of gender research published in scientific journals, from any initiative launched through the media/communication tools that I am going to read?
- What kind of initiative do you know that helps distinguish scientific evidence from gender hoaxes well?

In both cases, several response options are provided to participants and include the following communication tools: post mail, e-mail, phones, SMS/Text message, video conference and web conference, social networks, G Suite and Microsoft 365/Office and online Collaboration/Productivity Tools and the following initiatives: news, applications (apps), online platforms, scientific journals, scientific books, universities and web pages.

Question 1

Regarding the question “Have you received any information on results of gender research published in scientific journals, from any initiative launched through the media/communication tools that I am going to read?”, we can see almost half of the respondents (47.2%) of the responders have not received information of scientific research on education from any of the communication tools. However, 14.1% of the respondents received this information from social networks.

Table 5.54. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence “Have you received any information on results of gender research published in scientific journals such as Harvard, Cambridge or others, from any initiative launched through the following media/communication tools?”.

	Frequency	Percentage	Accumulated percentage
Post mail	263	2,9%	2,9%
E-mail	762	8,3%	11,2%
Phones	406	4,4%	15,6%
SMS/Text message	269	2,9%	18,6%
Video conference and web conference	302	3,3%	21,9%
Social networks	1290	14,1%	36,0%
G Suite and Microsoft 365/Office	194	2,1%	38,1%
Online Collaboration/Productivity Tools	356	3,9%	42,0%
Others	79	0,9%	42,9%
None	4317	47,2%	90,1%
I do not know	828	9,1%	99,1%
I prefer not to answer	82	0,9%	100,0%
TOTAL	9148	100,0%	100,0%

The response of people from vulnerable groups

As we have seen, more than half of participants had not received information about results of scientific research on gender from any communication tool and the most common communication tool from which participants had received information about these results were social networks. If we look at possible differences across vulnerable groups, we see that, in general, this is not the case.

For example, if we analyse the differences by gender, we can see that more than half of the men and women (57.57% of men and 57.61% of women) had not received any information about scientific research on gender, which implies that the variable “sex” has no influence in receiving information about the results of scientific research in gender. In addition, in both cases the most selected communication tool were social networks (17.33% of women and 17.16% of men), while the least selected was G Suite and Microsoft 365/Office (2.62% of women and 2.52% of men)

Table 5.55. Percentage of respondents according to their answers to the question “Have you received any information on results of gender research published in scientific journals such as Harvard, Cambridge or others, from any initiative launched through the following media/communication tools?”, by gender.

	Woman	Man	Trans	Non binary	Fluid	Others	Prefer not to answer	Total
Post mail	3,01	4,05	14,29	8,33	0,00	0,00	0,00	3,50
E-mail	8,99	11,50	28,57	0,00	0,00	3,85	3,03	10,15
Phones	5,09	5,85	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	3,03	5,41
SMS/Text message	3,25	3,94	0,00	16,67	0,00	3,85	0,00	3,58
Video conference and web conference	3,59	4,38	14,29	16,67	16,67	3,85	6,06	4,02
Social networks	17,33	17,16	14,29	16,67	50,00	7,69	6,06	17,18
G Suite and Microsoft 365/Office	2,62	2,52	0,00	8,33	16,67	0,00	3,03	2,58

Online Collaboration/ Productivity Tools	4,59	4,96	0,00	16,67	0,00	0,00	0,00	4,74
Others	1,13	0,97	0,00	0,00	0,00	3,85	0,00	1,05
None	57,61	57,57	28,57	25,00	33,33	69,23	51,52	57,51
I do not know	11,72	10,14	14,29	25,00	0,00	15,38	21,21	11,03
prefer not to answer	1,13	0,97	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	12,12	1,09

If we focus on the gender vulnerable groups, we can observe the percentage of participants from the LGBTIQ had not received information about results of gender research was slightly lower (49.02%), compared with the total of participants (57.51%).

Table 5.56. Percentage of respondents according to their answers to the question “Have you received any information on results of educational research published in scientific journals such as Harvard, Cambridge or others, from any initiative launched through the following media/communication tools?”, by vulnerable gender groups.

	Woman	LGBTI+	Prefer not to answer
Post mail	3,01	3,92	0,00
E-mail	8,99	5,88	3,03
Phones	5,09	0,00	3,03
SMS/Text message	3,25	5,88	0,00
Video conference and web conference	3,59	9,80	6,06
Social networks	17,33	15,69	6,06
G Suite and Microsoft 365/Office	2,62	3,92	3,03
Online Collaboration/ Productivity Tools	4,59	3,92	0,00
Others	1,13	1,96	0,00

None	57,61	49,02	51,52
I do not know	11,72	15,69	21,21
prefer not to answer	1,13	0,00	12,12

The following is an analysis of the response by the age of respondents:

Table 5.57. Percentage of respondents according to their answers to the question “Have you received any information on results of gender research published in scientific journals such as Harvard, Cambridge or others, from any initiative launched through the following media/communication tools?”, by age groups.

	16-24	25-34	35-49	50-64	+65	Total
Post mail	5,84	5,00	3,98	2,76	1,32	3,50
E-mail	16,67	16,10	9,94	7,36	6,17	10,15
Phones	10,31	9,83	5,12	2,71	3,52	5,41
SMS/Text message	6,87	5,95	3,98	2,03	1,47	3,58
Video conference and web conference	6,53	6,58	4,36	2,50	2,13	4,02
Social networks	24,74	23,79	17,57	13,35	12,56	17,18
G Suite and Microsoft 365/Office	5,15	4,76	2,98	1,41	0,44	2,58
Online Collaboration/ Productivity Tools	5,50	8,41	5,24	3,50	1,91	4,74
Others	0,69	0,48	0,80	1,15	2,06	1,05
None	38,83	42,51	56,31	65,94	69,60	57,51
I do not know	9,11	11,58	12,49	10,64	9,32	11,03
prefer not to answer	1,55	1,27	1,05	1,25	0,59	1,09

In this analysis we can see how the proportion of youth (participants aged 16-34), who had not received information about scientific research on gender is lower (38.83% for respondents aged 16-24 and 42.51% for those aged 25-34) than the rest of the age groups. In this line, the percentage of participants who received information about scientific research on gender decreases with the age of the participants. In addition, a higher proportion of youth (between 24.74% and 23.79%) received this type of information from social networks.

Regarding participants from low SES group, which includes a gross income below 16043€ per year, the results show that approximately half of the respondents from low SES (52.09%) had not received information about gender research from any communication tool, compared with the 57.51% of the total. Most of the respondents who had received this information, expressed that they had received it through social networks (20.17%) and e-mail (12.33%).

Table 5.58. Percentage of respondents according to their answers to the question “Have you received any information on results of gender research published in scientific journals such as Harvard, Cambridge or others, from any initiative launched through the following media/communication tools?”, by low level of SES¹².

	Low SES	Total
Post mail	5,02	3,50
E-mail	12,33	10,15
Phones	7,09	5,41
SMS/Text message	4,67	3,58
Video conference and web conference	4,84	4,02
Social networks	20,17	17,18
G Suite and Microsoft 365/Office	3,70	2,58
Online Collaboration/ Productivity Tools	6,21	4,74
Others	0,97	1,05

¹² Low SES is defined as having gross income below 16,043 Euros per year.

None	52,09	57,51
I do not know	10,57	11,03
prefer not to answer	0,88	1,09

When analysing the results taking into account ethnic minorities, we observe that less people from ethnic minorities expressed not having received information about research on gender. Specifically, we can observe that 31.55% of respondents from ethnic minorities had not received any information about gender research, while the proportion in people who do not belong to ethnic minority groups was 61.41%. The most reported communication tools in which respondents from ethnic minorities had received this information were social networks (28.11%), and by e-mail (20.65%) and the least reported was G Suite and Microsoft 365/Office (11.28%).

Table 5.59. Percentage of respondents according to their answers to the question “Have you received any information on results of gender research published in scientific journals such as Harvard, Cambridge or others, from any initiative launched through the following media/communication tools?”, for belonging to an ethnic minority group.

	Yes	No	I do not know	I prefer not to answer	Total
Post mail	13,00	2,62	4,74	4,90	3,50
E-mail	20,65	9,46	9,03	4,90	10,15
Phones	17,78	4,41	5,42	4,90	5,41
SMS/Text message	12,81	2,73	4,51	5,88	3,58
Video conference and web conference	12,43	3,18	5,87	5,88	4,02
Social networks	28,11	16,52	16,70	4,90	17,18
G Suite and Microsoft 365/Office	11,28	1,80	3,84	1,96	2,58
Online Collaboration/ Productivity Tools	13,77	3,90	6,77	2,94	4,74

Others	0,19	1,18	0,45	0,00	1,05
None	31,55	61,41	35,89	38,24	57,51
I do not know	7,46	10,13	27,09	16,67	11,03
prefer not to answer	0,19	0,76	2,03	22,55	1,09
Total	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

The same trend is observed in the analysis by religious minorities and 34.73% of the respondents had never received information about results from gender research. Among those who had received this information, the most common communication tools were social networks (27.77%) and e-mail (19.53%).

Table 5.60. Percentage of respondents according to their answers to the question “Have you received any information on results of gender research published in scientific journals such as Harvard, Cambridge or others, from any initiative launched through the following media/communication tools?”, for belonging to a religious minority group.

	Yes	No	I do not know	I prefer not to answer	Total
Post mail	10,08	2,76	5,18	3,26	3,50
E-mail	19,53	9,45	7,93	1,09	10,15
Phones	16,28	4,32	6,40	2,17	5,41
SMS/Text message	11,94	2,76	3,66	2,17	3,58
Video conference and web conference	10,70	3,40	2,74	5,43	4,02
Social networks	27,75	16,47	13,41	6,52	17,18
G Suite and Microsoft 365/Office	8,68	1,97	3,35	0,00	2,58
Online Collaboration/ Productivity Tools	11,32	4,13	4,57	2,17	4,74

Others	0,47	1,15	0,61	0,00	1,05
None	34,73	60,99	36,89	46,74	57,51
I do not know	7,91	10,42	28,35	14,13	11,03
prefer not to answer	0,62	0,78	2,44	21,74	1,09

In addition, although participants from religious minorities were the 8.59% of the total of respondents, they represented between 13.88% and 28.87% of the respondents who received information about gender research from all communicative tools.

Table 5.61. Percentage of respondents according to their answers to the question “Have you received any information on results of gender research published in scientific journals such as Harvard, Cambridge or others, from any initiative launched through the following media/communication tools?”, by religious minority and communication tools.

	Post mail	E-mail	phones	SMS/ Text message	Video conference web conference	Social networks	G Suite and Microsoft 365/Office	Online Collaboration Productivity Tools	Other	None	TOTAL
Yes	24,71	16,54	25,86	28,62	22,85	13,88	28,87	20,51	3,80	5,19	8,59
No	67,68	79,92	68,47	66,17	72,52	82,25	65,46	74,72	93,67	91,01	85,81
I do not know	6,46	3,41	5,17	4,46	2,98	3,41	5,67	4,21	2,53	2,80	4,37
Prefer not to answer	1,14	0,13	0,49	0,74	1,66	0,47	0,00	0,56	0,00	1,00	1,23

THE IMPACT OF INTERACTIONS

The objective of this section is to analyse whether the interactions of respondents from vulnerable with science have an impact on receiving or not information about scientific research on gender. We analyse the interactions through two questions:

- Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?

- Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?

Analysis of question 1: Have you received any information on results of gender research published in scientific journals, from any initiative launched through the media/communication tools that I am going to read?"

Among women who responded that something happened to her or her family that made her change her mind about science, the proportion of women who had not received information about gender research was lower (48,27% compared with the 57.61% of the total of women). Also in this case, social networks were the communication tool most used to receive information, with a total of 26.39% of responses from women with interactions with science (compared with 17.33% of the total of women).

Table 5.62. Percentage of respondents who answered "YES" to the question "Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science" by gender.

	Woman	Man	Non binary	Fluid	Others	Prefer not to answer	Total
Post mail	4,80	7,69	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	6,02
E-mail	13,24	19,66	0,00	0,00	20,00	0,00	15,99
Phones	9,02	11,48	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	10,02
SMS/Text message	6,43	9,16	0,00	0,00	20,00	0,00	7,62
Video conference and web conference	5,85	9,65	16,67	0,00	20,00	33,33	7,62
Social networks	26,39	27,96	33,33	100,00	40,00	0,00	27,13
G Suite and Microsoft 365/Office	4,80	6,11	16,67	0,00	0,00	0,00	5,38
Online Collaboration/Productivity Tools	7,68	10,99	33,33	0,00	0,00	0,00	9,17
Others	1,06	0,98	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	1,01
None	48,27	41,39	16,67	0,00	20,00	33,33	45,04

I do not know	8,06	6,84	16,67	0,00	20,00	33,33	7,62
Prefer not to answer	0,67	0,85	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,75

Among women who responded that something happened to her or her family that made her change her mind about science, the proportion of women who had not received information about gender research was lower (48,27% compared with the 57.61% of the total of women). Also in this case, social networks were the communication tool most used to receive information, with a total of 26.39% of responses from women with interactions with science (compared with 17.33% of the total of women).

Table 5.63. Percentage of respondents who answered “YES” to the question “Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?” by gender.

	Woman	Man	Trans	Non binary	Fluid	Others	Prefer not to answer	Total
Post mail	5,09	6,72	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	5,83
E-mail	13,64	19,83	0,00	0,00	0,00	11,11	0,00	16,52
Phones	8,23	9,38	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	14,29	8,74
SMS/Text message	5,49	6,22	0,00	0,00	0,00	11,11	0,00	5,83
Video conference and web conference	6,90	8,46	0,00	20,00	0,00	11,11	14,29	7,70
Social networks	29,47	29,21	0,00	20,00	66,67	11,11	28,57	29,29
G Suite and Microsoft 365/Office	3,92	4,48	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	4,15
Online Collaboration/Productivity Tools	7,68	9,29	0,00	20,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	8,42
Others	2,27	1,16	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	1,72
None	45,38	41,91	100,00	40,00	33,33	66,67	14,29	43,70

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

I do not know	7,68	7,55	0,00	20,00	0,00	11,11	28,57	7,70
Prefer not to answer	0,71	0,75	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	14,29	0,76

As we have seen the proportion of youth participants who had not received information about scientific research on gender is lower than older participants (38.83% for respondents aged 16-24 and 42.51% for those aged 25-34). At the same time, the percentage of participants who not received information about scientific research on gender increases with the age. Among the youth people, a higher proportion received information from social networks, but lower than the 25%. If we attend to the data regarding interactions, the proportion of youth participants who asked positively to the question “Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?” increases the positive answer to have received information of gender research. In this case, participants aged between 16-24 and 25-34 reach 31,47% and 33,24% respectively on the option social networks. The proportion of participants who answer negatively to the reception of information regarding gender research also decreases when they show interactions.

Table 5.64. Percentage of respondents who answered “YES” to the question “Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science” by group of age.

	16-24	25-34	35-49	50-64	+65	Total
Post mail	7,11	7,39	7,42	4,57	2,07	6,02
E-mail	20,81	22,17	15,68	12,10	9,50	15,99
Phones	16,24	15,27	9,78	5,94	4,13	10,02
SMS/Text message	11,68	9,11	9,11	4,79	3,31	7,62
Video conference and web conference	10,15	11,82	7,25	5,25	3,72	7,62
Social networks	31,47	33,25	30,19	19,63	19,42	27,13
G Suite and Microsoft 365/Office	7,61	7,14	7,93	2,28	0,00	5,38
Online Collaboration/Productivity Tools	9,14	13,05	11,47	5,48	3,72	9,17
Others	1,52	0,49	1,18	0,91	1,24	1,01
None	34,52	30,54	43,34	57,31	59,92	45,04
I do not know	3,55	8,87	7,08	8,68	8,26	7,62
Prefer not to answer	0,00	0,74	0,84	0,68	1,24	0,75

The proportions regarding the participants who answer positively the second question regarding interactions (among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?) is very similar. The pattern of responses is similar. The percentage of participants who have not received information on gender research increases gradually with age. Similarly, the percentage of young people who respond that they access information about gender research through social networks increases with interactions.

Table 5.65. Percentage of respondents who answered “YES” to the question “Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?” by group age.

	16-24	25-34	35-49	50-64	+65	Total
Post mail	7,51	7,51	6,42	4,78	1,57	5,83
E-mail	18,77	22,16	15,76	12,62	13,17	16,52
Phones	10,92	12,82	8,61	4,97	6,27	8,74
SMS/Text message	6,83	8,06	6,30	4,02	2,82	5,83
Video conference and web conference	7,85	9,89	8,00	6,31	5,33	7,70
Social networks	31,06	31,32	30,42	24,67	28,84	29,29
G Suite and Microsoft 365/Office	6,14	5,31	4,48	3,44	0,63	4,15
Online Collaboration/Productivity Tools	6,48	11,36	9,94	6,88	3,76	8,42
Others	1,37	0,55	1,09	2,87	3,76	1,72
None	33,79	35,16	44,61	52,20	51,10	43,70
I do not know	7,17	8,06	8,48	7,46	5,96	7,70
Prefer not to answer	0,34	0,73	0,61	1,34	0,63	0,76

Among the participants belonging to ethnic minority groups who responded affirmatively to the question about being interested in science, 22.27% said that they had received information. Social networks, with 30.47%, continue to be the most popular means of obtaining information. Without taking interactions into account, 61.41% of people did not receive information; this percentage decreases to 50.56% when interactions are considered.

Table 5.66. Percentage of respondents who answered “YES” to the question “Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science” by ethnic minority group.

	Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	Total

Post mail	17,58	4,04	6,32	7,14	6,02
E-mail	27,73	14,10	14,74	14,29	15,99
Phones	26,17	7,54	7,37	0,00	10,02
SMS/Text message	19,14	5,56	9,47	7,14	7,62
Video conference and web conference	16,41	6,15	8,42	0,00	7,62
Social networks	30,47	26,27	32,63	21,43	27,13
G Suite and Microsoft 365/Office	14,45	3,71	8,42	0,00	5,38
Online Collaboration/Productivity Tools	17,58	7,41	15,79	0,00	9,17
Others	0,39	1,13	1,05	0,00	1,01
None	22,27	50,56	21,05	28,57	45,04
I do not know	5,47	7,21	17,89	21,43	7,62
Prefer not to answer	0,39	0,73	1,05	7,14	0,75

Of those who responded affirmatively to the question about following scientists or people interested in science, the percentage who said they had not received information about gender research decreased from 61.41% to 47.58%. The percentage of people who have received information through social networks remains high at 36.5%.

Table 5.67. Percentage of respondents who answered “YES” to the question “Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?” by ethnic minority group.

	Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	Total
Post mail	19,77	4,18	4,08	6,25	5,83

E-mail	27,76	15,31	13,27	12,50	16,52
Phones	23,57	6,76	12,24	6,25	8,74
SMS/Text message	17,49	4,23	9,18	6,25	5,83
Video conference and web conference	18,25	6,20	11,22	12,50	7,70
Social networks	36,50	28,46	31,63	6,25	29,29
G Suite and Microsoft 365/Office	13,69	2,82	7,14	6,25	4,15
Online Collaboration/Productivity Tools	17,87	6,90	16,33	6,25	8,42
Others	0,38	1,93	1,02	0,00	1,72
None	17,11	47,58	31,63	37,50	43,70
I do not know	4,56	7,89	11,22	12,50	7,70
Prefer not to answer	0,38	0,75	0,00	12,50	0,76

The same trend is observed in the analysis by religious minorities. Among those who had received this information, the most common communication tools were social networks (27.77%) and e-mail (19.53%). Considering the first question regarding interactions (Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?), these percentages increase to 31.8% and 25.09% respectively. Finally, the same percentages continue their increase if we consider the second question regarding interactions (35.17% and 25.38% respectively). At the same time, respondents who express don't receive information decreases from 60.99% to a 49.57% (considering the first question on interactions) and to a 47.14% considering the second one (Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?).

Table 5.68. Percentage of respondents who answered "YES" to the question "Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science" for belonging to a religious minority group.

	Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	Total
Post mail	14,13	4,29	10,94	7,14	6,02
E-mail	25,09	14,39	17,19	0,00	15,99
Phones	25,09	7,26	9,38	7,14	10,02
SMS/Text message	19,79	5,35	9,38	0,00	7,62
Video conference and web conference	15,90	6,34	1,56	7,14	7,62
Social networks	31,80	26,40	25,00	21,43	27,13
G Suite and Microsoft 365/Office	13,07	4,03	4,69	0,00	5,38
Online Collaboration/Productivity Tools	18,73	7,39	10,94	0,00	9,17
Others	0,00	1,19	1,56	0,00	1,01
None	24,03	49,57	31,25	42,86	45,04
I do not know	5,30	7,72	10,94	28,57	7,62
Prefer not to answer	1,06	0,73	0,00	0,00	0,75

Table 5.69. Percentage of respondents who answered “YES” to the question “Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?” for belonging to a religious minority group.

	Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	Total
Post mail	14,68	4,29	9,38	11,76	5,83
E-mail	25,38	15,25	17,19	0,00	16,52

Phones	21,41	6,67	14,06	0,00	8,74
SMS/Text message	16,21	4,10	10,94	0,00	5,83
Video conference and web conference	15,60	6,53	3,13	17,65	7,70
Social networks	35,17	28,74	20,31	17,65	29,29
G Suite and Microsoft 365/Office	11,01	3,10	4,69	0,00	4,15
Online Collaboration/Productivity Tools	14,98	7,34	10,94	5,88	8,42
Others	0,61	1,95	0,00	0,00	1,72
None	23,55	47,14	32,81	47,06	43,70
I do not know	6,12	7,77	12,50	11,76	7,70
Prefer not to answer	0,61	0,76	0,00	5,88	0,76

Regarding household annual income it is important to highlight how 49.52% of the respondents who affirmatively answer the question “has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?”, prefer not to answer to the question about the reception of information on results of gender research by media. The same percentage is also very high, 47.15%, in the case of the respondents to the second question on interactions (see table below). In both tables below, the main way to access information by household income is social networks. People under 10,562€ uses mainly social networks (25.47%) and from 10,562€-16,043€ the percentage increases to 30.03%.

Table 5.70. Percentage of respondents who answered “YES” to the question “Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?” by household annual income in Euros.

	Less than 10,562	10.562-16.043	16.044-23.295	More than 23.295	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	Total
Post mail	7,32	8,87	6,73	4,43	1,43	4,81	6,02

E-mail	17,89	18,09	13,46	17,24	12,86	11,06	15,99
Phones	10,84	13,99	11,01	8,54	7,14	6,73	10,02
SMS/Text message	7,32	11,60	8,56	7,06	1,43	4,81	7,62
Video conference and web conference	6,23	10,58	9,17	7,39	1,43	6,25	7,62
Social networks	25,47	30,03	28,75	26,27	28,57	25,48	27,13
G Suite and Microsoft 365/Office	4,61	8,53	6,73	4,76	1,43	3,37	5,38
Online Collaboration/Productivity Tools	8,94	12,97	7,34	10,34	5,71	4,81	9,17
Others	0,81	1,71	0,61	0,66	0,00	2,40	1,01
None	42,28	37,20	44,04	49,43	45,71	49,52	45,04
I do not know	11,11	3,75	6,12	7,55	10,00	8,65	7,62
Prefer not to answer	1,36	0,34	0,92	0,66	0,00	0,48	0,75

Table 5.71. Percentage of respondents who answered “YES” to the question “Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?” by household annual income in euros.

	Less than 10.562	10.562-16.043	16.044-23.295	More than 23.295	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	Total
Post mail	8,14	8,60	6,72	3,97	5,21	3,80	5,83
E-mail	18,14	18,55	17,57	16,28	16,67	10,27	16,52
Phones	10,23	11,83	8,79	7,93	7,29	5,32	8,74

SMS/Text message	6,74	8,60	7,49	4,59	2,08	3,80	5,83
Video conference and web conference	6,98	10,48	9,56	6,89	4,17	6,46	7,70
Social networks	32,79	31,99	33,59	27,04	23,96	23,57	29,29
G Suite and Microsoft 365/Office	5,35	8,33	4,39	2,71	1,04	2,28	4,15
Online Collaboration/Productivity Tools	7,91	13,44	10,34	7,62	4,17	3,80	8,42
Others	1,86	1,88	1,55	1,36	1,04	3,04	1,72
None	36,51	38,44	39,28	49,37	47,92	47,15	43,70
I do not know	8,84	4,03	5,68	7,41	13,54	12,93	7,70
Prefer not to answer	0,93	0,27	0,78	0,52	0,00	2,28	0,76

Question 2

Regarding the question “What kind of initiative do you know that helps distinguish scientific evidence from gender hoaxes well?” we can see that 77.2% of the participants knew at least one initiative to distinguish scientific evidence from hoax. The most commonly initiatives identified by respondents were scientific magazines (15.7%), followed by universities (13.5%) and the less common were applications (3.6%). Finally, 13.5% of the respondents admitted not knowing any initiative to distinguish gender scientific evidence from hoaxes.

Table 5.72. Distribution of respondents' answers to the following sentence “What kind of initiative do you know that helps distinguish scientific evidence from gender hoaxes well?”

	Frequency	Percentage	Accumulated percentage
Initiative through the news	1425	10,7%	10,7%
Applications (apps)	476	3,6%	14,3%
Online platforms	1339	10,0%	24,3%
Scientific magazines	2087	15,7%	40,0%

Scientific books	1800	13,5%	53,5%
Universities	1653	12,4%	65,9%
Websites	1447	10,9%	76,7%
Others	64	0,5%	77,2%
None	1797	13,5%	90,7%
I do not know	1156	8,7%	99,4%
Prefer not to answer	84	0,6%	100,0%
TOTAL	13328	100,0%	100,0%

The response of people from vulnerable groups

According to the data, almost one-quarter of women respondents 24.90% expressed not knowing any initiative to distinguish gender scientific evidence and hoaxes. A slightly lower percentage was found in the case of men with of 22.89% men. In both cases, scientific magazines were the most common (26.29% in women and 29.13% in men).

Table 5.73. Percentage of respondents according to their answer to the question “What kind of initiative do you know that helps distinguish scientific evidence from gender hoaxes well?”, by gender.

	Woman	Man	Trans	Non binary	Fluid	Others	Prefer not to answer	Total
Initiative through the news	18,37	19,84	14,29	8,33	33,33	15,38	0,00	18,98
Applications (apps)	6,26	6,43	0,00	25,00	16,67	0,00	3,03	6,34
Online platforms	17,17	18,68	57,14	16,67	33,33	7,69	0,00	17,84
Scientific magazines	26,92	29,13	28,57	16,67	33,33	7,69	3,03	27,80
Scientific books	23,15	25,17	28,57	16,67	33,33	7,69	3,03	23,98
Universities	20,89	23,45	0,00	16,67	66,67	3,85	9,09	22,02
Websites	18,03	20,90	0,00	0,00	16,67	3,85	9,09	19,28

Others	0,73	1,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,85
None	24,90	22,89	0,00	25,00	0,00	38,46	24,24	23,94
I do not know	16,64	13,64	14,29	33,33	16,67	34,62	42,42	15,40
Prefer not to answer	1,21	0,94	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	12,12	1,12
TOTAL	100,00							

If we consider vulnerable gender groups, we see that the proportion of LGBTI+ individuals who knew at least one initiative was almost the same as the total (25.49% VS 23.94%). Similar trends were found in those respondents who preferred not to share their gender identity (24.24%). The most common initiative by LGBTI+ respondents were online platforms (19.61%), followed by news, scientific books and magazines, with 15.69% each.

Table 5.74. Percentage of respondents according to their answer to the question “What kind of initiative do you know that helps distinguish scientific evidence from gender hoaxes well?”, by vulnerable gender groups.

	Woman	LGBTI+	Prefer not to answer	Total
Initiative through the news	18,37	15,69	0,00	18,98
Applications (apps)	6,26	7,84	3,03	6,34
Online platforms	17,17	19,61	0,00	17,84
Scientific magazines	26,92	15,69	3,03	27,80
Scientific books	23,15	15,69	3,03	23,98
Universities	20,89	13,73	9,09	22,02
Websites	18,03	3,92	9,09	19,28
Others	0,73	0,00	0,00	0,85
None	24,90	25,49	24,24	23,94

I do not know	16,64	29,41	42,42	15,40
Prefer not to answer	1,21	0,00	12,12	1,12
TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

When deepening in the differences by age groups, the results point out that the proportion of youth aged between 16 and 34 who do not know any initiative to distinguish gender scientific evidence from hoax is lower than in other age groups (14.78% in 16-24 years old and 15.62% in 25-34 years old, compared with the total of 23.94%). In the same line, scientific magazines the most known in both cases (30.24% and 29.98%).

Table 5.75. Percentage of respondents according to their answer to the question “What kind of initiative do you know that helps distinguish scientific evidence from gender hoaxes well?”, by age groups.

	16-24	25-34	35-49	50-64	+65	Total
Initiative through the news	18,73	18,79	17,65	20,03	20,12	18,98
Applications (apps)	14,09	10,63	6,00	4,28	2,57	6,34
Online platforms	24,74	25,38	18,53	14,50	11,38	17,84
Scientific magazines	30,76	29,98	26,29	27,44	27,68	27,80
Scientific books	26,98	26,96	23,48	23,27	21,81	23,98
Universities	30,24	25,61	21,97	20,87	16,89	22,02
Websites	28,87	26,17	20,38	15,49	12,19	19,28
Others	0,34	0,40	0,71	1,20	1,25	0,85
None	14,78	15,62	23,23	28,69	30,10	23,94
I do not know	11,00	13,32	16,77	15,96	16,01	15,40
Prefer not to answer	1,37	1,43	0,96	1,20	0,88	1,12

TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
-------	--------	--------	--------	--------	--------	--------

The analysis of these data across SES points to a similar percentage of respondents who express not knowing any initiative to distinguish between gender scientific evidence and hoaxes (22.10% VS 23.94%). In this case, more than one-quarter of the respondents from low-SES knew scientific magazines (26.60%), followed by scientific books (24.83%) and universities (22.06%).

Table 5.76. Percentage of respondents according to their answer to the question “What kind of initiative do you know that helps distinguish scientific evidence from gender hoaxes well?”, by low level of SES.

	SES (level 2 and below)
Initiative through the news	19,29
Applications (apps)	7,40
Online platforms	19,95
Scientific magazines	26,60
Scientific books	24,83
Universities	22,06
Websites	20,52
Others	0,57
None	22,10
I do not know	14,49
Prefer not to answer	1,06
TOTAL	100,00

In the case of ethnic minorities, we observe a lower proportion of respondents who do not know any initiative to distinguish between gender scientific evidence and hoax (11.47% in comparison with 25.31% of the respondents who answer negatively). In addition, from the participants who

answer positively, approximately three out of ten (31.55%) knew it from scientific magazines and (30.40%) from online platforms.

Table 5.77. Percentage of respondents according to their answers to the question “What kind of initiative do you know that helps distinguish scientific evidence from gender hoaxes well?”, for belonging to an ethnic minority group.

Ethnic minority group	Yes	No	I do not know	I prefer not to answer	Total
Initiative through the news	26,39	19,06	11,96	6,86	18,98
Applications (apps)	16,06	5,61	5,42	6,86	6,34
Online platforms	30,40	17,30	13,32	6,86	17,84
Scientific magazines	31,55	28,48	16,93	12,75	27,80
Scientific books	27,92	24,68	13,09	6,86	23,98
Universities	27,34	22,53	11,74	6,86	22,02
Websites	25,24	19,23	15,35	8,82	19,28
Others	0,38	0,93	0,45	0,00	0,85
None	11,47	25,31	18,51	24,51	23,94
I do not know	8,99	14,75	30,70	22,55	15,40
Prefer not to answer	0,19	0,78	2,03	23,53	1,12
TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

It is also relevant that, although respondents from ethnic minorities were 6.97% of the total, they represented the 17.65% of the total of users who knew applications (apps) and the 11.87% of the respondents who knew online platforms to distinguish scientific evidence on gender from hoaxes.

Table 5.78. Percentage of respondents according to their answers to the question “What kind of initiative do you know that helps distinguish scientific evidence from gender hoaxes well?”, by ethnic minority and communication tools.

	Initiative through news	Apps	Online platforms	Scientific journals	Scientific books	Universities	Web pages	Others	None	TOTAL
Yes	9,68	17,65	11,87	7,91	8,11	8,65	9,12	3,13	3,34	6,97
No	86,11	75,84	83,20	87,88	88,28	87,78	85,56	93,75	90,71	85,77
I do not know	3,72	5,04	4,41	3,59	3,22	3,15	4,70	3,13	4,56	5,90
Prefer not to answer	0,49	1,47	0,52	0,62	0,39	0,42	0,62	0,00	1,39	1,36
	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

Similar results are found in the analysis by religious minorities: people who do not know any initiative to distinguish between scientific evidence and hoax in gender 14.73% in religious minority groups, compared with the 25.05% of the people from non-religious minority groups. In this case, scientific magazines are also the most known initiative (32.71%).

Table 5.79. Percentage of respondents according to their answers to the question “What kind of initiative do you know that helps distinguish scientific evidence from gender hoaxes well?”, for belonging to a religious minority group.

Religious minority group	Yes	No	I do not know	I prefer not to answer	Total
Initiative through the news	23,26	19,09	12,20	5,43	18,98
Applications (apps)	12,87	5,77	5,79	2,17	6,34
Online platforms	27,75	17,31	12,50	4,35	17,84
Scientific magazines	32,71	28,21	14,63	11,96	27,80
Scientific books	27,44	24,40	12,20	11,96	23,98
Universities	26,36	22,32	11,28	8,70	22,02
Websites	24,34	19,28	12,20	8,70	19,28

Others	0,62	0,90	0,61	0,00	0,85
None	14,73	25,05	19,82	25,00	23,94
I do not know	9,46	15,07	31,71	21,74	15,40
Prefer not to answer	0,47	0,81	2,44	22,83	1,12
TOTAL	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

As in the case of ethnic minorities, among all the respondents who knew examples of applications (apps) and online platforms to distinguish gender scientific evidence from hoaxes, respondents from religious minorities represented a 17.44% and a 13.37%:

Table 5.80. Percentage of respondents according to their answers to the question “What kind of initiative do you know that helps distinguish scientific evidence from gender hoaxes well?”, by religious minority and communication tools.

	Initiative through news	Apps	Online platforms	Scientific journals	Scientific books	Universities	Web pages	Others	None	TOTAL
Yes	10,53	17,44	13,37	10,11	9,83	10,28	10,85	6,25	5,29	8,59
No	86,32	78,15	83,27	87,06	87,33	86,99	85,83	90,63	89,82	85,81
I do not know	2,81	3,99	3,06	2,30	2,22	2,24	2,76	3,13	3,62	4,37
Prefer not to answer	0,35	0,42	0,30	0,53	0,61	0,48	0,55	0,00	1,28	1,23
	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

THE IMPACT OF INTERACTIONS

The objective of this section is to analyse whether the interactions of respondents from vulnerable with science have an impact on receiving or not information about scientific research on gender. We analyse the interactions through two questions:

- Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?
- Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?

Analysis of question 2: What kind of initiative do you know that helps distinguish scientific evidence from gender hoaxes well?

Without considering the questions that allow us to assess how the interactions influence the participants, a quarter of the women claimed not to have had access to information on how to differentiate scientific evidence on gender from hoaxes. In the case of men, this percentage was 22.89%. In the positive cases, the primary way of accessing the information was scientific journals (26.29% in women and 29.13% in men). When affirmative answers were given to the question "whether they had changed their perception of science or had become interested in it," the percentages of not having accessed information dropped in women to 14.2% and in men to 14.04%. Likewise, access to information through scientific journals increased to 36.28% in women and 38.34% in men.

Table 5.81. Percentage of respondents who answered "YES" to the question "Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?" by gender.

	Woman	Man	Non binary	Fluid	Others	Prefer not to answer	Total
Initiative through news	24,38	24,05	16,67	0,00	20,00	0,00	24,15
Applications (apps)	11,52	11,84	33,33	0,00	0,00	0,00	11,67
Online platforms	25,82	26,98	16,67	0,00	40,00	0,00	26,28
Scientific journals	36,28	38,34	16,67	0,00	40,00	33,33	37,10
Scientific books	30,81	33,21	33,33	0,00	20,00	0,00	31,77
Universities	26,68	32,36	33,33	0,00	20,00	33,33	29,16
Web pages	25,14	28,08	0,00	0,00	20,00	33,33	26,33
Others	0,86	1,34	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	1,07
None	14,20	14,04	33,33	0,00	0,00	0,00	14,13

I don't know	9,69	7,20	0,00	100,00	40,00	33,33	8,74
Prefer not to answer	0,48	1,10	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,75

In the case of people who responded affirmatively to the question "among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?" the same response pattern is observed as in the previous case. The percentages of not having accessed information are 13.4% in the case of women and 12.28% in the case of men. Once again, scientific journals are the primary source of information, with 39.03% of women and 40.5% of men.

Table 5.82. Percentage of respondents who answered "YES" to the question "Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?" by gender.

	Woman	Man	Trans	Non binary	Fluid	Others	Prefer not to answer	Total
Initiative through news	24,76	26,56	0,00	20,00	66,67	22,22	0,00	25,58
Applications (apps)	11,21	9,71	0,00	20,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	10,42
Online platforms	29,00	28,71	0,00	20,00	33,33	11,11	0,00	28,69
Scientific journals	39,03	40,50	0,00	0,00	66,67	22,22	14,29	39,55
Scientific books	34,01	35,77	0,00	20,00	66,67	11,11	0,00	34,68
Universities	31,74	34,19	0,00	40,00	66,67	11,11	14,29	32,84
Web pages	28,21	29,96	0,00	0,00	33,33	11,11	42,86	28,97
Others	1,10	1,16	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	1,12
None	13,40	12,28	0,00	20,00	0,00	44,44	0,00	12,93
I don't know	9,56	6,89	100,00	40,00	0,00	22,22	28,57	8,46
Prefer not to answer	0,39	0,58	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	14,29	0,52

When analyzing the influence of interactions by the age of group, we observe how the percentage of participants answering negatively to the question “What kind of initiative do you know that helps distinguish scientific evidence from gender hoaxes well?” decreases from the 14.78% in 16-24 years old in women to 11.17% (relative to their perception about science and they are interested in it) and 9.22% (regarding following scientific person in social networks). In the case of men, these percentages also decrease from 15.62% to 9,11% and 9.71%. Again, scientific journals are the primary way to access information, with 38.58% in the case of women and 39.16% of men (relative to their perception about science and they are interested in it). Attending the second question on interactions (among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?) the main way to be informed in the case of women is not scientific journals, are Universities with the 38.91%.

Table 5.83. Percentage of respondents who answered “YES” to the question “Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?” by group of age.

	16-24	25-34	35-49	50-64	+65	Total
Initiative through news	25,89	22,41	22,77	25,80	26,03	24,15
Applications (apps)	16,24	19,21	12,14	6,85	2,89	11,67
Online platforms	30,96	33,74	27,32	20,78	17,36	26,28
Scientific journals	38,58	39,16	36,26	39,04	30,99	37,10
Scientific books	31,47	34,24	32,38	31,28	27,27	31,77
Universities	35,03	31,28	31,20	27,40	19,01	29,16
Web pages	32,99	29,80	30,19	20,78	15,70	26,33
Others	0,00	0,99	1,01	1,60	1,24	1,07
None	11,17	9,11	12,65	18,49	20,66	14,13
I don't know	6,09	6,40	9,27	10,27	10,74	8,74
Prefer not to answer	0,00	1,23	0,84	0,23	1,24	0,75

Table 5.84. Percentage of respondents who answered “YES” to the question “Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?” by group of age.

	16-24	25-34	35-49	50-64	+65	Total
Initiative through news	25,94	25,27	24,73	27,15	25,39	25,58
Applications (apps)	17,06	15,38	9,33	7,65	3,13	10,42
Online platforms	32,76	36,45	28,73	23,71	19,75	28,69
Scientific journals	36,86	39,38	38,55	41,49	41,69	39,55
Scientific books	34,81	34,25	35,39	34,42	33,86	34,68
Universities	38,91	34,07	32,00	33,65	26,02	32,84
Web pages	35,15	32,97	31,03	24,28	18,81	28,97
Others	0,68	0,18	0,97	2,29	1,57	1,12
None	9,22	9,71	13,21	15,68	16,61	12,93
I don't know	6,83	6,04	9,45	8,60	11,29	8,46
Prefer not to answer	0,00	0,55	0,61	0,57	0,63	0,52

In the case of ethnic minorities, answering positively to the questions regarding interactions impact positively in an increment of respondents who know initiatives that help distinguish scientific evidence from gender hoaxes. Without the questions on interactions, the percentage of respondents who answered “none” was 11.47%. This percentage decreases to 4.3% (for the first question on interactions “has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?”) and 4.94% (for the second one “among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?”). Interactions help to reduce percentages regarding the no reception of information.

Analyzing through which kind of media the participants receive the information and without information regarding interactions, the primary way is through scientific journals (31.55%) and online platforms (30.4%). The percentage regarding scientific journals is practically the same if

we add the positive answers to the questions on interactions from 31.55% to 32.81% (for the first question on interactions) and 34.22% (for the second one). The main way counting the interactions is the online platforms with 37.11% (for the first question on interactions) and 36.5% (for the second one).

Table 5.85. Percentage of respondents who answered “YES” to the question “Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?” by ethnic minority group.

	Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	Total
Initiative through news	30,86	23,83	12,63	14,29	24,15
Applications (apps)	23,44	9,73	11,58	7,14	11,67
Online platforms	37,11	24,82	22,11	14,29	26,28
Scientific journals	32,81	38,58	28,42	14,29	37,10
Scientific books	28,13	33,36	21,05	0,00	31,77
Universities	30,08	29,78	17,89	21,43	29,16
Web pages	27,34	26,54	20,00	28,57	26,33
Others	0,00	1,32	0,00	0,00	1,07
None	4,30	16,21	6,32	21,43	14,13
I don't know	6,64	8,74	13,68	14,29	8,74
Prefer not to answer	0,39	0,66	2,11	7,14	0,75

Table 86. Percentage of respondents who answered “YES” to the question “Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?” by ethnic minority group.

	Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	Total
Initiative through news	31,56	25,22	20,41	6,25	25,58
Applications (apps)	23,95	8,74	9,18	18,75	10,42
Online platforms	36,50	27,62	31,63	25,00	28,69
Scientific journals	34,22	40,44	38,78	12,50	39,55
Scientific books	30,80	35,65	28,57	6,25	34,68
Universities	31,94	33,49	23,47	18,75	32,84
Web pages	28,52	29,22	26,53	18,75	28,97
Others	0,38	1,22	1,02	0,00	1,12
None	4,18	13,95	11,22	31,25	12,93
I don't know	4,94	8,92	8,16	6,25	8,46
Prefer not to answer	0,00	0,52	0,00	12,50	0,52

The results on religious minority groups are like ethnic minorities. Without information regarding interactions, 14.73% of the participants who did not know any initiative to distinguish between scientific evidence and hoax in gender were from religious minority groups and 25.05% from non-religious minority groups. The 14.73% decreases to 8.48% within the participants of a religious minority group who answered “yes” to the first question centred on interactions (see table below). At the same time, scientific journals are the primary way to know about scientific evidence (32.71% without questions regarding interaction) and 34.63% when we consider the first question regarding interactions (see table below).

Table 5.87. Percentage of respondents who answered “YES” to the question “Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?” for belonging to a religious minority group.

	Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	Total
--	-----	----	---------------	----------------------	-------

Initiative through news	28,98	23,63	18,75	7,14	24,15
Applications (apps)	21,20	9,97	10,94	7,14	11,67
Online platforms	32,16	25,48	23,44	7,14	26,28
Scientific journals	34,63	38,09	28,13	21,43	37,10
Scientific books	29,33	32,67	21,88	28,57	31,77
Universities	29,33	29,37	23,44	28,57	29,16
Web pages	28,27	26,47	14,06	28,57	26,33
Others	0,35	1,25	0,00	0,00	1,07
None	8,48	15,18	10,94	28,57	14,13
I don't know	5,65	9,11	10,94	21,43	8,74
Prefer not to answer	0,71	0,73	1,56	0,00	0,75

In the case of how answering the second question on interactions (see table below) affects accessing information on scientific evidence, the results show a similar pattern than the previous one. In this case, the percentage regarding scientific journals is 39.14% (5 point higher than the previous one). Accessing through scientific books also increases reaching 34.25%.

Table 5.88. Percentage of respondents who answered “YES” to the question “Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?” for belonging to a religious minority group.

	Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	Total
Initiative through news	29,66	25,26	20,31	5,88	25,58
Applications (apps)	18,65	9,15	9,38	11,76	10,42

Online platforms	32,72	28,31	25,00	11,76	28,69
Scientific journals	39,14	40,09	32,81	5,88	39,55
Scientific books	34,25	35,03	29,69	17,65	34,68
Universities	32,72	33,17	26,56	17,65	32,84
Web pages	29,66	29,31	17,19	17,65	28,97
Others	0,61	1,19	1,56	0,00	1,12
None	9,48	13,58	6,25	23,53	12,93
I don't know	3,67	8,91	14,06	23,53	8,46
Prefer not to answer	0,31	0,52	0,00	5,88	0,52

Regarding participants by household annual income, scientific journals is the main way to access to scientific information by people less than 10,562 and between 10,562 and 16,043€ with 33.88% in the first case, and 36.86€ in the second one (see table 89). The same percentage increases to a 40% among people under 10,562€ in the case of the second question regarding interactions (see table 90). Scientific books are the second way to access information for the people with less economic resources with 37.44%.

Table 5.89. Percentage of respondents who answered “YES” to the question “Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?” by household annual income in euros.

	Less than 10,562	10.562-16.043	16.044-23.295	More than 23.295	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	Total
Initiative through news	22,22	29,69	22,32	26,60	15,71	18,27	24,15
Applications (apps)	10,57	13,65	12,84	12,48	5,71	8,65	11,67
Online platforms	29,54	26,28	28,44	26,11	22,86	18,75	26,28
Scientific journals	33,88	36,86	36,09	41,38	24,29	36,54	37,10

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement num. 872396

Scientific books	30,89	35,15	29,66	34,32	20,00	28,37	31,77
Universities	29,27	27,30	29,05	32,18	20,00	25,96	29,16
Web pages	28,18	22,53	24,46	29,06	27,14	23,08	26,33
Others	0,81	0,68	0,61	1,15	1,43	2,40	1,07
None	13,28	12,29	13,46	12,97	17,14	21,63	14,13
I don't know	8,40	7,85	7,95	7,88	18,57	11,06	8,74
Prefer not to answer	1,36	0,34	0,31	0,49	1,43	1,44	0,75

Table 5.90. Percentage of respondents who answered “YES” to the question “Among the people you follow on social networks, is there a scientific person or person interested in science?” by household annual income in euros.

	Less than 10,562	10.562- 16.043	16.044- 23.295	More than 23.295	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	Total
Initiative through news	25,35	28,23	26,36	26,62	21,88	18,63	25,58
Applications (apps)	10,70	12,63	12,66	9,50	8,33	7,60	10,42
Online platforms	30,47	29,30	34,88	28,08	25,00	19,39	28,69
Scientific journals	40,00	36,83	36,69	42,69	34,38	37,26	39,55
Scientific books	37,44	33,87	34,63	35,39	29,17	30,80	34,68
Universities	36,28	26,34	31,78	35,28	30,21	30,04	32,84
Web pages	30,70	28,49	28,17	29,33	28,13	27,00	28,97
Others	0,70	0,54	1,81	1,04	1,04	1,90	1,12

None	9,77	12,63	13,95	13,36	13,54	15,21	12,93
I don't know	6,98	6,99	4,91	8,66	11,46	16,35	8,46
Prefer not to answer	0,93	0,54	0,26	0,31	0,00	1,14	0,52

Analysis of the impact of social interactions on the recognition (or not-recognition) of scientific evidence or education hoaxes

Linear regression could not be done because after building several predictive models to explain the variance of the dependent variables, in all cases the homoscedasticity criterion was not met, so we cannot ensure that the errors are normally distributed, and that means that we could incur in interpretations induced by a certain structure that does not correspond to the real distribution of the variable. For this reason, we have limited ourselves to studying the possible associations between variables, but we have decided not to assume a causal relationship on which to generate a predictive model to explain the dependent variables.

Among people who say that something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science, 75.4% do not use news as a source to discern between scientific evidences or fake news in education, compared to 24.6% who do.

Table 5.91. Initiative through the news by Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science.

		Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	Total
Not Initiative through the news	Count	1415	4010	563	105	6093
	% Within Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science	75,4%	82,6%	86,0%	88,2%	81,2%
Initiative through the news	Count	461	847	92		1414
	% Within Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science	24,6%	17,4%	14,0%	11,8%	18,8%

Count	1876	4857	655		7507
% Within Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%

The chi-square test has a significance of 0.000, less than 0.05, so we reject the null hypothesis and can affirm that there is a relationship between the two variables: those who for some reason are interested in science do not use the news as a source to distinguish between scientific evidence and fake in education.

Table 92: Chi-square tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic significance (bilateral)
Pearson's Chi-square	60,322 ^a		0,000
Likelihood ratio	58,945		0,000
Linear by linear association	55,188	1	0,000
N of valid cases	7507		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have an expected count of less than 5. The minimum expected count is 22.41.

Table 5.93: Symmetrical measurements

	Value	Asymptotic standard error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	0,090		0,000
	V for Cramer	0,090		0,000
	Contingency ratio	0,089		0,000
N of valid cases	7507			

a. The null hypothesis is not assumed.

b. Use of the asymptotic standard error that assumes the null hypothesis.

c. It is based on normal approximation.

When testing specifically for nominal variables, the results continue to confirm that there is a relationship between the two variables, and that the relationship is significant.

In the case of people who use apps to differentiate between scientific evidence and fake news in education, we see that those who have experienced something that made them to change their minds about science or become interested in science, 90.2% do not use apps as a source, while 9.8% do. This is similar to what happens among people who have not experienced something that made them interested in science. But if we look at the differences between those

who use apps and those who do not, then we see that it does seem that having had an experience that made you change your mind about science of becoming interested in science does seem to have some impact, because for those who do not use apps the difference is much larger than for those who do use apps (24% to 65.6% versus 40% to 50.2% respectively).

Table 5.94: Applications by Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?

		Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	Total
Not Applications (apps)	Count	1692	4626	615	114	7047
	% within Applications (apps)	24,0%	65,6%	8,7%	1,6%	100,0%
	% within Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science	90,2%	95,2%	93,9%	95,8%	93,9%
Applications (apps)	Count	184	231		5	460
	% within Applications (apps)	40,0%	50,2%	8,7%	1,1%	100,0%
	% within Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science	9,8%	4,8%	6,1%	4,2%	6,1%
Count		1876	4857	655		7507
% within Applications (apps)		25,0%	64,7%	8,7%	1,6%	100,0%
% within Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science		100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%

Reviewing the results of the chi-square test, we see that this relationship is significant.

Table 5.95: Chi-square tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic significance (bilateral)
Pearson's Chi-square	60,832 ^a		0,000
Likelihood ratio	55,755		0,000
Linear by linear association	32,861	1	0,000
N of valid cases	7507		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected a count of less than 5. The minimum expected count is 7.29.

Specific tests for nominal variables confirm this result:

Table 5.96: Symmetrical measurements

	Value	Asymptotic standard error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate significance
Nominal by Phi	0,090			0,000
Nominal V for Cramer	0,090			0,000
Contingency ratio	0,090			0,000
N of valid cases	7507			

- a. The null hypothesis is not assumed.
- b. Use of the asymptotic standard error that assumes the null hypothesis.
- c. It is based on normal approximation.

Regarding the use (or not) of online platforms, the results are similar. When people have experienced something that made them to change their minds about science or become interested in science, then they tend to give less value to information in education that comes through online platforms (73.7% do not use them compared to 26.3%); while those who have not experienced anything that made them interested in science 85.2% do not use online platforms, compared to 14.8% who do use them.

Table 5.97: Online platforms by Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?

		Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	Total
Not Online Platforms	Count	1382	4044	558	104	6088
	% within online platforms	22,7%	66,4%	9,2%	1,7%	100,0%
	% within Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science	73,7%	83,3%	85,2%	87,4%	81,1%
online platforms	Count	494	813			1419
	% within online platforms	34,8%	57,3%	6,8%	1,1%	100,0%
	% within Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science	26,3%	16,7%	14,8%	12,6%	18,9%
	Count	1876	4857	655		7507
	% within online platforms	25,0%	64,7%	8,7%	1,6%	100,0%

% within Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%
---	--------	--------	--------	--------	--------

The chi-square test indicates that this relationship is significant.

Table 5.98: Chi-square tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic (bilateral)	significance
Pearson's Chi-square	92,634 ^a		0,000	
Likelihood ratio	88,243		0,000	
Linear by linear association	74,396	1	0,000	
N of valid cases	7507			

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected a count of less than 5. The minimum expected count is 22.49.

And specific measures for nominal variables confirm the same conclusion.

Table 5.99: Symmetrical measurements

	Value	Asymptotic standard error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate significance
Nominal by Phi	0,111			0,000
Nominal by V for Cramer	0,111			0,000
Nominal by Contingency ratio	0,110			0,000
Interval by Pearson's R	-0,100	0,012	-8,668	,000 ^c
Ordinal by Spearman correlation	-0,105	0,012	-9,180	,000 ^c
N of valid cases	7507			

a. The null hypothesis is not assumed.

b. Use of the asymptotic standard error that assumes the null hypothesis.

c. It is based on normal approximation.

In the case of using scientific magazines as a source to access and contrast information in education, we see that there is an increase in using scientific journals among those who are interested in science than among those who say that nothing has happened to them to make them interested in science (32.4% versus 21.7%; and 60.4% versus 66.6% respectively). When we focus specifically on those who say that something did happen to them that made them to change their minds about science or become interested in science, we see that 39.5% use scientific magazines (versus 28.5% who do not). This trend is reversed when people have not had anything happen to them that made them interested in science.

Table 5.100: Scientific magazines by Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?

		Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	Total
Not Scientific journals	Count	1135	3475	514	95	5219
	% within Scientific magazines	21,7%	66,6%	9,8%	1,8%	100,0%
	% within Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science	60,5%	71,5%	78,5%	79,8%	69,5%
Scientific magazines	Count	741	1382			2288
	% within Scientific magazines	32,4%	60,4%	6,2%	1,0%	100,0%
	% within Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science	39,5%	28,5%	21,5%	20,2%	30,5%
Count		1876	4857	655		7507
% within Scientific magazines		25,0%	64,7%	8,7%	1,6%	100,0%
% within Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science		100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%

Again, both the chi-square and the symmetric measures confirm this trend.

Table 5.101: Chi-square tests

	Value	gl	Asymptotic significance (bilateral)
Pearson's Chi-square	112,179 ^a		0,000
Likelihood ratio	111,167		0,000
Linear by linear association	104,442	1	0,000
N of valid cases	7507		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have an expected count of less than 5. The minimum expected count is 36.27.

Table 5.102: Symmetrical measurements

		Value	Asymptotic standard error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	0,122			0,000
	V for Cramer	0,122			0,000
	Contingency ratio	0,121			0,000
N of valid cases		7507			

a. The null hypothesis is not assumed.

- b. Use of the asymptotic standard error that assumes the null hypothesis.
- c. It is based on normal approximation.

In the case of the use of scientific books, the same happens as with scientific journals: among those who use them as a source, it is more common among those who had something that made them to change their minds about science or become interested in science (32.6%) than among those who had nothing happen to them (23.1%). In other words, using scientific books as a source of information is indeed a trend among those who are interested in science.

Table 5.103: Scientific books by Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?

		Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	Total
Not Scientific Books	Count	1264	3735	531		5627
	% within Scientific books	22,5%	66,4%	9,4%	1,7%	100,0%
	% within Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science	67,4%	76,9%	81,1%	81,5%	75,0%
Scientific books	Count	612	1122	124		1880
	% within Scientific books	32,6%	59,7%	6,6%	1,2%	100,0%
	% within Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science	32,6%	23,1%	18,9%	18,5%	25,0%
	Count	1876	4857	655		7507
	% within Scientific books	25,0%	64,7%	8,7%	1,6%	100,0%
	% within Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%

Chi-square tests show that this is a relationship that is significant.

Table 104: Chi-square tests

	Value	gl	Asymptotic significance (bilateral)
Pearson's Chi-square	82,934 ^a		0,000
Likelihood ratio	80,848		0,000
Linear by linear association	72,421	1	0,000
N of valid cases	7507		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have an expected count of less than 5. The minimum expected count is 29.80.

Table 105: Symmetrical measurements

			Value	Asymptotic standard error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate significance
Nominal	by	Phi	0,105			0,000
Nominal		V for Cramer	0,105			0,000
		Contingency ratio	0,105			0,000
N of valid cases			7507			

a. The null hypothesis is not assumed.

b. Use of the asymptotic standard error that assumes the null hypothesis.

c. It is based on normal approximation.

Looking at the same question but among those who use university sources as a resource to cross-check information in education and distinguish whether or not it is scientific evidence, we see that among those who did have something happen to them that made them to change their minds about science or become interested in science, the majority do use university sources to cross-check information (31.9% vs. 22.6%).

Table 5.106: Universities by Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?

		Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	Total
Not Universities	Count	1262	3700	524		5582
	% within Universities	22,6%	66,3%	9,4%	1,7%	100,0%
	% within Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science	67,3%	76,2%	80,0%	80,7%	74,4%
Universities	Count	614	1157	131		1925
	% within Universities	31,9%	60,1%	6,8%	1,2%	100,0%
	% within Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science	32,7%	23,8%	20,0%	19,3%	25,6%
Count		1876	4857	655		7507
% within Universities		25,0%	64,7%	8,7%	1,6%	100,0%
% within Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you		100,0 %	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%

change your mind about science
or become interested in science

Again, chi-square tests confirm that this is a significant relationship.

Table 107: Chi-square tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic significance (bilateral)
Pearson's Chi-square	71,287 ^a		0,000
Likelihood ratio	69,625		0,000
Linear by linear association	62,308	1	0,000
N of valid cases	7507		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have an expected count of less than 5. The minimum expected count is 30.51.

Table 108: Symmetrical measurements

		Value	Asymptotic standard error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	0,097			0,000
	V for Cramer	0,097			0,000
	Contingency ratio	0,097			0,000
N of valid cases		7507			

a. The null hypothesis is not assumed.

b. Use of the asymptotic standard error that assumes the null hypothesis.

c. It is based on normal approximation.

In the case of websites, something different happens people who show interest in science consult them less as a source for differences between scientific evidence and fake in education than people who have not had anything happen to them that made them to change their minds about science or become interested in science (34.2% vs. 58% respectively).

Table 5.109: Web sites by Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science

		Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	Total
Not web pages	Count	1342	3952		113	5947
	% within Websites	22,6%	66,5%	9,1%	1,9%	100,0%
	% within Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science	71,5%	81,4%	82,4%	95,0%	79,2%
Websites	Count	534	905	115		1560
	% within Websites	34,2%	58,0%	7,4%	0,4%	100,0%

% within Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science	28,5%	18,6%	17,6%	5,0%	20,8%
Count	1876	4857	655		7507
% within Websites	25,0%	64,7%	8,7%	1,6%	100,0%
% within Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Both the chi-square test and the symmetric measures confirm again that this relationship appears to be significant.

Table 5.110: Chi-square tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic significance (bilateral)
Pearson's Chi-square	102,937 ^a		0,000
Likelihood ratio	104,433		0,000
Linear by linear association	86,724	1	0,000
N of valid cases	7507		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have an expected count of less than 5. The minimum expected count is 24.73.

Table 5.111: Symmetrical measurements

	Value	Asymptotic standard error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	0,117		0,000
	V for Cramer	0,117		0,000
	Contingency ratio	0,116		0,000
N of valid cases	7507			

a. The null hypothesis is not assumed.

b. Use of the asymptotic standard error that assumes the null hypothesis.

c. It is based on normal approximation.

Among those who answer this question with "none" (i.e. who explicitly state that they do not use any means to distinguish between scientific evidence and fake in education), the vast majority (more than 3 out of 4 people) show no interest in science (79.2%).

Table 5.112: None by Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science.

		Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	Total
Not None	Count	1671	3699	570	105	6045
	% within None	27,6%	61,2%	9,4%	1,7%	100,0%
	% within Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science	89,1%	76,2%	87,0%	88,2%	80,5%
None	Count	205	1158	85		1462
	% within None	14,0%	79,2%	5,8%	1,0%	100,0%
	% within Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science	10,9%	23,8%	13,0%	11,8%	19,5%
Count		1876	4857	655		7507
% within None		25,0%	64,7%	8,7%	1,6%	100,0%
% within Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science		100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%

Again, this trend is confirmed when the chi-square is calculated as a significant association.

Table 5.113: Chi-square tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic significance (bilateral)
Pearson's Chi-square	168,605 ^a		0,000
Likelihood ratio	180,852		0,000
Linear by linear association	21,904	1	0,000
N of valid cases	7507		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected a count of less than 5. The minimum expected count is 23.18.

Table 5.114: Symmetrical measurements

	Value	Asymptotic standard error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate significance
Nominal by Phi	0,150			0,000
Nominal	V for Cramer	0,150		0,000
	Contingency ratio	0,148		0,000
N of valid cases	7507			

- a. The null hypothesis is not assumed.
- b. Use of the asymptotic standard error that assumes the null hypothesis.
- c. It is based on normal approximation.

Analysis of the impact of social interactions on the recognition (or not-recognition) of scientific evidence or Gender hoaxes

In the following, we will analyse the impact of interactions on the use (or not) of different sources of information to see whether what is said about gender is (or is not) scientific evidence or hoax.

According to the responses to the questionnaire, those who are interested in science because something happened to them that made them to change their minds about science or become interested in science, tend not to use the news as a source to distinguish between what is and what is not scientific evidence in gender (75.9% versus 24.1% who do).

Table 5.115: News by Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?

		Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	Total
Not Initiative through the news	Count	1423	3982	574	103	6082
	% within Initiative through news	23,4%	65,5%	9,4%	1,7%	100,0%
	% within Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science	75,9%	82,0%	87,6%	86,6%	81,0%
Initiative through the news	Count	453	875	81		1425
	% within Initiative through news	31,8%	61,4%	5,7%	1,1%	100,0%
	% within Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science	24,1%	18,0%	12,4%	13,4%	19,0%
Count		1876	4857	655		7507
% within Initiative through news		25,0%	64,7%	8,7%	1,6%	100,0%

% within Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%
---	--------	--------	--------	--------	--------

This trend is significant, when the chi-square test is checked.

Table 116: Chi-square tests

	Value	gl	Asymptotic significance (bilateral)
Pearson's Chi-square	56,507 ^a		0,000
Likelihood ratio	56,834		0,000
Linear by linear association	53,156	1	0,000
N of valid cases	7507		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected a count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 22.59.

Table 117: Symmetrical measurements

	Value	Asymptotic standard error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate significance
Nominal by Phi	0,087			0,000
Nominal V for Cramer	0,087			0,000
Contingency ratio	0,086			0,000
Interval by Pearson's R	-0,084	0,011	-7,316	,000 ^c
Ordinal by ordinal Spearman correlation	-0,087	0,012	-7,528	,000 ^c
N of valid cases	7507			

a. The null hypothesis is not assumed.

b. Use of the asymptotic standard error that assumes the null hypothesis.

c. It is based on normal approximation.

If we look at what happens when using apps as a source of information, the same thing happens as in the previous case. People who are interested in science do not usually use apps as a source of data to check whether or not it is scientific evidence or a gender fake.

Table 5.118: Apps by Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science.

	Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	Total
Count	1657	4634	622		7031

Not Applications (apps)	% within Applications (apps)	23,6%	65,9%	8,8%	1,7%	100,0%
	% within Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science	88,3%	95,4%	95,0%	99,2%	93,7%
Applications (apps)	Count	219	223		1	476
	% within Applications (apps)	46,0%	46,8%	6,9%	0,2%	100,0%
	% within Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science	11,7%	4,6%	5,0%	0,8%	6,3%
	Count	1876	4857	655		7507
	% within Applications (apps)	25,0%	64,7%	8,7%	1,6%	100,0%
	% within Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%

Table 119: Chi-square tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic significance (bilateral)
Pearson's Chi-square	122,808 ^a		0,000
Likelihood ratio	112,011		0,000
Linear by linear association	86,594	1	0,000
N of valid cases	7507		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected a count of less than 5. The minimum expected count is 7.55.

Table 120: Symmetrical measurements

	Value	Asymptotic standard error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate significance
Nominal by Phi	0,128			0,000
Nominal V for Cramer	0,128			0,000
Contingency ratio	0,127			0,000
N of valid cases	7507			

a. The null hypothesis is not assumed.

b. Use of the asymptotic standard error that assumes the null hypothesis.

c. It is based on normal approximation.

When we look at the results regarding the use of online platforms as a source, we see that the trend we have been discussing in the previous cases is reproduced again: people who show

interest in science do not use online platforms as a source to contrast information and distinguish between scientific evidence and gender fakes.

Table 5.121: Online platforms by Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?

		Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	Total
Not Online Platforms	Count	1383	4112	564	109	6168
	% within Online platforms	22,4%	66,7%	9,1%	1,8%	100,0%
	% within Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science	73,7%	84,7%	86,1%	91,6%	82,2%
Online platforms	Count	493	745	91		1339
	% within Online platforms	36,8%	55,6%	6,8%	0,7%	100,0%
	% within Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science	26,3%	15,3%	13,9%	8,4%	17,8%
Count		1876	4857	655		7507
% within Online platforms		25,0%	64,7%	8,7%	1,6%	100,0%
% within Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science		100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%

Table 122: Chi-square tests

	Value	Gf	Asymptotic significance (bilateral)
Pearson's Chi-square	126,099 ^a		0,000
Likelihood ratio	119,739		0,000
Linear by linear association	101,240	1	0,000
N of valid cases	7507		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected a count of less than 5. The minimum expected count is 21.23.

Table 123: Symmetrical measurements

	Value	Asymptotic standard error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate significance
Phi	0,130			0,000
V for Cramer	0,130			0,000

Nominal by Nominal	Contingency ratio	0,129			0,000
N of valid cases		7507			

- a. The null hypothesis is not assumed.
- b. Use of the asymptotic standard error that assumes the null hypothesis.
- c. It is based on normal approximation.

In the case of the use of scientific journals to contrast information on gender, we see that there is a change in the trend: people who show an interest in science tend to use scientific journals to distinguish between scientific evidence and fake gender (33.3% versus 21.8% respectively). On the other hand, among those who do not show interest in science, the relationship is reversed (66.8% of those who do not use scientific journals to cross-check information, versus 59.4% who do).

Table 5.124: Scientific journals by Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science.

		Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	Total
Not Scientific journals	Count	1180	3618	522	100	5420
	% within Scientific journals	21,8%	66,8%	9,6%	1,8%	100,0%
	% within Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science	62,9%	74,5%	79,7%	84,0%	72,2%
Scientific magazines	Count	696	1239	133		2087
	% within Scientific journals	33,3%	59,4%	6,4%	0,9%	100,0%
	% within Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science	37,1%	25,5%	20,3%	16,0%	27,8%
Count		1876	4857	655		7507
% within Scientific journals		25,0%	64,7%	8,7%	1,6%	100,0%
% within Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science		100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%

Chi-square tests confirm that this change in trend is significant.

Table 125: Chi-square tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic significance (bilateral)
Pearson's Chi-square	120,167 ^a		0,000
Likelihood ratio	118,022		0,000
Linear by linear association	109,661	1	0,000
N of valid cases	7507		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected a count of less than 5. The minimum expected count is 33.08.

Table 126: Symmetrical measurements

		Value	Asymptotic standard error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	0,127			0,000
	V for Cramer	0,127			0,000
	Contingency ratio	0,126			0,000
Interval by interval	Pearson's R	-0,121	0,011	-10,549	,000 ^c
Ordinal by ordinal	Spearman correlation	-0,125	0,012	-10,881	,000 ^c
N of valid cases		7507			

a. The null hypothesis is not assumed.

b. Use of the asymptotic standard error that assumes the null hypothesis.

c. It is based on normal approximation.

This trend is maintained in the case of those who use scientific books as a source. Here it is also the case that those who show an interest in science use scientific books as a source more than those who do not (33.1% compared to 22.4%).

Table 5.127: Scientific books by Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?

		Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	Total
Not Scientific Books	Count	1280	3783	541	103	5707
	% within Scientific books	22,4%	66,3%	9,5%	1,8%	100,0%
	% within Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science	68,2%	77,9%	82,6%	86,6%	76,0%
Scientific books	Count	596	1074	114		1800
	% within Scientific books	33,1%	59,7%	6,3%	0,9%	100,0%
	% within Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science	31,8%	22,1%	17,4%	13,4%	24,0%
Count		1876	4857	655		7507

% within Scientific books	25,0%	64,7%	8,7%	1,6%	100,0%
% within Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%

The chi-square analysis confirms that this relationship is significant.

Table 128: Chi-square tests

	Value	gl	Asymptotic significance (bilateral)
Pearson's Chi-square	94,524 ^a		0,000
Likelihood ratio	92,920		0,000
Linear by linear association	87,520	1	0,000
N of valid cases	7507		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected a count of less than 5. The minimum expected count is 28.53.

Table 129: Symmetrical measurements

	Value	Asymptotic standard error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate significance
Nominal by Phi	0,112			0,000
Nominal V for Cramer	0,112			0,000
Contingency ratio	0,112			0,000
Interval by interval Pearson's R	-0,108	0,011	-9,410	,000 ^c
Ordinal by ordinal Spearman correlation	-0,111	0,012	-9,664	,000 ^c
N of valid cases	7507			

a. The null hypothesis is not assumed.

b. Use of the asymptotic standard error that assumes the null hypothesis.

c. It is based on normal approximation.

It is similar in the case of using university sources as a source of contrasting information.

Table 5.130: Universities by Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science?

		Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	Total
Not Universities	Count	1329	3878	545	102	5854
	% within Universities	22,7%	66,2%	9,3%	1,7%	100,0%
	% within Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about	70,8%	79,8%	83,2%	85,7%	78,0%

	science or become interested in science					
Universities	Count	547	979	110		1653
	% within Universities	33,1%	59,2%	6,7%	1,0%	100,0%
	% within Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science	29,2%	20,2%	16,8%	14,3%	22,0%
	Count	1876	4857	655		7507
	% within Universities	25,0%	64,7%	8,7%	1,6%	100,0%
	% within Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%

The chi-square test confirms that this is a significant relationship.

131: Chi-square tests

	Value	gl	Asymptotic significance (bilateral)
Pearson's Chi-square	80,050 ^a		0,000
Likelihood ratio	77,715		0,000
Linear by linear association	70,405	1	0,000
N of valid cases	7507		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected a count of less than 5. The minimum expected count is 26.20.

132: Symmetrical measurements

		Value	Asymptotic standard error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	0,103			0,000
	V for Cramer	0,103			0,000
	Contingency ratio	0,103			0,000
N of valid cases		7507			

a. The null hypothesis is not assumed.

b. Use of the asymptotic standard error that assumes the null hypothesis.

c. It is based on normal approximation.

In the case of people who use information from websites to check whether something is or is not scientific evidence on gender, the data indicate that those who are interested in science do use websites as a source of information (34.1% compared to 22.8% who do not use them).

Table 5.133: Web sites by Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science.

		Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	Total
Not web pages	Count	1382	4010	560	108	6060
	% within Web pages	22,8%	66,2%	9,2%	1,8%	100,0%
	% within Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science	73,7%	82,6%	85,5%	90,8%	80,7%
Websites	Count	494	847	95		1447
	% within Web pages	34,1%	58,5%	6,6%	0,8%	100,0%
	% within Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science	26,3%	17,4%	14,5%	9,2%	19,3%
	Count	1876	4857	655		7507
	% within Web pages	25,0%	64,7%	8,7%	1,6%	100,0%
	% within Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%

The chi-square test confirms this relationship.

Table 134: Chi-square tests

	Value	Gl	Asymptotic (bilateral)	significance
Pearson's Chi-square	87,857 ^a		0,000	
Likelihood ratio	85,587		0,000	
Linear by linear association	78,508	1	0,000	
N of valid cases	7507			

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have an expected count of less than 5. The minimum expected count is 22.94.

Table 135: Symmetrical measurements

		Value	Asymptotic standard error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	0,108			0,000
	V for Cramer	0,108			0,000
	Contingency ratio	0,108			0,000
Interval by interval	Pearson's R	-0,102	0,011	-8,907	,000 ^c

Ordinal by ordinal	Spearman correlation	-0,105	0,012	-9,154	,000 ^c
N of valid cases		7507			

- a. The null hypothesis is not assumed.
- b. Use of the asymptotic standard error that assumes the null hypothesis.
- c. It is based on normal approximation.

Finally, people who say they do not use any kind of source to check whether a piece of information about gender is scientific evidence or a fake, in most cases are people who say that nothing has happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science.

Table 5.136: None by Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science.

		Yes	No	I do not know	Prefer not to answer	Total
None	Count	1611	3464	532	103	5710
	% within None	28,2%	60,7%	9,3%	1,8%	100,0%
	% within Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science	85,9%	71,3%	81,2%	86,6%	76,1%
None	Count	265	1393	123		1797
	% within None	14,7%	77,5%	6,8%	0,9%	100,0%
	% within Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science	14,1%	28,7%	18,8%	13,4%	23,9%
Count		1876	4857	655		7507
% within None		25,0%	64,7%	8,7%	1,6%	100,0%
% within Has something happened to you or someone in your family that made you change your mind about science or become interested in science		100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%

The chi-square test indicates that this relationship is also significant.

Table 137: Chi-square tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic significance (bilateral)
Pearson's Chi-square	175,963 ^a		0,000
Likelihood ratio	187,213		0,000
Linear by linear association	29,958	1	0,000
N of valid cases	7507		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have an expected count of less than 5. The minimum expected count is 28.49.

Table 138: Symmetrical measurements

			Value	Asymptotic standard error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate significance
Nominal	by	Phi	0,153			0,000
Nominal		V for Cramer	0,153			0,000
		Contingency ratio	0,151			0,000
Interval interval	by	Pearson's R	0,063	0,010	5,484	,000 ^c
Ordinal by ordinal		Spearman correlation	0,083	0,010	7,228	,000 ^c
N of valid cases			7507			

a. The null hypothesis is not assumed.

b. Use of the asymptotic standard error that assumes the null hypothesis.

c. It is based on normal approximation.

Science targeting different social groups

Existing scientific literature highlights that the biggest number of initiatives follow a top-down approach. Similarly, SMA indicates that most of the initiatives did not target specifically any group, but were addressed to the whole society. However, some of the interventions were addressed to **specific** social actors, such as **vulnerable groups** (including women, children and youth), or **professionals** (such as teaching staff or policymakers). In FG, participants declared that participation in the discussion of everyday topics with scientific evidence increases self-confidence in people who are not used to get involved in these matters or do not have the right tools or platforms to get access to. Thus, we conclude that disseminating the social impact of science is important. In the same line, survey results showcase those **respondents who interacted with science** through both analysed interactions (living a situation that changed their mind about science and following a scientist on social media) **were more likely to receive information about scientific results on gender and education**. Therefore, it is important to create initiatives that can become a space in where **different audiences can interact**, so new ideas and knowledge can come up as a result.

Social Media to engage with different social actors

Social media can serve as an egalitarian space where different social actors can engage in scientific discussions. This importance has been identified in all data collection techniques. On the one hand, quantitative results from SMA indicate that (with one exception) **the presence of scientific evidence on the identified initiatives is majoritarian**, ranging from 64,28% to 86,26% in education and from 55.91% to 80.39% in gender. In addition, on Twitter and Reddit, **messages with scientific evidence tend to be given more retweets or punctuation**, in comparison with messages without scientific evidence. Similarly, survey participants expressed that in both, gender and education, **the most common communication tool used to receive information about scientific research were social networks** (14.1% and 12.7%). In addition, people from vulnerable groups were more likely to express using social media to learn about science and the percentages increased due to interactions with science.

Figure 6.2. Use of social media to learn scientific evidence in gender and education

On the other hand, qualitative data supports this finding. For instance, women participants in FG declared to rely more on social media compared to people from older ages and SMCO results showcase that scientific argumentation has fostered participation and virtual dialogue among users on concepts of education and/or gender.

Science with power to transform people's lives

Across all the implemented techniques, a common finding has been the potential of science of transforming and improving citizens' lives. Citizens are aware of some of these examples of social impact of research. In this vein, a wide majority (more than 90%) of citizens interactions on SMA included **transformative examples of initiatives that were increasing citizens' awareness of the social impact of research.**

Figure 6.3. Transformative messages on social media across strategies and topics

In the same vein, FG results showcase **that science is recognized as very important for people's lives, especially in fields such as medicine.** Scientific research is also perceived as a key element to re-configure some social beliefs, like what it really means the Women's International Day, for example. People can actually understand what this day means and, as a consequence, change their mind. Although the term "science" was not always well received by younger generations, which could have an impact in the way they engage with it, scientific research is perceived as a key element to reconfigure some social beliefs, according to FG participants. Finally, FG respondents emphasized **the awareness of the importance of scientific research is directly connected with the degree of people's trust in the field.**

Science and scientific evidence play a key role in a world facing new challenges: fake news and hoaxes

Among the main initiatives to raise citizens' awareness of social impact of scientific research, those that aim to provide tools to distinguish scientific evidence from hoaxes are given special consideration. In this sense, LGBTIQ+ participants in the FG expressed that it is key to disseminate research and scientific information and results at a large scale, which in turn will

help to stop fake news. Quantitative data points to the same direction and **more than half of the respondents** of the survey knew **at least one initiative to distinguish scientific evidence from hoax** in education and gender. The most known initiative were **scientific magazines**. Survey results also stressed that both analysed **interactions with science** (living a situation that changed their mind about science and following a scientist on social media), **promoted citizens' knowledge of initiatives to distinguish scientific evidence from hoax** in gender and education.

Figure 6.4. Knowledge of initiatives to distinguish scientific evidence from hoaxes in gender and education

The following report was prepared with the aim of explaining the objectives, techniques, methodologies and results that respond to Objective 2: explore the initiatives that are already making societal actors aware of the connection between the solutions they appreciate and the scientific research that led to them. Regarding the project objectives, it provides a better understanding about the general and specific objectives of ALLINTERACT project. Finally, it offers an overview about the preliminary results and conclusions, which respond to O2. Data gathered and analysed for O2, brought new insights on citizens' awareness of the impact of scientific research, including the identification of elements fostering (transformative dimension) and hindering (exclusionary dimension) their access to those benefits. Also, it provided fundamental information about specific groups and communities and their relationship with science and their perceptions about this field of knowledge, as well as their opinions about scientific research and the importance of counting on validated content in an era in full with fake news and hoaxes. In addition, it stressed the importance of social media as channels and platforms that science must continue using in order to disseminate results and engage with different targets. All the analyses were then integrated in the core Report 2 under the title "Initiatives which are making societal actors aware of the scientific research that led to the solutions they appreciate", giving answer to O2.